

United States Department of the Interior

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Sent Electronically

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Regulatory Division Chief
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Subject: Final Formal Consultation on the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project near the City of Morgan Hill, Santa Clara County, California and Partial Coverage under the Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan (Federal Energy Regulatory Commission [FERC] Project No. 5737-000-California Anderson Dam Hydroelectric, Santa Clara Valley Water District)

Dear Jennifer Polardino and Regulatory Division Chief:

This letter is in response to FERC's September 10, 2024, request for initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project (proposed project) near the City of Morgan Hill, Santa Clara County, California. FERC's request was received by the Service on September 10, 2024. FERC is the federal lead agency for the proposed project while the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (Corps) is a consulting agency. Both FERC and the Corps requested the initiation of formal consultation with the Service to cover the effects of each agency's proposed federal actions. The scope of each agency's proposed federal actions is summarized below and in Table 1. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally listed as threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*) and its designated critical habitat, threatened Central Distinct Population Segment of the California tiger salamander (Central California tiger salamander) (*Ambystoma californiense*), threatened Central Coast Distinct Population Segment of the foothill yellow-legged frog (Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog) (*Rana boylei*), threatened Bay checkerspot butterfly (*Euphydryas editha bayensis*) and its designated critical habitat, endangered Santa Clara Valley

dudleya (*Dudleya setchellii*), endangered Tiburon paintbrush (*Castilleja affinis* ssp. *neglecta*), endangered Coyote ceanothus (*Ceanothus ferrisiae*), endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), threatened Pacific Coast population of the western snowy plover (western snowy plover) (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*), endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of the longfin smelt (longfin smelt) (*Spirinchus thaleichthys*), and proposed threatened northwestern pond turtle (*Actinemys marmorata*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402). Critical habitat has been designated for the Central California tiger salamander and western snowy plover but does not occur within the action area.

The federal action on which we are consulting with FERC is Valley Water's petition pursuant to 18 C.F.R. § 4.102 (2022), where Valley Water, as the exemptee of the Anderson Dam Project No. 5737, proposes to fully retrofit Anderson Dam and conditionally surrender its small hydropower exemption from licensing¹. Valley Water proposes this surrender to be conditioned on completion of the proposed project, which encompasses the reconstruction of Anderson Dam to meet FERC's Part 12 seismic and flood protection dam safety standards. FERC's proposed federal action includes:

- Anderson Dam seismic retrofit construction including work on the dam embankment, spillway, diversion systems, and outlet works; pipeline realignments; installation of communication lines, dam controls, and instrumentation; temporary and permanent roadway modifications; and site restoration;
- Protection, mitigation, and enhancement measures including avoidance and minimization measures (AMMs), best management practices (BMPs), and mitigation measures; construction area wet weather bypass releases; construction period dry weather water releases and use of chillers; improvements to Ogier Ponds; monitoring and maintenance of salmonid spawning gravel and rearing habitat improvements in the Live Oak Restoration Reach; payment of Santa Clara Valley Habitat Conservation Plan/Natural Community Conservation Plan (SCVHP) mitigation fees; construction monitoring and avoidance plans; recreation improvements; and improvements to the Coyote Percolation Facility;
- Post-construction operation of Anderson Dam including implementation of rule curves and pulse flows (based on and modified from the Fish and Aquatic Habitat Collaborative Effort (FAHCE) Agreement); establishment of an Operations Work Group to prescribe and implement pulse flows; and adaptive management of the protection, mitigation, and enhancement measures and/or features constructed or improved upon during the interim risk reduction measures and retrofit;
- Hydroelectric facility decommissioning; and

¹ To "surrender a hydroelectric project exemption" means to voluntarily give up the legal status that allows a small hydroelectric project to operate without needing a full license from FERC, which is done by filing a petition with FERC outlining the plans for decommissioning and restoring the project site.

- Surrender of the hydroelectric project exemption upon completion of the dam retrofit.

The federal action on which we are consulting with the Corps is the Corps' issuance of a permit to Valley Water pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 et seq.) (Clean Water Act) for Valley Water's implementation of all Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project components involving discharges of dredge or fill material into waters of the United States. This includes implementation of the seismic retrofit of Anderson Dam and related facilities, subject to implementation of Valley Water's standard BMPs, the Santa Clara Valley Habitat Agency's (SCVHA) AMMs, SCVHP conditions, and mitigation measures, in addition to the implementation of several conservation measures (CMs)² including:

- Ongoing maintenance of spawning gravels and large woody debris installations within the FERC Order Compliance Project's (FOCP) Live Oak Restoration Reach by placing additional sediment and gravels in Coyote Creek;
- Maintenance of the creek habitat and geomorphology improvements in the North Channel that were constructed by the FOCP;
- Construction of the Ogier Ponds creek/pond separation geomorphic and habitat restoration CM;
- Construction of the Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam facility fish passage barrier remediation CM; and
- Implementation of the Sediment Augmentation Program that involves long-term plans to place sediment and gravels in Coyote Creek.

As is the case for FERC, with respect to the Corps, some CMs that do not involve dredge or fill within waters of the United States, such as the long-term operations of Anderson Dam and Coyote Percolation Dam, will be outside of the Corps' jurisdiction, but have been included to facilitate analysis of the entire Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project. Table 1 below summarizes for each proposed project activity whether FERC and/or the Corps have jurisdiction and oversight responsibilities.

Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), FERC and the Corps submitted a biological evaluation for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Bay checkerspot butterfly, Bay checkerspot butterfly critical habitat, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, Tiburon paintbrush, Coyote ceanothus, California Ridgway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and northwestern pond turtle, and not likely to adversely affect the longfin smelt, California least tern, western snowy plover, and California red-legged frog critical habitat.

² CMs are conservation measures implemented by Valley Water as part of the proposed project as required by regulatory agencies other than the Service (e.g., National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), Corps, California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board (SFRWQCB), and State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB)). These are separate from the "conservation measures" in the *Conservation Measures* section of this biological opinion proposed by Valley Water to avoid, minimize, and mitigate effects to federally listed species regulated by the Service or required by SCVHA or the SCVHP.

Table 1. Major components and mitigation measures of the federal actions associated with the proposed project and FERC's initial determinations of oversight responsibilities.

Project Component	FERC Jurisdiction (Surrender Proceeding)	Corps Jurisdiction (Clean Water Act 404 Dredge and Fill)
<i>Seismic Retrofit (ADSRP)***</i>		
Dam Embankment Retrofit, Spillway Replacement, Temporary Diversion Systems, Outlet Works	Yes	Yes
Infrastructure modifications related to ADSRP: Pipeline realignments, communication lines, roadway modifications	Yes	No, unless they involve the discharge of fill into waters of the United States
Decommissioning of hydropower facility	Yes	No
<i>Conservation and Mitigation Measures (CMs)***</i>		
Normal operation of upstream Coyote Reservoir (not part of Anderson Dam Project) during ADSRP Anderson Reservoir drawdown (deadpool and lower) and ADSRP construction period	No	No
Construction Period Wet Weather Bypass (Stage 1 & 2 Diversions System releases)	Yes	Yes
Construction Period Dry Weather Imported Water Releases (from Coyote Discharge Line and Cross Valley Pipeline Extension, including use of chillers)	Yes	No
Ogier Ponds CM* (physically separate and hydrologically disconnect Coyote Creek from Ogier Ponds; construct a 6,500-foot reach of Coyote Creek channel and an associated, approximately 45-acre floodplain at Ogier Ponds; complete fill and discontinuation of Ponds 1 and 5 and the partial fill of Ponds 2 and 5)	No	Yes
Maintenance of the North Channel Reach (maintain the constructed wetland bench, maintain design flow capacity through the North Channel, and replace restoration plantings, as needed)	Yes	No, unless activities involve the discharge of fill into waters of the United States
Maintenance Activities at the Live Oak Restoration Reach (placement of gravel and maintenance of placed large woody debris to improve spawning habitat conditions)	Yes	Yes
Sediment Augmentation Program (placing up to 500 cubic yards of sediment in Coyote Creek initially at the Live Oak Restoration Reach, and later at multiple locations downstream of Anderson Dam within the Live Oak Restoration Reach and Ogier Ponds)	No	Yes

Project Component	FERC Jurisdiction (Surrender Proceeding)	Corps Jurisdiction (Clean Water Act 404 Dredge and Fill)
restoration area as determined by adaptive management)		
Geomorphic Flows Plan (integrated into Post-Construction Operations to provide additional support for biological features of steelhead critical habitat that are maintained by periodic high flows capable of inundating the floodplain, scouring substrate, mobilizing gravel, and supporting channel migration)	No	No
Construction of Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam Fish Passage Enhancements*	No	Yes
Coyote Creek Facilities Plans: Laguna Seca Groundwater Remediation Plan & Metcalf Ponds Stream Corridor Restoration Plan* (see Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam and Fish Ladder Operations Plan, below)	No	No, unless they involve the discharge of fill into waters of the United States
Cherry Flat Reservoir Cooperative Operating Agreement*	No	No
Payment of SCVHP Mitigation Fees**	No	No
Payment of Fees to Baylands Predator management and high tide refugia enhancement program**	No	No
BMPs, SCVHP conditions, AMMs, and Mitigation Measures as included in Appendix A of the surrender application not already listed above specific to dam retrofit construction	Yes	Yes
Preparation of a Water Quality Monitoring and Protection Plan	Yes	No, unless it involves the discharge of fill into waters of the United States
Recreational Facility Modifications (restoring park facilities closed during construction, new park entrance, expanded parking near the dam)	Yes	No, unless it involves the discharge of fill into waters of the United States
Cultural resources monitoring and mitigation as defined under a Programmatic Agreement	Yes	Yes
<i>Construction Monitoring and Interim Maintenance at the Anderson Dam Project***</i>		
Construction Phase Water Quality Monitoring (water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, suspended sediment, sediment deposition, groundwater management program monitoring, and localized construction area dewatering)	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Stream Flow Water Temperature Forecast Modeling	Yes	Yes

Project Component	FERC Jurisdiction (Surrender Proceeding)	Corps Jurisdiction (Clean Water Act 404 Dredge and Fill)
Construction Phase Terrestrial Wildlife Monitoring and Avoidance Measures	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Fisheries Monitoring (Juvenile Rearing and Growth Comparative Studies, Environmental DNA Monitoring, Vaki Riverwatcher Adult Escapement Monitoring, Fish Rescue and Relocation Plan, Migration Flow Monitoring, Migration Study, Spawning Surveys, and Habitat Restoration Monitoring)	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Northwestern Pond Turtle Monitoring	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Invasive Species Management in Upper Penitencia Creek (in any construction year when steelhead relocation to Upper Penitencia Creek occurs)	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Invasive Species Monitoring and Control in Coyote Creek (removal non-native fish, crayfish, American bullfrog, red-eared slider)	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase <i>Phytophthora</i> Pathogen Monitoring Plan and Management Plan	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Wetland and Riparian Habitat Dryback Monitoring	Yes	Yes
Construction Phase Vegetation Monitoring and Avoidance, Milkweed Survey Plan	Yes	Yes
Interim North Channel Maintenance	Yes	Yes
Operations & Maintenance of Anderson Dam and construction site prior to surrender being effective including potential refill of reservoir, debris removal, and revegetation, etc.	Yes	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Terrestrial Animal Monitoring (bald eagles, golden eagles, pallid bat)	Yes	No
Crotch's Bumble Bee Avoidance Plan (unless and until Crotch's bumble bee is added to the SCVHP as a covered species)	Yes	No
<i>Post-Construction Anderson Dam Facilities Operations and Maintenance After Surrender is Effective</i>		
Reservoir Refilling and Inflow	No	No
Reservoir Outflow (releases to the creek and raw water distribution system)	No	No
Post-Construction Operational Rule Curves (FAHCE Plus Modified)*	No	No

Project Component	FERC Jurisdiction (Surrender Proceeding)	Corps Jurisdiction (Clean Water Act 404 Dredge and Fill)
Imported Water Releases and Pipeline Maintenance *	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Anderson Dam and Pipeline Maintenance	No	No
Coyote Discharge Line and Cross Valley Pipeline Extension Maintenance	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Lower Cold Water Management Zone Restoration Evaluation*	No	No
Ogier Ponds Operations and Maintenance*	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Maintenance of the North Channel Reach	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Spawning Gravel and Sediment Augmentation Program Maintenance	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam Operations and Maintenance	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam and Fish Ladder Operations Plan (part of the Coyote Creek Facilities Plan)	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
Post-Construction Cross Valley Pipeline Extension Operation	No	No, unless maintenance actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States
<i>Adaptive Management Program</i>		
Post-Construction Project and FAHCE Adaptive Management Program*	No	No, unless maintenance or adaptive management actions involve new discharge of dredge or fill material in waters of the United States

*Denotes FAHCE measure proposed to be completed as part of ADSRP. However, FAHCE is an off-exemption agreement (i.e., FERC and the Corps are not parties to the agreement) that includes actions that were contemplated irrespective of ADSRP.

**Because these proposed measures would involve Valley Water contributing payments to funds managed by other agencies, FERC and the Corps would have no oversight authority for how the funds are managed.

***For project components or CMs requiring monitoring, the monitoring activities itself may not require specific or separate FERC or Corps authorization, but it may be a condition of the surrender order and/or

Clean Water Act 404 permit, respectively, to ensure compliance with the Act, National Historic Preservation Act, and Clean Water Act.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following:

- 1) The September 10, 2024, letter from FERC requesting the initiation of formal consultation on the proposed project;
- 2) The May 17, 2024, *Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project Biological Evaluation for Three Plant Species and Nine Animal Species* (Corps and FERC 2024);
- 3) The August 2012 *Final Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan* (SCVHP) (ICF International 2012, <http://scv-habitatagency.org/178/Final-Habitat-Plan>);
- 4) Communications from 2018 to present among the Service, FERC, Division of Safety of Dams (DSOD), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), Corps, California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), Valley Water, San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board (SFRWQCB), State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB), SCVHA, Santa Clara County Parks & Recreation Department, H.T. Harvey & Associates (HTH), and Stillwater Sciences;
- 5) The February 25, 2025, *Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project Final Environmental Impact Report* (Valley Water 2025); and
- 6) Other information available to the Service.

The SCVHP is a 10(a)(1)(B) permit under the Act that covers the effects of a number of covered activities on the California red-legged frog, California red-legged frog critical habitat, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Bay checkerspot butterfly, Bay checkerspot critical habitat, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, Tiburon paintbrush, Coyote ceanothus, and northwestern pond turtle (ICF International 2012). The proposed project is considered a covered project by the SCVHP, and the majority of proposed project activities and their effects are explicitly covered by the SCVHP. However, due to recent modifications to the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project that differ from how the project was described in the SCVHP in 2012, some of the proposed project's effects are not covered by the SCVHP's 10(a)(1)(B) permit under the Act (e.g., additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir beyond the 3.5 years covered under the SCVHP, passing of flows from Anderson Dam greater than 500 cubic feet per second (cfs), and the effects on listed amphibians and aquatic reptiles of relocating steelhead from Coyote Creek to Upper Penitencia Creek). Additionally, the SCVHP does not cover any effects to the listed tidal marsh species California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse (e.g., the effects of passing flood flows from Anderson Dam during seismic retrofit construction on these listed tidal marsh species further downstream). Therefore, this biological opinion addresses the effects of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP. All of the effects of the proposed project on the Bay checkerspot butterfly and Bay checkerspot butterfly critical habitat are covered by the SCVHP, and therefore, are not included in this biological opinion. The SCVHP only covers effects to the Tiburon paintbrush from the implementation of conservation actions within the SCVHP reserve system; therefore, this biological opinion addresses the indirect effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition from construction vehicle exhaust (i.e., the facilitation of the spread of invasive plant species) on the

two occurrences of the Tiburon paintbrush located outside of the SCVHP reserve system that are downwind from proposed project construction activities.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the longfin smelt. No proposed project activities will occur in or near the tidally influenced portions of Coyote Creek where the longfin smelt occurs. However, increased sediment transport associated with dewatering the reservoir and exposing erodible sediment that can be transported during precipitation events could affect longfin smelt individuals and their habitat within the tidally influenced portions of Coyote Creek. Longfin smelt are unlikely to be adversely affected by increased turbidity associated with sediment mobilization; rather, they may benefit from turbidity, which is thought to shield longfin smelt larvae and juveniles, which are weak swimmers, from predators. Increased sediment transported during precipitation events due to Seismic Retrofit construction activities may also benefit longfin smelt through increased input of inorganic sediment, which helps to sustain and build marshes (especially in the face of sea level rise), thereby increasing the organic inputs of tidal marshes. The implementation of FAHCE rule curves at Anderson Dam after construction of the Seismic Retrofit, which will increase reservoir releases by 10 to 20 cfs, will have a discountable effect on the salinity levels of longfin smelt habitat in the tidally influenced reaches of Coyote Creek.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern. The proposed project will have no direct effects on the California least tern, as this species occurs in the action area only along Coyote Slough, and indirect effects are not expected to occur to this species. There are no records of the species foraging in Coyote Slough; when this species is observed in the vicinity of the action area, it is foraging in managed salt ponds and over the more extensive open San Francisco Bay, so this species may not forage in Coyote Slough much, if at all. California least terns do not nest in the action area, and do not roost in habitats that could be adversely affected by increased flooding or sediment deposition that may occur during proposed project construction. Although California least terns could be adversely affected by increased turbidity as a result of sediment mobilization, or by mobilization of contaminants, if present in the action area when sediment mobilization occurs, the species is not expected to be present at that time. The California least tern is absent from the region from October through March, and although the eBird database contains hundreds of records of the species from Santa Clara County from July through September, there are only five records from April through June (eBird 2024, <https://ebird.org/home>). Thus, during the wet season, when sediment mobilized from Anderson Reservoir could potentially increase turbidity of waters in the action area or introduce contaminants, California least terns will be absent from the action area.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover. Although the western snowy plover occurs near tidal marsh and aquatic habitats along Coyote Slough, it makes little to no use of these habitats. Rather, western snowy plovers in southern San Francisco Bay (South Bay) occur primarily in managed ponds that provide bare salt panne habitat, and such areas are outside of the proposed project's action area. Although western snowy plovers could be adversely affected by increased turbidity as a result of sediment mobilization, or by mobilization of contaminants, on the rare occasions when they forage in intertidal habitats, the species is not expected to make substantial use of the portions of the action area where these effects would occur.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect California red-legged frog critical habitat because the only project activities occurring within California red-legged frog critical habitat are the translocation of steelhead to Upper Penitencia Creek and the

removal of invasive species (e.g., bullfrogs, non-native fish, red-eared sliders, non-native crayfish) in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed. Steelhead relocation would not modify California red-legged frog habitat or the primary constituent elements of designated critical habitat, and with implementation of the measures in the Fish Rescue and Relocation Plan and other proposed conservation measures (e.g., minimizing the potential for the introduction of amphibian diseases and invasive New Zealand mudsnails during steelhead relocation), the impacts of the steelhead relocation on California red-legged frog critical habitat in Upper Penitencia Creek will be minimal. California red-legged frogs will benefit from the removal of invasive species within the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed.

The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP on the California red-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, Tiburon paintbrush, Coyote ceanothus, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse, and conference opinion on the northwestern pond turtle.

Consultation History

- April 2018-October 2024: The Service met monthly with Valley Water, FERC, NMFS, the Corps, CDFW, SFRWQCB, SWRCB, SCVHA, DSOD, Santa Clara County Parks & Recreation Department, HTH, and Stillwater Sciences to discuss the proposed project.
- March 2019-March 2022: The Service attended quarterly meetings with executive federal agency staff including NMFS, FERC, the Corps, and Valley Water convened by Congresswoman Lofgren, with Congresswoman Eshoo and Congressmen Khanna and Panetta participating to provide updates on the status of the proposed project.
- February 20, 2020: Due to limited existing outlet capacity at Anderson Dam and the presence of densely populated areas downstream of the dam, in order to reduce the risk of dam failure from an earthquake, FERC ordered Valley Water to maintain the reservoir no higher than elevation 565 feet (North American Vertical Datum of 1988) effective immediately; to start lowering Anderson Reservoir to deadpool³ beginning no later than October 1, 2020; to take all appropriate measures to maintain and quickly lower the reservoir to deadpool in the event of significant inflow once the deadpool is reached; to assess and address the issue of potential rim instability during drawdown; and to expedite design, construction, and operations of a new, low-level outlet in advance of the proposed project. FERC's direction to Valley Water is referred to herein as the FOCP (FERC Order Compliance Project).
- March 16, 2020: FERC requested the initiation of formal consultation with the Service on the FOCP.

³ Deadpool occurs when water in a reservoir drops so low that it cannot flow downstream from the dam.

- September 15, 2020: The Service issued its biological opinion to FERC on the FOCP concluding that all FOCP project activities are covered by the SCVHP (Service 2020a, Service file number 08ESMF00-2020-F-1348-2).
- April 19, 2021: The Service provided comments on the draft outline of the biological evaluation for the proposed project.
- December 13, 2022: The Service attended a site visit to Ogier Ponds.
- September 28, 2023: The Service received from Valley Water the draft biological evaluation and the draft petition for surrender of the hydroelectric exemption at Anderson Dam.
- October 2, 2023: The Service provided comments on the Draft Environmental Impact Report for the proposed project.
- May 22, 2024: The Service received the revised draft biological evaluation.
- August 7, 2024: The Service met with FERC and the Corps to discuss the formal consultation process.
- September 10, 2024: The Service received from FERC the request for initiation of formal consultation and the final biological evaluation.
- September 11, 2024: The Service provided information to FERC and the Corps on a third population of Tiburon paintbrush observed along Coyote Ridge at SCVHA's Richmond Ranch Preserve in May 2024 near the action area for indirect effects for atmospheric nitrogen deposition and requested information on whether this population would be adversely affected.
- October 4, 2024: The Service received from FERC responses to most of the Service's questions about the final biological evaluation.
- October 8, 2024: The Service met with FERC and the Corps to discuss how the terms and conditions in the biological opinion would be directed for each of the proposed project activities based on FERC's and the Corps' respective jurisdictions and oversight responsibilities. FERC and the Corps requested a draft biological opinion,
- October 17, 2024: Valley Water confirmed that the newly discovered population of Tiburon paintbrush at SCVHA's Richmond Ranch Preserve is outside of the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition.
- January 16, 2025: The Service provided the draft biological opinion to FERC and the Corps.
- February 21, 2025: FERC and the Corps provided comments on the draft biological opinion including ensuring the project description is consistent with Valley Water's Final Environmental Impact Report (Valley Water 2025).
- March 5-7, 2025: The Service received comments from Valley Water on the draft biological opinion.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION AND CONFERENCE OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The purpose of the proposed project is to seismically retrofit, maintain, and operate Anderson Dam and Reservoir to meet FERC and DSOD safety requirements, thereby allowing Valley Water to maximize water supply and related incidental benefits, while avoiding and minimizing environmental impacts of the implementation of those safety directives and requirements. Without such regulatory compliance, Valley Water would be required to maintain a very low water level in Anderson Reservoir, which would in turn reduce water supplies that would otherwise be available for water supply deliveries to treatment plants, managed groundwater recharge, and maintenance of a local source of emergency water supply. Valley Water would likely have to replace those lost supplies to achieve its water supply and management goals that may result in significant cost increases, to the extent that any alternative resources are available.

Per FERC requirements, the proposed project addresses seismic deficiencies of the dam, specifically providing a stable dam embankment capable of withstanding the maximum credible earthquakes on the Calaveras and Coyote Creek Range Front Faults. In addition to the seismic deficiencies of the dam, presently the spillway lacks the capacity to safely pass the flood flows related to passage of the probable maximum flood (PMF) event and emergency reservoir drawdown. An updated PMF evaluation completed in 2013 (HDR 2013) predicts a peak spillway discharge of 95,800 cfs at a reservoir stage of elevation 652.5 feet during the PMF. The PMF flow exceeds the current spillway capacity by 50 percent and would cause overtopping of the existing dam embankment by several feet. Overtopping of the dam could lead to dam failure. FERC (as well as DSOD) dam safety criteria require that spillways be sized to safely pass PMF flows without overtopping the dam. Consequently, the spillway will be modified and improved, in conjunction with raising of the dam crest, to address this deficiency.

DSOD requires the new outlet works at Anderson Reservoir to be capable of lowering the reservoir's maximum storage depth by 10 percent within seven days and draining its full content within 90 days, even if a fault offset were to occur. DSOD also requires that the entire spillway (including the currently unlined portion of the spillway) be able to contain the PMF, and will require deepening and hardening of the unlined portion in order to mitigate the risk of spillway failure in the event of a PMF.

Implementation of the proposed project, including the CMs, will result in a more seismically safe dam that will allow Valley Water to better carry out water supply and groundwater recharge activities. Operational flexibility will also be improved by the proposed project that will: minimize the risk of reservoir spills and minimize downstream flooding; provide in-stream environmental flows consistent with regulatory requirements; and restore recreational opportunities at Anderson Reservoir and along the Coyote Creek corridor. Figure 1 below shows the location of the proposed project within the Coyote Creek watershed. Table 1 above summarizes for each proposed project activity whether FERC and/or the Corps have jurisdiction and oversight responsibilities.

Figure 1. Action area and proposed project locations (copied from Figure 4 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

The proposed project includes:

1. Improvements to Anderson Dam and associated facilities (collectively, the Seismic Retrofit Improvements): removal and replacement of the existing dam, increasing the height of the dam crest, removal and replacement of the existing spillway, conversion of the Stage 1 Diversion System to the Stage 2 Diversion System, construction of the outlet works, connections to existing Anderson Force Main and Main Avenue pipelines, improvement of the communication network connectivity in the proposed project area, modification of existing roadways throughout the proposed project area, decommissioning of the existing hydroelectric facility, and surrendering the hydroelectric project exemption (i.e., voluntarily giving up the legal status that allows a small hydroelectric project to operate without needing a full license from FERC, which is done by filing a petition with the FERC outlining the plans for decommissioning and restoring the project site).
2. During construction, Valley Water will monitor water quality in Coyote Creek and Anderson Reservoir, habitat conditions to support steelhead, suspended sediment and sediment deposition in Coyote Creek, groundwater levels, invasive species presence, wetland dryback conditions, northwestern pond turtles, and survey for milkweed (*Asclepias* species), the larval host plant for the federal candidate monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*). In addition, Valley Water will implement measures to prevent the spread of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*. As needed, native aquatic species will be relocated from work areas and reaches of Coyote Creek downstream from work areas if habitat becomes unsuitable.
3. Post-construction operations include the operation of Anderson Dam facilities according to the FAHCE operational rule curves, release of imported water to the downstream end of the CWMZ via the Cross Valley Pipeline Extension, development and implementation of an updated operations plan for the Coyote Percolation Dam facility, storing local and imported water in Anderson Reservoir, and adaptive management activities. An Operations Work Group will also be established to discuss and provide updates on FAHCE operations. The Operations Work Group will include representatives from NMFS and CDFW. An annual coordination meeting will be scheduled, frequent operational updates will be provided, and additional coordination will occur as needed during dry or low storage years. One meeting will be scheduled to occur annually, no later than February 15th of each year, with a focus on potential modifications to operations based on current conditions in the watershed and projections of 90 percent historical flow exceedance for the remainder of the water year. More frequent coordination will occur as needed in low storage and/or dry and very dry years, which could include monthly meetings. The Valley Water Operations team will provide updates to the Operations Work Group via email as changes occur associated with winter baseflows and when pulse flow triggers occur.

SCVHP-Covered Activities

The SCVHP is a 10(a)(1)(B) permit under the Act that covers the effects of covered activities on the California red-legged frog and its designated critical habitat, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Bay checkerspot butterfly and its designated critical habitat, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, Tiburon paintbrush, Coyote ceanothus,

and northwestern pond turtle (ICF International 2012). The proposed project is considered a covered project by the SCVHP, and the majority of proposed project activities are explicitly covered by the SCVHP⁴.

These SCVHP covered activities include, but are not limited to:

1. Minor ground disturbance associated with the decommissioning of the hydroelectric facility;
2. Dewatering of Anderson Reservoir and maintaining it in a dewatered condition for up to 3.5 years;
3. All dam removal and replacement activities associated with the embankment, crest, spillway, outlet works, pipelines, and roadways, including related modifications of Coyote Creek, borrow/quarrying, staging, stockpiling, and construction access;
4. Recreational facility modifications;
5. Most of the proposed CMs for fish are associated with FAHCE. The SCVHP explicitly covers reservoir re-operation to enhance flow, temperature, and water quality conditions downstream from reservoirs for fish; cold water releases from the hypolimnion of Anderson Reservoir between May 1 and October 31; releases from Anderson Reservoir for two 5-day pulse flows, and “releases up to the capacity of the outlet (approximately 550 cfs) to enhance downstream channel and floodplain habitat”; the Cherry Flat Reservoir Cooperative Operating Agreement; Ogier Ponds geomorphic and habitat restoration; maintenance of spawning gravel and rearing habitat improvements; sediment augmentation; the Coyote Percolation Dam Phase 2 Fish Passage Enhancement Project; and FAHCE-associated monitoring and adaptive management measures, including monitoring of water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and fish in the Functional Cold Water Management Zone (FCWMZ) in Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam. An Operations Work Group will also be established to discuss and provide updates on FAHCE operations of Anderson Dam;
6. Groundwater monitoring, *Phytophthora* monitoring, northwestern pond turtle monitoring, milkweed surveys, environmental DNA sampling, and post-construction validation monitoring for flow measures.
7. Coyote Ceanothus. Coyote ceanothus is present on the right dam abutment and in serpentine-influenced habitats immediately north and southeast of the dam. Approximately 2,666 individuals within the Seismic Retrofit construction footprint will be lost to clearing and construction, and additional seedlings and saplings that have recently established below the reservoir rim will be impacted by construction activities or when the reservoir is refilled following proposed project completion. Additional

⁴ Project activities that are consistent with how they were described in the SCVHP in 2012 are “covered activities” and, therefore, their effects on SCVHP covered species are covered under the 10(a)(1)(B) permit for the SCVHP. However, due to recent modifications to the project description for the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project that significantly diverge from how they were described in the SCVHP in 2012, some of the effects of the proposed project activities are not covered by the SCVHP and, therefore, are covered under this biological opinion (e.g., additional year of dewatering Anderson Reservoir beyond the 3.5 years defined in the SCVHP, passing flows from Anderson Dam of greater than 500 cfs, and relocating steelhead to another stream).

individuals could be adversely affected by grading near root zones, dust mobilization, spread of the water mold *Phytophthora*, and facilitation of invasion by non-native plants due to ground disturbance during Seismic Retrofit construction. Non-SCVHP-covered effects to Coyote ceanothus are limited to adverse effects of dust mobilization during the additional year of reservoir dewatering, beyond the 3.5 years covered by the SCVHP.

Conservation Measures for SCVHP-Covered Activities

1. BMPs are standard practices that prevent, avoid, or minimize potentially adverse effects associated with construction, operations, and maintenance activities. Valley Water routinely incorporates a wide range of BMPs from its Best Management Practices Handbook (Valley Water 2014a) into project designs and throughout the implementation of projects (Table 2). In addition, for work in and near streams, Valley Water will also employ other BMPs included in the 2014–2023 Stream Maintenance Program Manual (Valley Water 2014b), as necessary, to reduce impacts on specific resources (Table 2).

Table 2. BMPs (Corps and FERC 2024, Table 23; Valley Water 2014a, 2014b).

Valley Water BMP	BMP Description
Handbook BMPs	
ANI-5: Slurry Mixture near Waterways	Would reduce potential impacts from slurry
AQ-1: Use Dust Control Measures	Would install dust control measures prescribed by the Bay Area Air Quality Management District (BAAQMD) for all construction projects
AQ-2: Avoid Stockpiling Odorous Materials	Would restrict the handling, storage, and disposal of odorous materials within 1,000 feet of sensitive land uses
BANK-1: Bank Stabilization Design to Prevent Erosion Downstream	Would reduce the potential for erosion at streambanks
BANK-3: Bank Stabilization Post-Construction Maintenance	Would reduce impact of erosion during post-construction maintenance
BI-2: Minimize Impacts to Steelhead	Would reduce impacts to steelhead during activities

Table 2 continues on the next page.

Table 2 (continued). BMPs (Corps and FERC 2024, Table 23; Valley Water 2014a, 2014b).

Valley Water BMP	BMP Description
BI-3: Remove Temporary Fills	Would remove temporary fill material upon finishing work to reduce impacts to water quality
BI-4: Minimize Adverse Effects of Pesticides on Non-target Species	Would ensure that pesticides are handled, stored, transported, and used appropriately to avoid unintended impacts on non-target species
BI-8: Choose Local Ecotypes of Native Plants and Appropriate Erosion Control Seed Mixes	Would require that restored areas are planted with native species that are ecologically appropriate to the work area and help improve visual conditions post-construction
BI-9: Restore Riffle/Pool Configuration of Channel Bottom	Would enhance aquatic habitat and restore its functions to native biota
BI-11: Minimize Predator-Attraction	Would reduce the potential for pests to be attracted to the Project Area, causing damage to agricultural operations
GEN-1: In-Channel Work Window (for maintenance)	Would reduce impacts related to in-channel work
GEN-4: Minimize Disturbance Area	Would reduce risk area if disturbance area is minimized
GEN-16: In-Channel Minor Activities	Would reduce large impacts related to in-channel activities
GEN-17: Employee/Contractor Training	Would reduce risk of impacts from improper activities
GEN-20: Erosion and Sediment Control	Would reduce potential impacts of erosion by installing control measures
GEN-21: Staging and Stockpiling	Would reduce impacts related to storing of equipment and materials
GEN-22: Sediment Transport	Would reduce impacts from sediment-laden water reaching waterways
GEN-23: Stream Access	Would reduce number of access points for potential impacts related to increased disturbed areas
GEN-24: On-Site Hazardous Materials	Would reduce potential for contamination from hazardous materials
GEN-25: Existing Hazardous Materials	Would dispose of hazardous materials appropriately
GEN-26: Spill Prevention and Response	Would reduce risk of potential spills of hazardous materials
GEN-28: Fire Prevention	Would reduce risk of fire impacts
GEN-30: Vehicle Maintenance	Would ensure that on-site equipment is operating properly through vehicle maintenance
GEN-31: Vehicle Cleaning	Would ensure that vehicles are clean when entering a site
GEN-32: Vehicle Fueling	Would avoid impacts from fuel spills
GEN-35: Pump/Generator Operations and Maintenance	Would reduce impacts related to pump or generator operations and maintenance

Table 2 continues on the next page.

Table 2 (continued). BMPs (Corps and FERC 2024, Table 23; Valley Water 2014a, 2014b).

Valley Water BMP	BMP Description
HM-1: Comply with All Pesticide Application Restrictions and Policies	Would reduce hazardous impacts associated with the use of pesticides
HM-2: Minimize Use of Pesticides	Would reduce hazardous impacts associated with the use of pesticides
HM-4: Comply with All Pesticide Usage Requirements	Comply with all pesticide usage requirements
HM-5: Comply with Restrictions on Herbicide Use in Upland Areas	Would reduce impacts associated with the use of herbicides
HM-6: Comply with Restrictions on Herbicide Use in Aquatic Areas	Would reduce impacts associated with the use of pesticides
HM-7: Restrict Vehicle and Equipment cleaning to Appropriate Locations	Would reduce potential impacts associated with cleaning construction vehicles and equipment
HM-8: Vehicle Fuel & Maintenance	Would reduce the risk of spills or accidental releases of hazardous materials
HM-9: Hazardous Materials Management	Would reduce risk of spills or accidental releases of hazardous materials
HM-10: Spill Prevention	Would reduce the risk of spills of hazardous materials
HM-12: Fire Prevention	Would reduce the potential for fires
REVEG-1: Seeding	Would require that restored areas are planted with native seeds as soon as work activities are complete
REVEG-2: Planting Material	Would require that restored areas are replanted with locally collected native species and that species selection is based on surveys of natural areas on the same creek that have a similar ecological setting
SED-1: Groundwater Management	Would reduce risk of water quality contamination
SED-2: Prevent Scour	Would ensure appropriate grading following sediment removal to reduce scour
SED-3: Restore Channel Features	Would restore pre-construction conditions for channel features
VEG-1: Minimize Local Erosion	Would reduce local erosion potential from in-channel vegetation removal
VEG-2: Non-native Plant Removal	Would reduce impacts from non-native plants in surrounding areas
VEG-3: Appropriate Equipment for Instream Removal	Would reduce risk of impacts from damaging equipment
WQ-1: Conduct Work from Top of Bank	Would reduce the effect of machinery on streambed and water quality
WQ-2: Evaluate Use of Wheel and Track Mounted Vehicles in Stream Bottoms	Would reduce the potential effects of machinery and vehicles on stream bottoms
WQ-3: Limit Impact of Pump and Generator Operations and Maintenance	Would reduce impacts to water quality and aquatic species

Table 2 continues on the next page.

Table 2 (continued). BMPs (Corps and FERC 2024, Table 23; Valley Water 2014a, 2014b).

Valley Water BMP	BMP Description
WQ-4: Limit Impacts from Staging and Stockpiling Materials	Would reduce the potential for equipment at staging areas and stockpiled materials to damage soils in agricultural production
WQ-5: Stabilize Construction Entrances and Exits	Would reduce runoff and erosion and reduce impacts on instream biota and water quality
WQ-6: Limit Impact of Concrete Near Waterways	Would reduce runoff from increasing impervious surfaces and eliminate contact with uncured concrete
WQ-8: Minimize Hardscape in Bank Protection Design	Would reduce downstream or adjacent bank scour and erosion
WQ-9: Use Seeding for Erosion Control, Weed Suppression, and Site Improvement	Would reduce the potential for erosion by installing erosion control measures
WQ-10: Prevent Scour Downstream of Sediment Removal	Would decrease scour downstream of sediment removal by grading the channel transitions and ensuring that there are no rapid changes in the slope.
WQ-11: Maintain Clean Conditions at Work Sites	Would require that work areas and access roads are maintained in an orderly condition and that materials or equipment left on site overnight are stored as inconspicuously as possible
WQ-12: Manage Well or Exploratory Boring Materials	Would reduce runoff and erosion and reduce impacts on instream biota and water quality
WQ-15: Prevent Water Pollution	Would reduce impact to aquatic species and reduce transport of pollution in the channel network
WQ-16: Prevent Stormwater Pollution	Would reduce impact to aquatic species and reduce transport of pollution in the channel network
WQ-17: Manage Sanitary Waste	Would reduce the risk of waste spillage associated with temporary sanitary facilities

2. Valley Water will adhere to all applicable SCVHP conditions, and all applicable SCVHP AMMs, including the aquatic habitat AMMs from SCVHP Table 6-2 (ICF International 2012, <https://scv-habitatagency.org/178/Santa-Clara-Valley-Habitat-Plan>), throughout proposed project implementation. Valley Water will also pay applicable SCVHP mitigation fees, which are included in the proposed project as a Service conservation measure. All SCVHP conditions and AMMs will be incorporated into the construction documents (plans and specifications). Relevant SCVHP conditions include:
 - a. Condition 1: Avoid Direct Impacts on Legally Protected Plant and Wildlife Species;
 - b. Condition 3: Maintain Hydrologic Conditions and Protect Water Quality;
 - c. Condition 4: Avoidance and Minimization for In-stream Projects;
 - d. Condition 5: Avoidance and Minimization for In-stream Operations and Maintenance;
 - e. Condition 7: Rural Development Design and Construction Requirements;
 - f. Condition 11: Stream and Riparian Setbacks;

- g. Condition 12: Wetland and Pond Avoidance and Minimization;
 - h. Condition 13: Serpentine and Associated Species Avoidance and Minimization;
 - i. Condition 17: Tricolored Blackbird;
 - j. Condition 19: Plant Salvage When Impacts Are Unavoidable; and
 - k. Condition 20: Avoid and Minimize Impact to Covered Plant Occurrences.
2. Water Quality Monitoring in Coyote Creek: Valley Water will monitor water temperature and dissolved oxygen monitoring in Coyote Creek within the FCWMZ to determine if steelhead rescue is necessary. Valley Water will also monitor sediment deposition and suspended sediment in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam.
3. Wetland and Riparian Habitat Dryback Plan and Groundwater Management Plan. Valley Water will monitor groundwater, groundwater-dependent habitats (e.g., riparian and wetland habitat along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley such as Laguna Seca), and groundwater recharge from the Coyote Discharge Line downstream to Coyote Creek streamflow gauge #5058. The Wetland and Riparian Habitat Dryback Plan's (Valley Water 2020c) and Groundwater Management Plan's (Valley Water 2021e) focus is to monitor and manage groundwater recharge and avoid or minimize dryback conditions and impacts to wetlands and riparian habitats within Coyote Valley due to a reduced flow in Coyote Creek and a reduction in shallow groundwater levels in Coyote Valley during and after FOCP and during proposed project construction. The conditions of habitats will be monitored along Coyote Creek and within a portion of Coyote Valley to determine if there is a reduction in the surface area of wetlands and/or riparian habitats due to proposed project construction-related dryback. Aerial imagery, site visits, and photo documentation will be utilized to collect baseline (post-FOCP), interim, and after proposed project completion vegetation information. If early signs of dryback are observed during monitoring, Valley Water will determine whether different management of imported water releases during the construction and reservoir drawdown period could be used to reduce the impacts (i.e., increasing release rates of imported water).
4. Phytophthora Plant Pathogen Management and Monitoring. Valley Water will implement plans to prevent, avoid, and/or minimize the spread of *Phytophthora* infestations as a result of construction and project-related activities. Management and planning will involve the evaluation of site conditions prior to proposed project construction (i.e., existing contaminated sites), identification of sensitive plant species and communities, identification of project activities that have the potential to spread the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*, and the implementation of project-specific measures (e.g., hygiene and sanitation, access and movement, vegetation disposal, soil transport, and revegetation) to prevent the spread of *Phytophthora* by the proposed project.
5. Milkweed Survey Plan. Milkweed (*Asclepias* species), the larval host plant for the federal candidate monarch butterfly, are known to be present at scattered locations along Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam. Valley Water will conduct surveys of milkweed prior to the start of any ground disturbance or vegetation removal activities. A qualified biologist will survey the footprint of all potential impact areas, plus a 25-foot buffer around each impact area, for milkweed plants. If any milkweed is found, it will be

avoided, if feasible. If avoidance is infeasible, the milkweed will be inspected for monarch eggs or larvae, and if any of these are found, Valley Water will consult with the Service to discuss recommendations and approach to minimize impacts. If the monarch butterfly is added to the SCVHP as a covered species, as proposed in an amendment to the SCVHP currently being prepared, Valley Water's compliance with all monarch-related SCVHP conditions would supersede continued implementation of the Milkweed Survey Plan.

6. Fisheries Monitoring. Valley Water will monitor steelhead migration flows and conduct juvenile steelhead rearing studies, environmental DNA monitoring, VAKI (a computer-based fish counter) adult escapement monitoring, electrofishing, and spawning surveys.
7. Invasive Aquatic Species. Valley Water will dispatch non-native aquatic species (e.g., bullfrogs, non-native fish, non-native crayfish, and red-eared sliders) during the localized dewatering occurrences.
8. Northwestern Pond Turtle Monitoring. A Northwestern Pond Turtle Monitoring Plan (HTH 2020b) was prepared for the FOC. Monitoring efforts, defined through consultation with CDFW, the Service, and SCVHA for the FOC, will continue through proposed project construction. In coordination with these agencies, Valley Water will continue to implement northwestern pond turtle monitoring efforts in suitable habitat in the FCWMZ in Coyote Creek. The purpose of the monitoring will be to determine if a significant reduction in northwestern pond turtle populations has occurred from proposed project construction. Monitoring efforts will include surveys and reporting for the northwestern pond turtle in Coyote Creek. Surveys will be conducted on sunny days from midmorning to late afternoon to standardize conditions among surveys.
9. Invasive Species Monitoring and Control. Valley Water prepared an Invasive Species Monitoring and Control Plan (Valley Water 2020b) for the FOC that will continue to be implemented through construction of the proposed project. The species targeted by the plan include non-native fish, crayfish, American bullfrog, and red-eared sliders, as well as opportunistic removal of other non-native species. The non-native fish species that pose the most significant risk to native fish and wildlife are the predatory largemouth bass, spotted bass, green sunfish, bluegill, crappie, and catfish. Because these target species are widespread and the project area is not a closed system, complete eradication or control is not anticipated. Decontamination protocols will be implemented to prevent the spread of chytrid fungus (*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (Bd)), ranavirus, other pathogens, and non-native invasive species. Preventative controls at various locations may include signage discouraging release of unwanted pets.
10. Implementation of AMMs during Post-Construction Maintenance at Anderson Dam and CM Facilities to Reduce the Potential for Introduction or Spread of *Phytophthora*. Valley Water will develop and implement AMMs to reduce the potential for introduction and spread of *Phytophthora* during post-construction maintenance at Anderson Dam, because the Dam Maintenance Program (under which post-construction maintenance will occur) does not include AMMs for this purpose. AMMs will also be implemented during maintenance of CM facilities to reduce the potential for introduction and spread of *Phytophthora* during post-construction maintenance to affect sensitive communities. The AMMs will include a description of areas that are contaminated with *Phytophthora*; sensitive habitats that are not contaminated with *Phytophthora*; procedures for

decontamination of tools, equipment, vehicles, and maintenance personnel clothing and footwear prior to accessing those sensitive habitats; procedures for ensuring that water for irrigation or dust suppression, soil, mulch, plant material, and other materials are free from *Phytophthora* if used in, near, or upslope from sensitive habitats that are not contaminated with *Phytophthora*; decontamination procedures for vehicles, equipment, tools, footwear, and personnel clothing after working in areas contaminated by *Phytophthora*; and other procedures deemed necessary. Details of the BMPs will be developed following proposed project completion, as they will be informed by the results of *Phytophthora* monitoring during, and following completion of, proposed project construction.

11. Special-Status Plant Survey in the Previously Unsurveyed Portions of the Seismic Retrofit Area. Valley Water will conduct a survey for special-status plant species in the limited portions of the Seismic Retrofit area that provide potential special-status plant habitat but have not yet been surveyed. The survey will be conducted according to SCVHP standards and protocols, by a SCVHP-approved botanist, and will be floristic in nature so that all potentially occurring special-status plants are detected if present. Multiple site visits will be necessary to detect all the potentially occurring species by targeting their flowering periods.
12. Coyote Ceanothus. In compliance with a SCVHP requirement for Valley Water to protect or create a new population of this species within five years of proposed project impacts, an occurrence of Coyote ceanothus on the Baird and Davidson properties (i.e., Llagas Road population), on the west side of Coyote Valley, was recently acquired and protected. The SCVHP also states that within the 50-year permit term, five populations of Coyote ceanothus must be created or protected (ICF International 2012). To meet the SCVHP's long-term requirements, Valley Water has begun establishing a new population of Coyote ceanothus on property it owns on Coyote Ridge, north of Anderson Dam. Planting of seedlings and direct seeding in the test plots on Coyote Ridge has been occurring annually since 2015, and these plants are being monitored to determine the success of the site to support a new, functional population of Coyote ceanothus (Valley Water 2023b). Based on the results of this initial planting, Valley Water has prepared an occurrence creation plan that summarizes all the research and field efforts (Valley Water 2018), and this plan is being used to guide a subsequent full-scale planting effort currently underway, with the goal of establishing a viable Coyote ceanothus population on Valley Water's Coyote Ridge property (Valley Water 2023b). Plants are being grown via seed collected from the Anderson Dam population in a nursery and planted in accordance with the occurrence creation plan, as modified based on lessons learned from the initial planting effort. Success criteria include whether the population is reproducing and self-sustaining (based on reproduction and survival rates) over time, with minimal active site management. Specific management activities for the long-term health of the population will be described in a subsequent long-term management plan.

The SCVHP requires specific AMMs for covered activities that have the potential to affect SCVHP covered species, sensitive habitats, natural communities, and jurisdictional wetlands and other waters in Santa Clara County. Valley Water will implement all protection measures listed above for the affected species as set forth in the SCVHP.

In addition to AMMs, the SCVHP utilizes a variety of development-based fees to fund mitigation that will offset losses of land cover types, covered species habitat, and other biological

values. Valley Water will pay all applicable development fees to the SCVHA identified in the Development Fee Table (Table 9-6) and described in Chapter 9.4.1 of the SCVHP (updated fee schedules are available at <https://www.scv-habitatagency.org/206/Habitat-Agency-Fee-Schedule>).

When the provisions listed above are met, incidental take of the California red-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Bay checkerspot butterfly, and northwestern pond turtle resulting from the proposed project activities above that are SCVHP-covered activities will be authorized through the SCVHP's incidental take permit (Fish and Wildlife Permit No.: TE-94345A-0). The effects to listed species and critical habitat including the California red-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Bay checkerspot butterfly, Bay checkerspot butterfly critical habitat, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, Tiburon paintbrush, Coyote ceanothus, and northwestern pond turtle that would result from the issuance of this incidental take permit were analyzed in the Service's April 2013 *Intra-Service Biological Opinion on Issuance of a Section 10(a)(1)(B) Incidental Take Permit for the Santa Clara Valley Habitat Conservation Plan/Natural Community Conservation Plan* (Service 2013a, https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/plan_documents/bobs/bobs_2900.pdf).

Activities not Covered by the SCVHP

The following proposed project activities are not covered by the SCVHP, and therefore, their effects are addressed in this biological opinion.

1. Dewatering of Anderson Reservoir for longer than 3.5 years. The proposed project will require dewatering for up to 4.5 years; therefore, from fall of Year 5 until the reservoir refills during the wet season following Year 6 (approximately one year), effects on federally listed species of the reservoir's dewatered condition are not covered by the SCVHP (e.g., adverse effects of dust mobilization on the Coyote ceanothus and Santa Clara Valley dudleya during the additional year of reservoir dewatering, beyond the 3.5 years covered by the SCVHP; injury or mortality of Central California tiger salamanders, California red-legged frogs (including eggs and larvae), Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and northwestern pond turtles in the dewatered reservoir, and potential dryback effects on North Coyote Valley breeding habitat for these listed amphibians and aquatic reptiles, as well as the possible (though unlikely) increased risk of predation attempts if individuals are displaced from burrows by higher construction-period flows through Anderson Dam). Activities that will be occurring within the dewatered reservoir in Year 6 include hauling of material from the Packwood Gravel Borrow Pit and Stockpile Area K, placement of small amounts of material in the Reservoir Disposal Area, and restoration of access roads.
2. Relocation of steelhead to another stream. Valley Water intends to maintain suitable conditions for steelhead in the FCWMZ throughout proposed project construction. However, if water levels become too low or water temperatures too high, so that steelhead relocation is necessary during project construction, fish will be moved to a more suitable location, which may include lower Coyote Creek near its confluence with Upper Penitencia Creek or Upper Penitencia Creek within Alum Rock Park.
3. Differences in dam releases between those covered by the SCVHP and those that may occur during project construction and post-construction operations. As discussed in Table

2-4 of the SCVHP (ICF International 2012), the SCVHP covers Anderson Dam releases during dewatering for seismic retrofit construction up to 550 cfs, the capacity of the current dam outlet, for dewatering during the period November 1 to April 30 and up to 50 cfs for dewatering during the period May 1 to October 31. The SCVHP describes these maximum releases as being associated with draining the reservoir to dewater it for construction. The SCVHP indicates that if dewatering flows will exceed those in Table 2-4 of the SCVHP, those flows would not be covered by the SCVHP.

4. Effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition on Tiburon paintbrush. Although Tiburon paintbrush is a SCVHP-covered species, the SCVHP only covers impacts on this species from management of SCVHP preserves, and neither of the two populations on Coyote Ridge that could be affected by project-related nitrogen emissions (i.e., Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations) are located in SCVHP preserves.
5. Effects to listed tidal marsh species. The SCVHP does not cover species associated with the tidal marshes of San Francisco Bay, so any potential direct or indirect effects of the proposed project on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse are not covered by the SCVHP, and any take authorization for these species will be provided through this biological opinion.

Conservation Measures for Activities not Covered by SCVHP

1. Invasive Plant Management at Two Tiburon Paintbrush Populations. Valley Water will offset impacts from proposed project-related atmospheric nitrogen deposition on the Tiburon paintbrush by performing invasive plant management in and around two Tiburon paintbrush populations on Coyote Ridge⁵, including the Paintbrush Hill population on Valley Water's Coyote Ridge property and the Paintbrush Canyon population on land owned by Waste Management, Inc. Nitrogen deposited on nutrient-poor serpentine soils facilitates the ability of nonnative grasses and forbs to compete with serpentine endemic plants such as Tiburon paintbrush, so invasive plant management will directly address and reduce the impacts of nitrogen deposition. During each year of construction for the Ogier Ponds CM⁶, as well as the year following completion of that CM, Valley Water will perform manual weeding of plants considered to be of moderate or high invasiveness by the California Invasive Plant Council (2024) on the Paintbrush Hill population and perform manual weeding or fund weeding at the Paintbrush Canyon population. Such weeding will be performed at least twice during each growing season in which invasive plant management occurs. Weeding may be performed by hand or using hand-held motorized tools (e.g., line trimmers) as long as no impacts to individual Tiburon paintbrush plants would occur. Special care will be taken to avoid trampling individual Tiburon paintbrush plants, which are quite fragile.

⁵ A third population of Tiburon paintbrush was recently discovered near the action area in May 2024 on SCVHA's Richmond Ranch Preserve on Coyote Ridge (M. Fogarty, SCVHA, in litt. 2024; SCVHA in litt. 2024), but SCVHA is expected to maintain, monitor, and restore this population under the long-term management plan being developed for the Richmond Ranch Preserve under the SCVHP. This population is outside of the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition.

⁶ The Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations of Tiburon paintbrush are downwind from the Ogier Ponds CM, and thus are most likely to be adversely affected by nitrogen emissions from construction vehicles during construction of the Ogier Ponds CM.

2. Special-Status Species AMMs During Year 6 Reservoir Dewatering. Valley Water and/or its contractor will implement the following AMMs during Year 6 construction activities (i.e., dewatering; movement of construction personnel, vehicles, and equipment; or storage or stockpiling of equipment or materials) in the dewatered bed of Anderson Reservoir:
 - a. Prior to Year 6 construction activities, Valley Water will obtain approval from the Service and CDFW of appropriate relocation sites for all life forms of the Central California tiger salamander, California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and northwestern pond turtle.
 - b. A qualified biologist approved by the Service and CDFW (hereafter “approved biologist”) will conduct a pre-activity survey for all life forms of the Central California tiger salamander, California red-legged frog, and northwestern pond turtle (as well as the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, even though it is unlikely to be present) in areas where they could be stranded or desiccated as those pools are pumped out or dry out. Any individuals detected will be moved to the Service/CDFW-approved relocation sites.
 - c. Within 48 hours prior to the start of construction or other activities within the bed of the reservoir, following dewatering in the spring of Year 6, an approved biologist will conduct a pre-activity survey for all life forms of the Central California tiger salamander, California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and northwestern pond turtle in areas where they could be subject to impacts from activities in the bed of the reservoir during Year 6 construction. Any individuals detected will be moved to Service/CDFW-approved relocation sites.
 - d. Before any heavy equipment stored overnight is moved, a dedicated member of the construction crew trained by an approved biologist will inspect the area underneath and around the equipment to determine that no Central California tiger salamanders, California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, or northwestern pond turtles are present and at risk of being crushed by moving equipment. If an individual of one of these species is present in an area where it could be killed or injured by proposed project activities, that member of the construction crew will contact the approved biologist, who will capture and relocate the animal to a Service/CDFW-approved relocation site.
 - e. An approved biologist will be on-site or on-call during all activities that could result in the take of the Central California tiger salamander, California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, or northwestern pond turtle to determine that all conservation measures are being implemented appropriately and to relocate any individual of these species that needs to be relocated to avoid injury or mortality.
 - f. Pipes diverting water from behind check dams or cofferdams to outlets below Anderson Dam will be completely screened with wire mesh not larger than 5 millimeters, to prevent Central California tiger salamanders, California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and northwestern pond turtles from being entrained in outflow pipes. Screens will not be placed directly on the

openings of the diversion pipes, to avoid having flow velocities that are too great for small or larval animals. Rather, the screens will be placed farther from the pipe, encircling an area of water just above the entrance to the diversion or formed into a cage around the pipe entrance, so that flow velocities through the screen are not so high as to entrain animals against the screen.

3. Nonnative Species Management in Upper Penitencia Creek Watershed. During each year in which steelhead relocation to Upper Penitencia Creek occurs during proposed project construction, prior to relocation, Valley Water will perform management of nonnative species that could adversely affect Central California tiger salamanders, California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and northwestern pond turtles on Valley Water-owned properties in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed. Such management will include the removal and euthanasia of bullfrogs, nonnative fish, and/or nonnative turtles from selected ponds on Valley Water's Upper Penitencia Creek watershed properties. Prior to performing annual nonnative species management, Valley Water will provide the Service and CDFW a description of the proposed nonnative species management and obtain those agencies' approval of the management activities. Following the implementation of the annual nonnative species management, Valley Water will provide the Service and CDFW a brief report summarizing the management actions performed.
4. Contribution to Baylands Predator Management. Valley Water will contribute funds to be used for predator management in areas where predation of the California Ridgway's rail and/or salt marsh harvest mouse could occur in the South Bay. Valley Water will provide \$22,500 in funding (approximately half of the entire 2022 predator management budget for the Service's Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge) for each year during Seismic Retrofit construction in which flows through Anderson Dam exceed 2,500 cfs. Valley Water will develop and implement an agreement with the U.S. Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (APHIS), which performs predator management in coordination with the Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge. That agreement will specify the funding that Valley Water will provide for predator management and, generally, how APHIS personnel will utilize those funds. In any given year, how those funds are spent will be determined by Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge biologists, who routinely work with APHIS to prioritize predator management needs based on the most pressing predation issues occurring around the Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge, on special-status species, at that time. Prior to the start of Seismic Retrofit construction, Valley Water will provide APHIS with \$45,000 in funding, representing two years' predator management activities. This funding will be provided in advance of impacts from >2,500 cfs flows through the dam actually occurring, and for more than one year's predator management, to assist APHIS in planning for its staffing needs to perform the necessary predator management. Subsequently, during each year of Seismic Retrofit construction, Valley Water will monitor whether flows through Anderson Dam exceed 2,500 cfs. If such flows occur in a given calendar year, \$22,500 will be debited from the initial payment of \$45,000. If flows exceed 2,500 cfs in two years during construction, Valley Water will provide another \$22,500 payment for another, future year of predator management. Valley Water will continue to make such payments for each year in which flows exceed 2,500 cfs during Seismic Retrofit construction.

5. High-Tide Refugia Enhancement: Valley Water will contribute funds to one or more ongoing programs that focus on removal of nonnative marsh vegetation and/or planting or management of native marsh vegetation that provides suitable high tide refugia for species such as the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Examples of programs to which Valley Water might contribute include the San Francisco Bay Sea Lavender Control Program, the Invasive *Spartina* Project (to which Valley Water might contribute funds for restoration rather than invasive *Spartina* control), or revegetation efforts performed by Save the Bay or other organizations. Valley Water will contribute \$20,000 to such programs for each year in which flows exceed 2,500 cfs during Seismic Retrofit construction.

Action Area

The action area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action." For the proposed project, the action area for direct effects includes the approximately 1,492-acre proposed project footprint where all proposed project activities will physically take place (Figure 1) including Anderson Reservoir, Anderson Dam, Ogier Ponds (approximately 4 miles downstream of Anderson Dam), the Coyote Percolation Dam (approximately 10 miles downstream of Anderson Dam), lands in the immediate vicinity of Anderson Reservoir and Coyote Creek that are owned by Valley Water and the County of Santa Clara, portions of the Cochrane Road and Coyote Road rights-of-way, as well as all proposed construction staging areas, borrow areas, stockpile areas, disposal areas, parking areas, and "off-street" access roads. The action area for direct effects also includes the approximately 10 miles of the Coyote Creek channel from Anderson Dam downstream to the Coyote Percolation Dam.

The action area also includes the following areas outside of the proposed project footprint that would be subjected to direct or indirect effects as a consequence of the proposed project (Figure 1):

1. All areas within 100 feet of the proposed project footprint where proposed project activities could disturb listed animal species by noise and visual disturbance;
2. All areas within 100 feet of the proposed project footprint where proposed project activities could adversely affect listed plants via dust or the introduction and spread of invasive plant species and the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*;
3. All reaches of Coyote Creek from Anderson Dam downstream to the San Francisco Bay, approximately 40 stream miles, that could be affected by changes in flow rates and sediment mobilization during proposed project construction. The lower limits of the action area along Coyote Slough, where tidal marshes associated with Coyote Slough are included in the action area, were established by modeling of anticipated sediment mobilization due to proposed project activities (AECOM 2021). For the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the action area encompasses a predicted 155 acres of tidal areas in the South Bay near Coyote Slough that would be subject to additional inundation if a 50-100-year flood event (5,000 cfs) were passed through Anderson Dam during the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction;
4. Groundwater-dependent habitats for the California red-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, and northwestern pond turtle along Coyote Creek and in the

approximately 1,000-acre North Coyote Valley, including seasonal wetlands such as Laguna Seca, that could potentially be adversely affected by a reduction in Coyote Creek flow during proposed project construction (see yellow-dashed lines in Figure 2 below);

5. Aquatic habitats within 250 feet of steelhead relocation sites in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park where California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, Central California tiger salamanders, and northwestern pond turtles could be disturbed directly during steelhead relocation activities or indirectly by the introduction of diseases or invasive New Zealand mudsnails; and
6. Serpentine soils communities (Figure 1) supporting the Coyote ceanothus, Santa Clara Valley dudleya, or Tiburon paintbrush along Coyote Ridge downwind (generally east and southeast) of proposed project construction activities (e.g., downwind of Ogier Ponds CM and Seismic Retrofit construction areas) that could be adversely affected by the spread of invasive plant species facilitated by nitrogen emissions from equipment and vehicles during proposed project construction, and thus by the proposed project's contribution to the cumulative effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition.

The action area also includes the following locations where conservation measures will be implemented for the benefit of the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, northwestern pond turtle, Tiburon paintbrush, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse:

1. The streams and ponds on Valley Water's property in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed where invasive aquatic predators will be removed for the benefit of the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, and northwestern pond turtle;
2. The Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations of the Tiburon paintbrush where Valley Water will implement invasive plant species control for the benefit of the Tiburon paintbrush to minimize the indirect effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction vehicles; and
3. Locations in the South Bay, to be approved by the Service, where Valley Water will fund predator management and high-tide refugia enhancement for the benefit of the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse if flows passed from Anderson Dam exceed 2,500 cfs during the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. "Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide

Figure 2. Action area for the indirect effects (see dashed-yellow lines) of lowered flows in Coyote Creek on groundwater-dependent wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley as defined by the study area for the FOCPP Wetland and Riparian Habitat Dryback Monitoring Plan (copied from Figure 2 in HTH 2023).

condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the action area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which determines all consequences to listed species that are caused by the proposed federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-federal activities in the action area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the listed species.

Status of the Species

California Red-legged Frog

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the *California Red-legged Frog (Rana draytonii) 5-Year Review: Summary and Evaluation* (Service 2022, https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/4025.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the December 2022 5-year review was finalized, with habitat loss and fragmentation, isolation of populations south of Santa Barbara County and in the Sierra Nevada, invasive predators, and climate change being the most significant effects.

Central Coast Foothill Yellow-legged Frog

The Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog was federally listed as threatened by the Service on September 28, 2023 (Service 2023g). For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the April 2023 *Species Status Assessment Report for the Foothill Yellow-legged Frog (Rana boylei), Version 2.11* (Service 2023f, <https://ecos.fws.gov/ServCat/DownloadFile/235951>). Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the April 19, 2023, species status assessment was finalized, with altered hydrology (e.g., dams), summertime cold water releases for salmonids, residential and agricultural development, wildfire, predation by native or non-native species, disease (i.e., Bd), and climate change being the most significant effects.

Central California Tiger Salamander

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the *5-Year Review California Tiger Salamander Central California Distinct Population Segment (Ambystoma californiense)* (Service 2023e, https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/5721.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the August 10, 2023, 5-year review was finalized, with loss of habitat, hybridization with non-native tiger salamanders, and climate change being the most significant effects.

Northwestern Pond Turtle

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the *Species Status Assessment Report for the Northwestern Pond Turtle (Actinemys marmorata) and Southwestern Pond Turtle (Actinemys pallida)* (Service 2023a). On October 2, 2023, the Service proposed listing the northwestern pond turtle as threatened (Service 2023b). Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the October 2, 2023, listing proposal was issued, with habitat loss and fragmentation, altered hydrology, roads, predation on juveniles by nonnative bullfrogs, predation on nests by native mammals (e.g., skunks), competition with nonnative turtles, turtle-shell disease, and drought and high-severity wildfires exacerbated by climate change being the most significant effects.

Tiburon Paintbrush

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the *5-Year Review Tiburon Paintbrush (Castilleja affinis subsp. neglecta)* (Service 2021a, https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/3523.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the September 10, 2021, 5-year review was finalized, with grazing, herbivory, trampling, wild pig rooting, soil erosion and slipping, foot traffic, restricted habitats/range, small population size, competition with invasive plants exacerbated by atmospheric nitrogen deposition from vehicle exhaust, fire retardant, and climate change/drought being the most significant effects.

A new population of the Tiburon paintbrush was discovered in May 2024 along Coyote Ridge at SCVHA's 944-acre Richmond Ranch Preserve north of Metcalf Road in Santa Clara County increasing the total number of extant populations rangewide to eight, three of which are in Santa Clara County (M. Fogarty, SCVHA, in litt. 2024; SCVHA in litt. 2024). The newly discovered population of Tiburon paintbrush at the Richmond Ranch Preserve contained 167 individuals in May 2024 and will be protected under the reserve system for the SCVHP (SCVHA in litt. 2024). SCVHA will develop a long-term management plan for the Richmond Ranch Preserve which will preserve, manage, monitor, and restore the Tiburon paintbrush. As required by the SCVHP, the Richmond Ranch Preserve will be protected under a conservation easement, a long-term management plan must be approved by the Service and CDFW, and implementation of the management plan must begin within at least five years of SCVHA acquiring the preserve (i.e., by February 2029).

Coyote Ceanothus

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the *Coyote Ceanothus (Ceanothus ferrisae) 5-Year Review: Summary and Evaluation* (Service 2023d, https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/4203.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the July 7, 2023, 5-year review was finalized, with the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*, atmospheric nitrogen deposition, invasive plant species, herbivory/seed predation, altered fire regime, and climate change being the most significant effects.

More than half of the Kirby population, the smallest of the three extant populations of the Coyote ceanothus, burned in a fire in August 2023 (Valley Water 2024c). Fifty Coyote ceanothus were observed within the occurrence immediately after the fire (Valley Water 2024c). The majority of the unburned Coyote ceanothus shrubs showed little to no seed maturing at the time of the survey in August 2023, indicating there was likely little to no flowering of plants in 2023 despite adequate rainfall (Valley Water 2024c). Many (though not all) of the Coyote ceanothus shrubs were over mature with thick woody growth, senescing limbs, and a thin leafy canopy likely due to documented inbreeding depression in the Kirby population (Valley Water 2024c). Some of the Coyote ceanothus shrubs had recently been cut as a fire break (Valley Water 2024c). Valley Water conducted a post-fire survey of the Kirby population in April 2024 and observed 440 Coyote ceanothus seedlings directly adjacent to or within completely burned Coyote ceanothus shrubs (Valley Water 2024c). No seedlings were observed under five unburned Coyote ceanothus shrubs within the burn area (Valley Water 2024c). Across the creek drainage in an area of unburned Coyote ceanothus shrubs, Valley Water observed approximately 150 seedlings in one specific area adjacent to mature Coyote ceanothus shrubs on a northwest-facing slope that has active erosion and an absence of grass cover (Valley Water 2024c). The observations confirm the importance of fire in promoting the germination of Coyote ceanothus seedlings. However, the observation of seedlings in an unburned area without grass cover subject to erosion demonstrates that Coyote ceanothus seedlings may also germinate in areas where soil is disturbed if invasive grass cover is removed.

Santa Clara Valley Dudleya

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the 5-Year Review: *Santa Clara Valley Dudleya (Dudleya setchellii)* (Service 2021b, https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/962.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the May 6, 2021, 5-year review was finalized, with urban development, utility transmission line construction, competition with invasive plants exacerbated by nitrogen deposition from vehicle exhaust, catastrophic wildfire, herbivory, and climatic change being the most significant effects.

California Ridgway's Rail

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the 5-Year Review: *California clapper rail (Rallus longirostris obsoletus)* (Service 2020b, https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/3088.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the August 31, 2020, 5-year review was finalized, with habitat loss and fragmentation, invasive *Spartina* control efforts, predation, mercury contamination, and sea level rise being the most significant effects.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' rangewide status, please refer to the 5-Year Review: *Salt marsh harvest mouse (Reithrodontomys raviventris)* (Service 2021c, <https://ecosphere-documents-production->

public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the December 28, 2021, 5-year review was finalized, with habitat loss and fragmentation, invasive plant species, predation, and sea level rise being the most significant effects.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the action area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the action area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the action area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the environmental baseline.

Habitats within the Proposed Project Footprint

Anderson Reservoir is located on lands within the cities of Morgan Hill and San José and unincorporated Santa Clara County, California. The project area includes Anderson Reservoir, Anderson Dam, Ogier Ponds (approximately 4 miles downstream of Anderson Dam), the Coyote Percolation Dam (approximately 10 miles downstream of Anderson Dam), lands in the immediate vicinity of Anderson Reservoir and Coyote Creek that are owned by Valley Water and the County of Santa Clara, portions of the Cochrane Road and Coyote Road rights-of-way, as well as all proposed construction staging areas, borrow areas, stockpile areas, disposal areas, parking areas, and “off-street” access roads. The project area also includes approximately 10 miles of the Coyote Creek channel from Anderson Dam to the Coyote Percolation Dam, and two fish relocation sites: (1) along Coyote Creek near its confluence with Upper Penitencia Creek, and (2) along Upper Penitencia Creek in Alum Rock Park.

Existing land uses within and adjacent to the project area include vast areas of parkland at Anderson Lake County Park. Other land uses around the reservoir include grazing lands and single-family residences (both rural and suburban). Downstream of Anderson Dam, Anderson Lake County Park adjoins the Coyote Creek Parkway approximately 1 mile downstream of Anderson Dam. Land use designations within or adjacent to the project area include regional parks, agriculture, and hillsides in unincorporated Santa Clara County; open space, residential (detached low density), sports recreation/leisure, and public facilities in the City of Morgan Hill; and open hillside.

Based on dominant plant species and general community composition, the project area supports 15 land cover types, natural communities, and habitats (Table 3).

Reservoir

Anderson Reservoir is an anthropogenic feature created from the impoundment of Coyote Creek. The reservoir is impounded by a compacted embankment dam made of earth and rock, which is approximately 240 feet high. The reservoir land cover type was mapped in all areas below the elevation of the reservoir's rim, which is 627.9 feet, equivalent to the spillway elevation. Currently, the water level in Anderson Reservoir is in a drawn-down condition well below the

Table 3. Acres of each land cover type in the project areas for the Seismic Retrofit, Ogier Ponds CM, Coyote Percolation Dam CM, North Channel Extension, and Live Oak restoration reach areas (Table 2 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

Land Cover Type	Seismic Retrofit (acres)	Ogier Ponds CM (acres)	Coyote Percolation Dam (acres)	Live Oak Restoration Reach (acres)⁷	Total (acres)⁸
Reservoir	1,206.80 ⁹	17.20	0.00	0.00	1,224.00
Pond	0.19	2.13	0.00	0.00	2.32
Perennial Stream	0.75 ¹⁰	1.25	0.39	3.79	6.18
Intermittent Stream	1.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.28
Coastal & Valley Freshwater Marsh	0.53	3.65	0.00	0.01	4.19
Seasonal Wetland	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.05
Mixed Riparian Forest & Scrub	6.27	4.95	0.20	7.64	19.06
Willow Riparian Forest & Scrub	0.00	14.35	0.00	0.00	14.35
California Annual Grassland	21.20	40.50	0.00	0.00	61.70
Mixed Serpentine Chaparral	2.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.50
Northern Coastal Scrub/Diablan Sage Scrub	11.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.10
Coast Live Oak Forest & Woodland	14.30	0.70	0.00	0.10	15.10
Foothill Pine-Oak Woodland	11.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.20
Grain, Row-crop, Hay & Pasture, Disked/Short-term Fallowed	0.00	11.70	0.00	0.00	11.70
Urban-Suburban	12.00	4.70	2.90	0.01	19.61
Disturbed by FOCP ¹¹	87.50	0.10	0.10	0.00	87.70
TOTAL	1,375.62	101.28	3.59	11.55	1,492.04

⁷ Acreages for the Live Oak Restoration Reach in this table do not include portions of that CM that overlap the Seismic Retrofit area, which includes the North Channel maintenance area (0.002 acre of intermittent stream, 0.70 acre of perennial stream, 0.004 acre of coastal and valley freshwater marsh, 3.07 acres of mixed riparian woodland and forest, 3.5 acres of coast live oak forest and woodland, 0.1 acre of California annual grassland, and 0.6 acre of urban-suburban).

⁸ The “Total” column summarizes the total acreages within the Seismic Retrofit, Ogier Ponds CM, and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas. Additional minor impacts in the Ogier Ponds and Live Oak Restoration Reach areas may result from the Sediment Augmentation Program.

⁹ A total of 357.6 acres of reservoir are present within the currently proposed Seismic Retrofit construction footprint, and an additional 849.2 acres are additional areas within the reservoir where construction activities could potentially occur.

¹⁰ In addition to the 0.73 acre of perennial stream that will be impacted by Seismic Retrofit construction outside the FOCP footprint, 1.98 acres that will have been temporarily impacted by the FOCP may be impacted by Seismic Retrofit construction as well.

¹¹ Portions of the project area in the “Disturbed by FOCP” category will have been impacted by FOCP immediately prior to commencement of the Seismic Retrofit, Ogier Ponds CM, and Coyote Percolation Dam CM. Permanent SCVHP mitigation fees will have been paid by Valley Water for impacts to the areas that will have been permanently impacted by FOCP. The conditions within those areas will either be developed (“urban/suburban”) or some highly disturbed version of the underlying pre-FOCP land cover type that is no longer representative of a specific SCVHP land cover type when Seismic Retrofit activities commence. Therefore, the project baseline land cover type for these areas is not provided in Table 3.

height of its original design elevation due to DSOD and FERC restrictions since the FOCP in 2020. The exposed shoreline rim is rocky, steeply sloped, and sparsely vegetated in many areas, although some vegetation, including grasses, bull thistle, coyote brush, and Russian thistle, has become established in areas that have not recently been inundated. No substantial amounts of emergent vegetation are present in or around Anderson Reservoir.

The reservoir land cover type is also present within the Ogier Ponds CM area; there, the larger impoundments (Ponds 1, 2, and 4 of the Ogier Ponds complex) are considered reservoir due to the large size and deep nature of these artificial waterbodies (former gravel pits). Farther downstream, the portion of the Coyote Percolation Pond immediately upstream from the Coyote Percolation Dam CM is also considered reservoir.

Pond

The pond land cover type is present in the Seismic Retrofit area in a small pool immediately below the concrete-lined spillway at Anderson Dam, and in portions of the Ogier Ponds CM area. The small pond below the concrete-lined spillway is lined with rock and supports no substantive vegetation. At the Ogier Ponds, the pond land cover type is represented by Pond 5, a groundwater-supported pond that is not in-line with Coyote Creek as Ponds 1 through 4 are. Pond 5 is a shallow pond ringed by cattails and other emergent vegetation. Along Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas, additional off-channel ponds occur at the Ogier Ponds and near Coyote Ranch.

Perennial Stream

In the project area, perennial stream habitat is represented solely by Coyote Creek. Coyote Creek originates on Mount Sizer, located approximately 7 miles northeast of Anderson Dam, and flows through the western slope of the Diablo Range. At the base of the Diablo Range, the creek is impounded by two dams, first by Coyote Reservoir and then by Anderson Reservoir. Downstream of Anderson Reservoir, the creek continues north from Morgan Hill into San José and empties into San Francisco Bay. In some areas, the perennial stream habitat supports perennial marsh vegetation. Flow in the reach of Coyote Creek downstream of Coyote Dam and entering Anderson Reservoir is regulated by releases from Coyote Dam; these releases maintain perennial flows in the intervening reach. Downstream from Anderson Dam, flow is regulated primarily by releases from Anderson Dam. The perennial stream land cover type includes short segments of channel within the Ogier Ponds complex that carry water between reservoir/pond land cover types, as well as the reach of Coyote Creek within the Coyote Percolation Dam CM area and Live Oak Restoration Reach.

Intermittent Stream

In the Seismic Retrofit area, the intermittent stream land cover type is present within a channel between the waterfall downstream from the unlined portion of the Anderson Dam spillway and the North Channel of Coyote Creek, and within the North Channel itself (including the North Channel Extension area). These areas experience wet-season flow, typically at very low rates unless Anderson Reservoir is spilling. The majority of intermittent stream channel bed is excavated bedrock (associated with previous quarrying activities at Chert Hill) with little soil development, and therefore vegetation is typically sparse. Water moves within a dispersed, finger-like network of smaller channels during low flow events. Only during reservoir spill releases is the entire channel filled with water. Farther downstream, the North Channel of Coyote Creek is dominated by cobbles. Here the intermittent channel is underlain by riverwash, and a riparian forest canopy grows along the channel up to the top of bank.

Coastal and Valley Freshwater Marsh

In the Seismic Retrofit area, coastal and valley freshwater marsh occurs within the unlined portion of the Anderson Dam spillway and in very limited areas along the North Channel of Coyote Creek. Vegetation within this habitat is dominated by perennial aquatic emergent vegetation, such as cattails, and shoreline plants that grow along the edge of the aquatic habitat, such as iris-leaved rush, tall flatsedge, fringed willow herb, and fiddle dock. Coastal and valley freshwater marsh is present in several areas within the Ogier Ponds CM area. There, large stands of coastal and valley freshwater marsh dominated by cattails and California bulrush are present in the southwest portion of Pond 2 and around Pond 5, and small patches occur around the perimeter of Pond 1. Along Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas, coastal and valley freshwater marsh occurs in several additional areas, including areas downstream from the Coyote Creek Golf Course access road, upstream from Bailey Avenue, and near Coyote Ranch.

Seasonal Wetland

No seasonal wetland is present within the Seismic Retrofit area or Coyote Percolation Dam CM area. At the Ogier Ponds CM area, seasonal wetland is represented by a small depressional area in the historical channel of Coyote Creek, just south of Pond 4 at the Ogier Ponds. This seasonal wetland is likely supported by high groundwater during the wet season and is dominated by annual beard grass. This wetland is shallow and does not pond for long periods, even during the wet season. Along Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas, additional seasonal wetlands occur in portions of the Ogier Ponds complex that are outside of the Ogier Ponds CM area.

Mixed Riparian Woodland and Forest

In the Seismic Retrofit area, mixed riparian woodland and forest occurs along riparian corridors downstream of the Anderson Reservoir spillway and along Coyote Creek, including both the North and South Channels. This land cover type includes a variety of riparian shrubs and trees including arroyo willow, red willow, California sycamore, bigleaf maple, and white alder. These riparian tree species often co-occur with coast live oaks, and mixed riparian woodland and forest intergrades with coast live oak forest and woodland in some areas. The understory is composed of California blackberry, California wildrose, and other shrubs and herbaceous species along the banks.

Extensive mixed riparian woodland and forest is present in the Ogier Ponds CM area along the historical Coyote Creek channel downstream from Barnhart Avenue, along the current Coyote Creek channel at the downstream end of the Ogier Ponds complex, in the North Channel Extension and Live Oak Restoration Reach, and in several locations around the pond and reservoir land cover types. Dominant plant species here include arroyo willow, red willow, California sycamore, and Fremont cottonwood. At the Coyote Percolation Dam CM area, and along much of Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas, mixed riparian woodland and forest lines both sides of Coyote Creek.

Willow Riparian Forest and Scrub

No willow riparian forest and scrub is present within the Seismic Retrofit area or Coyote Percolation Dam CM area. At the Ogier Ponds CM area, this land cover type occurs in a number of locations. It is present along the segments of Coyote Creek that flow into and through the pond complex, around the perimeters of some of the pond/reservoir land cover types, and in a portion of the historical Coyote Creek channel downstream from Ogier Avenue. This land cover type is dominated by arroyo willow, red willow, and Fremont cottonwood, often in very dense

stands. Willow riparian forest and scrub is also present along several segments of Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas.

California Annual Grassland

California annual grassland is an herbaceous plant community dominated by nonnative annual grasses. Within the Seismic Retrofit area, this land cover type is found on the downstream dam face; in areas within the Basalt Hill Borrow Area and along access roads to that borrow area; along the edge of the reservoir rim (just above the high-water line); and within the Live Oak Picnic area. This land cover type also dominates most of the upland portions of the Ogier Ponds CM area, as well as most upland areas along Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas. Dominant species include nonnative grasses such wild oats, bromes, and Italian rye grass. Common nonnative and native forbs include clovers, filarees, Jersey cudweed, lupines, yarrow, and California poppy. Several invasive weeds are also common, including yellow star-thistle, bull thistle, and milk thistle. In addition, several small patches of native bunchgrass habitat are present around Anderson Dam (such as in and just north of the Basalt Hill Borrow Area) within areas mapped as California annual grassland or in small openings within other habitat types. Purple needlegrass is the dominant species in these native grasslands.

Mixed Serpentine Chaparral

Mixed serpentine chaparral occurs in the Seismic Retrofit area on dry slopes underlain by serpentine soils. The majority of mixed serpentine chaparral is present on the northern side of the Anderson Dam spillway (including both the concrete-lined and unlined portions), where extensive stands of this land cover type covering the ridge to the north barely extend into the project area. Smaller areas of mixed serpentine chaparral are present within the project area just northeast of the spillway and northeast of the boat ramp at Anderson Dam; in both areas, proposed project activities will extend into the chaparral above the reservoir rim, into mixed serpentine chaparral. Coyote ceanothus forms dense stands and dominates this land cover type. Other common shrubs include California sagebrush, toyon, coyote brush, and bigberry manzanita. This habitat also includes several small serpentine rock outcrops at the base of Silica Carbonate Hill. Just outside the project area, Santa Clara Valley dudleya occur on these outcrops.

Northern Coastal Scrub/Diablan Sage Scrub

The northern coastal scrub/Diablan sage scrub land cover type occurs on dry, exposed slopes with shallow soils within the Seismic Retrofit area. This land cover type includes several different shrub communities that intergrade on the site. Areas of northern coastal scrub/Diablan sage scrub in the Basalt Hill Borrow Area are dominated by coyote brush and support little plant diversity. A large contiguous patch of scrub habitat on the right (north) abutment of Anderson Dam and patches along the southern edge of the unlined portion of the Anderson Dam spillway and in the former Chert Hill quarry area support a diverse assemblage of native shrubs including California sagebrush, black sage, and yerba santa. California buckwheat, sticky monkey flower, Coyote ceanothus, and bigberry manzanita also occur in this land cover type. In areas with dense shrub cover, there is very little herbaceous community; however, occasional openings support both native and nonnative grasses and forbs.

Coast Live Oak Woodland and Forest

In the Seismic Retrofit area, coast live oak forest and woodland generally occurs on mesic (moderately moist) slopes and in lowland areas with relatively deep, fertile soil. The majority of this land cover type occurs on flat terrain along Coyote Creek in the Live Oak Picnic area,

directly north of Cochrane Road. Smaller patches are present on the northeast side of the Basalt Hill Borrow Area and along its associated access road.

At the Ogier Ponds CM area, coast live oak forest and woodland is present along the southwestern terrace above the historical Coyote Creek channel on either side of Ogier Avenue, and in one small patch southeast of Pond 4. Coast live oak is the dominant tree species. The majority of areas mapped as this land cover type are woodlands with open canopies; however, several relatively small but dense patches support overlapping canopies and could be classified as forest. This land cover type also includes occasional California bay and California sycamore trees. Common woody understory species include toyon and California blackberry. The herbaceous community is similar to that of the California annual grassland community, but with a greater component of native forbs and grasses.

Foothill Pine-Oak Woodland

Foothill pine-oak woodland generally occurs in drier areas with shallow soils and often intergrades with scrub and chaparral habitats. In the Seismic Retrofit area, this land cover type occurs throughout much of the rocky Basalt Hill Borrow Area, on portions of the right (north) abutment of Anderson Dam, and on slopes north of the unlined portion of the spillway and in the Chert Hill area. The dominant tree species is foothill pine. In disturbed areas, the understory is often dominated by nonnative, invasive species including pampas grass. In less disturbed areas the understory contains a higher proportion of native trees and shrubs, including coast live oak, coyote brush, and toyon. The herbaceous layer is generally similar to that in the California annual grassland habitat but is sparse in some areas due to a buildup of pine needles and thatch.

Grain, Row-crop, Hay and Pasture, Disked/Short-term Fallowed

The grain, row-crop, hay and pasture, disked/short-term fallowed land cover type occurs in the project area only at the Ogier Ponds CM area. There, this land cover type is represented by an agricultural field on the northwest side of the Monterey Road/Barnhart Avenue intersection. Based on a review of aerial photos, this field is disced frequently and has been mostly bare in recent years, though it has apparently been planted in hay in some years. Weedy plant species, such as those occurring in California annual grassland described above, likely occur in this field when it is fallow.

Urban-Suburban

The urban-suburban land cover type includes developed/artificial habitats such as access roads, parking lots, structures (including the dam spillway), park facilities associated with Anderson Lake County Park, and landscaped areas. This land cover type also includes areas with a very low cover of ruderal species, similar to those occurring within the California annual grassland plant community, growing on the rocky soils east of the dam crest. Several earthen or concrete-lined swales occur directly adjacent to the existing roads. Urban-suburban areas are also present along roads at the Ogier Ponds CM area and hardscaped and graveled areas at the Coyote Percolation Dam CM area. Landscaped areas support a variety of nonnative and native species including Peruvian pepper tree, rosemary, and planted coast live oaks.

Central California Sycamore Alluvial Woodland

The central California sycamore alluvial woodland land cover type is absent from the Seismic Retrofit, Ogier Ponds CM, and Coyote Percolation Dam CM areas, and no project construction activities are proposed or expected to occur in sycamore alluvial woodland. However, this land cover type is described here because it is present in two areas along Coyote Creek between the Seismic Retrofit area and the Coyote Percolation Dam CM area. Sycamore alluvial woodland is

present on the northeast side of Coyote Creek just downstream from U.S. Highway 101 (upstream from the Ogier Ponds) and adjacent to the Coyote Creek Golf Course. Sycamore alluvial woodland occurs in broad floodplains with deep alluvial material and is dominated by western sycamores, with lesser numbers of species such as willows and coast live oak. The sycamores are widely spaced, allowing ample light to reach the ground, so that ground cover is similar in most areas to California annual grassland.

Habitats within the Action Area outside of the Proposed Project Footprint

The proposed project will also result in direct and/or indirect effects on biological resources in portions of the action area that are outside the proposed project areas described above. The limits of the action area cannot be defined precisely due to uncertainty regarding the extent to which indirect effects (such as effects of nitrogen emissions and deposition) may occur, but Figure 1 indicates areas referenced below. Given the vast extent of this action area and the uncertainty regarding the precise locations of impacts to this area, habitat/land cover types within the action area have not been mapped or quantified as those within the project area have. Land cover types within these areas are generally described as follows:

Steelhead Relocation Sites

Steelhead may be relocated to Coyote Creek near its confluence with Upper Penitencia Creek and/or the reach of Upper Penitencia Creek in Alum Rock Park. Land cover types in both areas consist of perennial stream, mixed riparian woodland forest, and urban-suburban, and characteristic plant and animal species are as described above for those three land cover types. Upper Penitencia Creek is lined with big-leaf maple white alder and western sycamore. The proposed steelhead relocation site in Coyote Creek near the confluence with Upper Penitencia Creek is surrounded by high-density urban and industrial development and is adjacent to the San Jose Flea Market. The proposed steelhead relocation site in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park occurs in a more natural setting in an east-west canyon with steep sides surrounded by grasslands, shrublands, and woodlands that are protected as a wildlife sanctuary; this site receives a moderate level of disturbance by people recreating at the 720-acre Alum Rock Park.

Coyote Creek Downstream to San Francisco Bay

Coyote Creek from Anderson Dam downstream to southern San Francisco Bay, which runs a distance of approximately 40 stream miles, could be affected by changes in flow rates and sediment mobilization during project construction; the lower limits of this impact area, at the mouth of Coyote Slough, were established by modeling of sediment mobilization (AECOM 2021).

Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam consists of a non-tidal channel for approximately 31.5 stream miles. Land cover types in this reach include primarily perennial stream, mixed riparian woodland and forest, willow riparian forest and scrub, coastal and valley freshwater marsh, and urban-suburban. Limited areas of central California sycamore alluvial woodland, which is dominated by California sycamore, are also present (e.g., just downstream from U.S. Highway 101 between Anderson Dam and the Ogier Ponds, and just downstream from the Ogier Ponds). Valley Water typically releases enough water from Anderson Dam (or other sources) to maintain flow throughout the reach downstream from the dam. This segment of creek supports a largely natural (as opposed to concrete-lined) bed and banks. Along these nontidal reaches of creek, dominant land cover types are mixed riparian woodland and forest, and willow riparian forest and scrub, with limited areas of sycamore alluvial woodland. Dominant trees include yellow willow, red willow, arroyo willow, Fremont cottonwood, California sycamore,

and box elder. These riparian land cover types occur mostly as narrow corridors of vegetation due to encroachment by adjacent land uses, maintenance of areas outside the riparian habitats (e.g., for flood management or anthropogenic uses), and lack of adequate water to support riparian trees and shrubs. Golf courses/urban parks line portions of Coyote Creek as well.

Tidal reaches of Coyote Creek/Coyote Slough include approximately 8.5 stream miles from the vicinity of Dixon Landing Road downstream to the Coyote Slough/Alviso Slough confluence. These tidal reaches flow through marsh that is fresh/brackish in their upper reaches, where they are dominated by California bulrush, alkali bulrush, cattails, and perennial pepperweed, but this vegetation transitions into salt marsh species such as Pacific cordgrass, pickleweed, and marsh gumplant toward the downstream portion of Coyote Slough. Mudflats are exposed at low tide along Coyote Slough, those these mudflats become extensive only toward the lower portion of the slough. Tidal areas at elevations too low to support emergent vegetation consist of subtidal areas that are inundated even at the lowest tides and intertidal mudflats that are exposed during low tide.

Groundwater-Dependent Wetlands in North Coyote Valley

North Coyote Valley is dominated by agricultural activities, represented in the SCVHP as a “grain, row crop, hay & pasture, disked/short-term fallowed” land cover type. However, some natural land cover types are present as well. These include perennial ponds, seasonal wetlands, willow riparian forest and scrub, and mixed riparian woodland and forest. Areas along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley supporting wetland (coastal and valley freshwater marsh and seasonal wetland), aquatic (pond and perennial stream), or riparian (mixed riparian woodland, and forest and willow riparian forest and scrub) habitats, which are dependent on groundwater levels, could be subject to reduced water availability if Coyote Creek flows decrease during project construction. The characteristic plant and animal communities present in these areas are as described for these land cover types above. However, seasonal wetlands are much more extensive in North Coyote Valley than they are in the project area.

In particular, Laguna Seca is a large seasonal wetland in North Coyote Valley that historically spanned more than 1,000 acres (<https://news.openspaceauthority.org/blog/new-era-for-laguna-seca>). It sits in a low basin near where Fisher Creek meets Coyote Creek (Figure 2). During wet years, Laguna Seca becomes a large, shallow lake. Historically, the wetland existed nearly year-round, where water would fan out and fill the basin in the rainy season, at times getting up to 10 feet deep (<https://news.openspaceauthority.org/blog/new-era-for-laguna-seca>). However, in 1916, Laguna Seca was completely transformed and repurposed for agricultural use, disrupting the marshland ecology of the basin through draining, ditching, clearing, burning, and disking (<https://news.openspaceauthority.org/blog/new-era-for-laguna-seca>). As a result of this disturbance, modern-day Laguna Seca is dry for most of the year and typically only holds surface water during the rainy winter seasons. The Santa Clara Open Space Authority, in partnership with Peninsula Open Space Trust and the City of San Jose, is planning the restoration of Laguna Seca by increasing the abundance of groundwater and restoring the floodplain (<https://news.openspaceauthority.org/blog/new-era-for-laguna-seca>).

In November 2019, the San Jose City Council unanimously approved the purchase and permanent protection of 937 acres in the North Coyote Valley through a public and private partnership with the Peninsula Open Space Trust and the Santa Clara Valley Open Space Authority (<https://protectcoyotevalley.org/timeline/>). In November 2021, the San Jose City Council voted to change the land use designation of North Coyote Valley to open space and agriculture, and to remove the Urban Reserve designation from Mid Coyote Valley, thus

relinquishing all intent of annexation and development (<https://protectcoyotevalley.org/timeline/>). In December 2021, the Santa Clara County Board of Supervisors approved a Climate Resilience District for both Mid and South Coyote Valley, imposing restrictions on the size and type of development allowable there and supporting climate-resilient agriculture (<https://protectcoyotevalley.org/timeline/>). As a result of the City and County actions, Coyote Valley is now protected from urban-scale development (<https://protectcoyotevalley.org/timeline/>).

Serpentine Communities along Coyote Ridge Downwind of Project Construction Areas

Serpentine communities (e.g., serpentine bunchgrass grassland and mixed serpentine chaparral) (Figure 1), such as those on Coyote Ridge that are located downwind (primarily east and southeast) of the Seismic Retrofit and Ogier Ponds CM construction areas, are in the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen emissions from equipment and vehicles during project construction. Thus, these serpentine habitats could be adversely affected by the proposed project's contribution to the cumulative effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition that could degrade these habitats by facilitating the spread of invasive plant species. The serpentine bunchgrass grasslands subject to such effects include much more extensive, higher-quality grassland, such as that dominating Coyote Ridge to the north of Anderson Dam, than is present in the project area. Serpentine bunchgrass grassland on Coyote Ridge supports native plant communities dominated by purple needlegrass and a variety of forbs, including rare plants such as Santa Clara Valley dudleya, federally listed as endangered Metcalf Canyon jewelflower (*Streptanthus glandulosus* ssp. *albidus*), and most beautiful jewelflower.

Serpentine communities occur on hills on either side of the Santa Clara Valley, from Coyote Ridge on the east and the Santa Teresa Hills on the west, south to the San Martin and Harvey Bear Ranch areas. Smaller patches of serpentine grassland occur elsewhere, such as on Communications Hill, Tulare Hill, and north of Alum Rock in San Jose. These communities occur on shallow soils derived from serpentinite. Most serpentine soils support a diverse grassland assemblage dominated by dwarf plantain, Italian ryegrass, and spring and summer wildflowers, including goldfields, buttercup, purple owl's-clover, exserted paintbrush, and tidy-tips, among many others. Native grasses, such as purple needlegrass, junegrass, big squirreltail, and creeping wildrye, are common throughout this community. Serpentine grasslands support Bay checkerspot butterfly and several rare plant species, such as Metcalf Canyon jewelflower, most beautiful jewelflower, smooth lessingia, and Tiburon paintbrush. Other serpentine communities also support rare plants; for example, serpentine rock outcrops/barrens may support Santa Clara Valley dudleya, serpentine seeps support Mt. Hamilton thistle, and mixed serpentine chaparral supports Coyote ceanothus and Loma Prieta hoita.

California Red-legged Frog

California red-legged frogs are not known or expected to breed in Anderson Reservoir, which is not considered suitable habitat for the species (ICF International 2012). Designated critical habitat unit STC-1 is located immediately northeast of Anderson Reservoir, and the reach of Upper Penitencia Creek that may be used as a steelhead relocation site is located within that unit (Service 2010). At Anderson Dam itself, California red-legged frogs have been observed in only one area – three adults were observed in cattail-lined pools within the unlined portion of the spillway, downstream from the concrete spillway, during monitoring associated with proposed project geotechnical investigations in June 2020; two of these individuals were relocated to Rosendin Pond approximately 0.3 mile southeast of the dam spillway to prevent injury during the geotechnical work (the third individual moved out of the work area on its own). The pools in

the unlined spillway are unlikely to support a viable breeding population of California red-legged frogs due to the abundance of non-native bullfrogs and fish, which may prey on California red-legged frog eggs or larvae. During the aforementioned monitoring, 248 non-native largemouth bass, black crappie, and common carp, as well as 510 red swamp crayfish and 31 adult, 165 metamorph, and 3,131 larval bullfrogs were removed from the unlined portion of the spillway. Nevertheless, the occurrence of California red-legged frogs in the unlined spillway suggests that the species could attempt breeding in the unlined spillway chute and demonstrates the ability of the species to reach Anderson Dam from nearby breeding locations. The pools below the spillway waterfall could also potentially support breeding attempts by California red-legged frogs.

Suitable breeding habitat for California red-legged frogs is present in Rosendin Pond, 0.3 mile southeast of the dam spillway and approximately 500 feet southeast of Basalt Hill. Juvenile California red-legged frogs have been observed at Rosendin Pond over several years, indicating that California red-legged frogs likely breed in this pond. California red-legged frogs may also breed in and disperse from other ponds scattered around Anderson Reservoir, and though the reservoir itself does not provide suitable habitat for the species, California red-legged frogs may disperse into the bed of the dewatered reservoir. California red-legged frogs could also use small mammal burrows and crevices present throughout the Seismic Retrofit component of the action area as refugia. However, because no individuals were found during burrow scoping surveys on the dam during four years of surveys (Valley Water 2010, 2011, 2012b, 2013), this species is expected to use such upland refugia infrequently and in low numbers.

Within the action area, California red-legged frogs are expected to occur in Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam only as rare dispersants, and the species is not expected to occur at all within the lower, more urban reaches of Coyote Creek. The majority of the reach of Coyote Creek between Anderson Dam and the Ogier Ponds provides relatively low-quality breeding habitat because it conveys sustained flows of 2 to 3 feet deep with few deeper, slow flowing or still pools or backwater areas. Nonnative predatory fish, crayfish, and bullfrogs are also abundant throughout Coyote Creek, further reducing the probability that California red-legged frogs successfully breed there, and there are no records of California red-legged frogs in Coyote Creek between Anderson Dam and the Ogier Ponds (CDFW 2024). However, California red-legged frog adults, tadpoles, and egg masses were reported at an unspecified location in the Ogier Ponds in 2002 and 2003 (California Natural Diversity Database [CNDDDB] occurrence number 620, CDFW 2024). The Ogier Ponds provide ostensibly suitable habitat for breeding California red-legged frogs, but bullfrogs (and nonnative fish in some ponds) are abundant, making the Ogier Ponds an unlikely location to support a viable California red-legged frog population. Nevertheless, based on the presence of ostensibly suitable habitat conditions, as well as the 2002-2003 CNDDDB record, baseline surveys were conducted along Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam in 2019. No individual California red-legged frogs were observed during these focused daytime and nighttime visual encounter surveys. Furthermore, no individual California red-legged frogs of any life stage were observed during concurrent baseline Central California tiger salamander larval surveys of the off-channel Ogier Ponds (Valley Water 2019).

These negative survey results, coupled with the abundance of non-native, predatory fish and bullfrogs in study reaches of Coyote Creek and associated ponds, suggest that it is unlikely that a breeding population of California red-legged frogs is present, or that this species occurs regularly or in substantial numbers, in Coyote Creek and associated aquatic habitats downstream from Anderson Dam. However, the species is known to be present in ponds, wetlands, and streams near the Kirby Canyon landfill across U.S. Highway 101, approximately 0.5 mile east of Coyote

Creek, and it has also been recorded in the Coyote Canal where it crosses under U.S. Highway 101 (CDFW 2024). There are seven CNDDDB occurrences of the California red-legged frog within 0.3 mile of Coyote Creek primarily on the opposite side (east) of U.S. Highway 101 (CDFW 2024):

1. An unspecified number of California red-legged frogs observed in the vicinity of the Kirby Canyon landfill California red-legged frog mitigation site along U.S. Highway 101 within 0.3-0.6 mile east of Ogier Ponds within the Coyote Canal and within three ponds in 2016 and in two ponds in 2017 (CNDDDB occurrence number 538, CDFW 2024);
2. One adult and 20 California red-legged frog tadpoles observed in an in-channel pool off Coyote Canal and tributaries at the Coyote Ridge Open Space Preserve in April 2012 within 0.3-0.7 mile east of the Bailey Avenue bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,117, CDFW 2024);
3. One adult and 20 California red-legged frog tadpoles observed in an in-channel pool off Coyote Canal and tributaries in April 2012 within 0.55-0.75 mile north of the Bailey Avenue bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,525, CDFW 2024);
4. Two adult California red-legged frogs observed in a foothill spring in August 2007 approximately 0.6 mile northeast of the Coyote Ranch Road bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 991, CDFW 2024);
5. Four adult California red-legged frogs observed in the Coyote Creek Canal extension near Metcalf Road in August 2000 approximately 0.28 mile northeast of Parkway Lakes and 0.5 mile northeast of the Metcalf Road bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 419, CDFW 2024);
6. An unknown number of California red-legged frogs observed at the Basking Ridge Preserve mitigation site near Metcalf Road in June 1999 approximately 0.28 mile northeast of Parkway Lakes and 0.5 mile northeast of the Metcalf Road bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 556, CDFW 2024); and
7. One adult and two juvenile California red-legged frogs observed on both sides of U.S. Highway 101 adjacent to and within 0.28 east of the U.S. Highway 101 crossing over Coyote Creek near Highway 85 (CNDDDB occurrence number 553, CDFW 2024).

California red-legged frogs from these sites could occasionally disperse under U.S. Highway 101 toward the Ogier Ponds and Coyote Creek using culverts. Such individuals could then occur in Coyote Creek, the Ogier Ponds, and the Coyote Ranch and Metcalf Ponds farther north, and the species could even attempt breeding in these areas. However, it is highly unlikely that a viable breeding population is currently established in any areas that could be affected by proposed project dewatering. Therefore, this species is considered a possible rare and infrequent dispersant in areas that could potentially be affected by changes in flow in and along Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam.

Coyote Creek flow may influence groundwater levels in North Coyote Valley, and therefore the occurrence of the California red-legged frog in North Coyote Valley is also considered. Although the species has been recorded on either side of Coyote Valley, such as in a number of locations east of U.S. Highway 101 and in the hills to the west, there are no records of the species on the

valley floor apart from the 2002-2003 record from the Ogier Ponds (CNDDDB occurrence number 620, CDFW 2024). For example, a number of surveys for the species have been conducted along Fisher Creek and in ponds in North Coyote Valley, yet the species has not been detected (HTH 2000e, 2000f, 2000g, 2006a, 2006b, 2007a, 2007b, 2020a, and 2021).

California red-legged frogs are known to occur within the action area along reaches of Upper Penitencia Creek where steelhead relocation may occur at Alum Rock Park: four adult California red-legged frogs were observed there in 2013 (CNDDDB occurrence number 410, CDFW 2024). The species has been recorded on several occasions (and recently) within Upper Penitencia Creek in and upstream from Alum Rock Park.

The action area is located in the South and East San Francisco Bay recovery unit for the California red-legged frog (Service 2002). No core areas for the California red-legged frog are located within the action area (Service 2002). Only the steelhead relocation area is located within designated critical habitat unit STC-1 for the California red-legged frog (Service 2010). The eastern shoreline of Anderson Reservoir is located along the boundary of designated critical habitat unit STC-1 (Service 2010).

Based on the known occurrence of the California red-legged frog within and near the action area and the availability of suitable aquatic habitat and upland dispersal habitat within the action area, the Service believes the California red-legged frog is likely to disperse, forage, and shelter within the action area.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

The California red-legged frog is a covered species under the SCVHP. The SCVHP authorizes over the 50-year permit term the permanent loss of 299 acres of primary habitat (i.e., aquatic habitat) and 12,937 acres of secondary habitat (i.e., upland dispersal habitat) and the temporary disturbance of 116 acres of primary habitat and 1,489 acres of secondary habitat (International 2012). As of June 2023 (Year 11 of the SCVHP), the SCVHP has authorized 19 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of primary habitat, 10 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of secondary habitat, 23 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of primary habitat, and 38 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of secondary habitat for the California red-legged frog (SCVHA 2024a, Table 6). The SCVHP requires by Year 45 (2057) the preservation of 1,430 acres of modeled primary habitat and 41,800 acres of modeled secondary habitat for the California red-legged frog in the SCVHP reserve system (ICF International 2012, p. 5-148). As of June 2023, the SCVHP has achieved approximately 28 percent of the preservation requirements for California red-legged frog primary habitat and 35 percent of the preservation requirements for California red-legged frog secondary habitat (SCVHA 2024a, Figure 8). The SCVHP requires that 40 percent of the ponds in the reserve system in each of the two California red-legged frog recovery units have documented successful breeding California red-legged frogs (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023, in the SCVHP reserve system, four out of 25 (16 percent) of the ponds in the South and East San Francisco Bay recovery unit (unit 4) and none of the 13 ponds (0 percent) in the Diablo Range/Salinas Valley recovery unit (unit 6) have documented successful breeding California red-legged frogs (SCVHA 2024a, Table 9).

Central Coast Foothill Yellow-legged Frog

There are no recent records of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog from the majority of the proposed project area, including in the vicinity of Anderson Dam and Reservoir, the Ogier Ponds, or the Coyote Percolation Dam Phase 2 Fish Passage Enhancement Project. The SCVHP

models portions of Coyote Creek below Anderson Reservoir as secondary habitat for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog (ICF International 2012). However, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are no longer known to occur along Santa Clara County streams below major reservoirs, including Anderson Reservoir (Valley Water 1999, CDFW 2024). No surveys conducted for the Dam Maintenance Program, FOCPP, or the proposed project have detected the species at or near Anderson Dam. Reconnaissance-level surveys and habitat assessments for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, conducted in April, June, and August 2016 along the reach of Coyote Creek between Coyote Dam and Anderson Reservoir, did not detect the species (Valley Water 2016). Similarly, reconnaissance-level surveys along this reach of creek for the Coyote Canyon County Park Natural Resource Management Plan did not detect any Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs (HTH 2019).

In 2019, focused surveys for Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were conducted in April, May, and June along Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam to provide baseline information for monitoring of the effects of the proposed project dewatering on SCVHP-covered species (Valley Water 2019). These surveys covered reaches of the creek from Metcalf Road to Coyote Ranch Road; from Bailey Avenue to the Coyote Creek Golf Course and along the southwest side of the Coyote Creek Golf Course; from the south end of the Ogier Ponds to the U.S. Highway 101 overpass; and from U.S. Highway 101 upstream to the Anderson Dam outlet. No Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were detected.

The nearest known extant occurrence of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog to the action area is located along Otis Creek, a tributary to the reach of Coyote Creek that extends from Coyote Dam to Anderson Reservoir, approximately 0.4 mile upstream from the confluence of Otis Creek with Coyote Creek in August 2019 (Sullivan 2019). The nearest presumed extant CNDDDB occurrence of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog to the action area is from San Felipe Creek, approximately 4.5 miles upstream from the nearest proposed project stockpiling area and 1.45 miles northeast of the northwestern arm of Anderson Reservoir (CNDDDB occurrence number 94, CDFW 2024); this record is from 1971 and may no longer be an extant occurrence (CDFW 2024). The CNDDDB also includes a number of occurrences along Coyote Creek and its tributaries upstream from Coyote Reservoir at Palassou Ridge Open Space Preserve and Henry W. Coe State Park (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 119, 118, 117, 98, 120, 96, 97, and 99; CDFW 2024).

Given the presence of Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs in Otis Creek, it is possible that this species could disperse into Coyote Creek between Coyote Dam and Anderson Reservoir. Breeding along this reach of Coyote Creek could occur if hydrologic conditions were suitable, though variability in releases from Coyote Dam (as a part of the normal operations of the dam) during the breeding season could result in streamflow reduction that could lead to desiccation of egg masses or stranding of tadpoles. As a result, it is unlikely that this reach of Coyote Creek supports a viable breeding population. If Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were to disperse into Anderson Reservoir from either Otis Canyon/Coyote Creek to the south or San Felipe Creek to the north, normal conditions in Anderson Reservoir (i.e., the presence of vast, deep water) would likely prevent this stream-dwelling frog from reaching Anderson Dam. When the reservoir is dewatered during proposed project implementation, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs could attempt to disperse into the bed of the reservoir along these tributaries. However, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are closely associated with cobbly streams, whereas areas where proposed project activities will occur in Anderson Reservoir are lined with fine sediment that has accumulated in the reservoir bed and lack any riparian vegetation. Due to the expected low sizes (owing to the paucity of recent records and detections during surveys) of

Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog populations that occur in areas where they could disperse to the proposed project area, there is a very low probability that Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs would occur in areas where proposed project activities will take place within the bed of the dewatered reservoir. Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are not expected to reach Anderson Dam itself, or to occur along Coyote Creek downstream from the dam.

Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are present in Upper Penitencia Creek upstream of where steelhead may need to be relocated if conditions for fish in the FCWMZ become unsuitable during proposed project construction. Six juvenile Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were found in Upper Penitencia Creek approximately 0.7 mile east of (upstream from) its confluence with Arroyo Aguague in 2008 (CNDDDB occurrence number 57, CDFW 2024); this location is above a fish passage barrier for steelhead at Alum Rock Canyon. The species was also detected in Upper Penitencia upstream from Cherry Flat Reservoir in May 2020 approximately 3 miles east (upstream) of the proposed steelhead relocation area (CNDDDB occurrence number 177, CDFW 2024). The CNDDDB reports a presumed extant occurrence of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog at the proposed steelhead relocation area in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park, but the species was last observed at this location in 1973 (CNDDDB occurrence number 56, CDFW 2024). The lack of recent detections lower in Upper Penitencia Creek, where steelhead relocation would occur (if it is necessary at all), suggests that Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are scarce or absent in the areas that may be affected by proposed project activities.

Based on the known occurrence of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog in Upper Penitencia Creek upstream of the proposed steelhead relocation area, the Service believes the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog has a moderate potential to forage and disperse within the proposed steelhead relocation area though infrequently and in low numbers. The Service believes the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog has a very low potential to occur in the bed of Anderson Reservoir when it is dewatered during proposed project construction due to its known occurrence in tributaries upstream but lack of suitable cobbled stream habitat and riparian vegetation in the bed of Anderson Reservoir.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

The Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog is a covered species under the SCVHP. The SCVHP authorizes over the 50-year permit term the permanent loss of 2 miles of primary habitat (e.g., stream breeding habitat) and 5 miles of secondary habitat (e.g., stream non-breeding habitat) and the temporary disturbance of 0.7 mile of primary habitat and 1.3 miles of secondary habitat (International 2012). As of June 2023 (Year 11 of the SCVHP), the SCVHP has authorized 15 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of primary habitat, 18 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of secondary habitat, 29 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of primary habitat, and 24 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of secondary habitat for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog (SCVHA 2024a, Table 6). The SCVHP requires by Year 45 (2057) the preservation of 104 miles of modeled primary and secondary habitat for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog in the SCVHP reserve system (ICF International 2012, p. 5-151). The SCVHP reserve system is expected to protect at least four known breeding occurrences of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog in at least four of the watersheds: three on Llagas Creek above Chesbro Reservoir, and one on San Felipe Creek above Anderson Reservoir (ICF International 2012, p. 5-152). As of June 2023, the SCVHP has achieved approximately 22 percent of the preservation requirements for Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog primary habitat and 26 percent of the preservation requirements for Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog secondary habitat (SCVHA 2024a, Figure 8). As of fall 2023, two

breeding occurrences of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog have been protected within the SCVHA reserve system in Llagas Creek at the Calero County Park Preserve and the Lakeside Ranch Preserve (SCVHA 2024b, Table 9; Nomad Ecology 2023; CNDDDB occurrence numbers 91 and 93, CDFW 2024). At the Calero County Park Preserve, eight juveniles and one adult Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog were observed in Llagas Creek in 2018, and nine adults, two subadults, four juveniles, and more than 1,000 tadpoles/metamorphs were observed in 2017 (CNDDDB occurrence number 91, CDFW 2024). At the Lakeside Ranch Preserve, one adult Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog and one egg mass were observed in Llagas Creek on May 19, 2023, and 46 young of the year and one metamorph Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog were observed on September 9, 2023 (Nomad Ecology 2023). No Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were observed in Heron Creek at the Lakeside Ranch Preserve although it provides suitable breeding habitat for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog (Nomad Ecology 2023).

Central California Tiger Salamander

No critical habitat for the Central California tiger salamander occurs within or immediately adjacent to the action area; the nearest critical habitat unit (Unit 7, also known as the San Felipe Creek Unit) is located northwest of Anderson Reservoir (Service 2005). Annual surveys conducted on all burrows on the dam faces from 2010 through 2013 using a fiber-optic scope did not detect Central California tiger salamanders using burrows on the site (Valley Water 2010, 2011, 2012b, 2013). However, Central California tiger salamanders are known to occur in the vicinity of the proposed project area. In 2001, a Central California tiger salamander was observed on the roadway between the top of the parking lot and Anderson Dam (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 535, CDFW 2024), and in 2011, a Central California tiger salamander was observed in a weep hole in the floor of the dam spillway during a pre-work biological inspection (Valley Water 2012b). On March 4, 2016, an individual was found in a drain near the top of the boat ramp (S. Rottenborn, HTH, pers. obs.). A known Central California tiger salamander breeding pond (Rosendin Pond) is located 0.3 mile southeast of the dam spillway and approximately 500 feet southeast of the Basalt Hill Borrow Area portion of the proposed project area (CNDDDB occurrence number 591, CDFW 2024).

Additional ponds that provide potentially suitable breeding habitat for the Central California tiger salamander are present at various locations around Anderson Reservoir. Central California tiger salamanders are known to disperse up to 1.3 miles from breeding locations (Orloff 2007). Virtually all of the Seismic Retrofit component of the proposed project area, including the dam, staging areas, and in-reservoir work areas, are located within potential dispersal distance for Central California tiger salamanders breeding in the Rosendin Pond or, if Central California tiger salamanders are present in other ponds around the reservoir, within dispersal distance of those ponds. Central California tiger salamanders could potentially occur within these areas during seasonal movements to and from breeding ponds, and they may use burrows of small mammals, such as California ground squirrels and valley pocket gophers, on the site as upland refugia. Thus, Central California tiger salamanders are known to occur in and near the dam and reservoir portions of the proposed project area, although they likely do so infrequently and in low numbers given the paucity of records near the dam. The “reservoir” land cover type is not considered suitable habitat for this species (ICF International 2012), though individuals may disperse into the bed of the dewatered reservoir.

Central California tiger salamanders do not breed in swiftly flowing streams such as Coyote Creek. Downstream of Anderson Dam, a number of ponds provide ostensibly suitable breeding

habitat for Central California tiger salamanders. Central California tiger salamanders were observed in a pond at the Riverside Golf Course in 1996 within approximately 900 feet of the Coyote Creek Golf Drive bridge over Coyote Creek (CNDDDB occurrence number 462, CDFW 2024). Central California tiger salamanders were also observed in ponds near Parkway Lakes within 0.1-0.7 mile from Coyote Creek on the opposite of U.S. Highway 101 in (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 465, 581, and 1,062, CDFW 2024); some of the ponds have since been lost to residential development, but the adjacent grasslands and a few ponds are being preserved and managed for the Central California tiger salamander at the 206-acre Basking Ridge Preserve as mitigation for the development (Land Trust of Santa Clara Valley 2024).

The only location providing potentially suitable breeding habitat in ponds with a direct hydrologic connection to Coyote Creek (and therefore in an area that could be affected by increased or decreased streamflow related to proposed project dewatering) is the Ogier Ponds, which were modeled by the SCVHP as potential breeding habitat for the species. Therefore, a subset of these ponds was investigated during 2019 baseline surveys (Valley Water 2019). In the Ogier Ponds that are in-line with Coyote Creek, successful Central California tiger salamander breeding is not expected to occur due to the abundance of large predatory fish and bullfrogs (Barry and Shaffer 1994, Shaffer and Trenham 2005). Even in the Ogier Ponds that are not in-line with the creek, the abundance of predatory bullfrogs, fish, and crayfish likely precludes maintenance of a viable Central California tiger salamander breeding population. Although some of those ponds are seasonal, the seasonal ponds are hydrologically connected to perennial ponds when groundwater levels are high enough, allowing fish and crayfish to enter even the seasonal ponds. Nevertheless, larval surveys were conducted in 2019 in a group of ponds that are not in-line with Coyote Creek to determine whether there was evidence of breeding by Central California tiger salamanders. No Central California tiger salamander larvae were detected. Instead, vertebrate species captured and/or observed were adult, juvenile, and larval bullfrogs, larval Pacific treefrogs, and small fish, including mosquito fish. Because these fish and bullfrogs are known to adversely affect Central California tiger salamander breeding (Fisher and Shaffer 1996, Leyse 2005, Shaffer and Trenham 2005), the Central California tiger salamander is not expected to breed successfully in these ponds. For the same reasons, Central California tiger salamanders are not expected to breed in the Parkway Lakes ponds or the Metcalf Percolation Pond, near the location of the proposed Coyote Percolation Dam Phase 2 Fish Passage activities.

Coyote Creek flow may influence groundwater levels in North Coyote Valley, and therefore the occurrence of Central California tiger salamanders in North Coyote Valley was also considered. This species has been recorded breeding in several ponds on the west side of the North Coyote Valley floor south of Bailey Avenue and west of Santa Teresa Boulevard, and adults have been observed on the western edge of the valley floor in that area (HTH 2000a, 2000b, 2000c, 2020, 2021; CNDDDB occurrence numbers 343, 345, 346, 347, 348, 459, 460, and 461, CDFW 2024). Surveys in other ponds and pools in North Coyote Valley have not detected the species (HTH 2000d, 2002, 2003, 2020a, 2021).

Central California tiger salamanders are unlikely to occur at the steelhead relocation site in Upper Penitencia Creek due to swift flows and the presence of fish and bullfrogs, and other aquatic predators. However, there are several CNDDDB occurrences of the Central California tiger salamander within 2-2.5 miles of the steelhead relocation site in Upper Penitencia Creek, and suitable upland habitat is located between these occurrences and the steelhead relocation site (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 362, 925, and 952, CDFW 2024). Therefore, if any amphibians were infected by amphibian diseases at the steelhead relocation site, they could disperse into

occupied Central California tiger salamander habitat in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed and infect Central California tiger salamanders.

The action area is located in the East Bay recovery unit and the Northwest Diablo Range management unit for the Central California tiger salamander (Service 2017).

Based on the many known occurrences of the Central California tiger salamander within the salamander's 1.3-mile dispersal distance of the action area and the availability of suitable habitat within the action area, the Service believes the Central California tiger salamander is likely to occur within the action area.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

The Central California tiger salamander is a covered species under the SCVHP. The SCVHP authorizes over the 50-year permit term the permanent loss of 77 acres of primary habitat (i.e., aquatic breeding habitat) and 12,855 acres of secondary habitat (i.e., upland habitat) and the temporary disturbance of 14 acres of primary habitat and 1,529 acres of secondary habitat (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023 (Year 11 of the SCVHP), the SCVHP has authorized 1 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of primary habitat, 8 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of secondary habitat, 2 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of primary habitat, and 19 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of secondary habitat for the Central California tiger salamander (SCVHA 2024a, Table 6). The SCVHP requires by Year 45 (2057) the preservation of 195 acres of modeled primary habitat and 41,700 acres of modeled secondary habitat for the Central California tiger salamander in the SCVHP reserve system (ICF International 2012, p. 5-141). As of June 2023, the SCVHP has achieved approximately 24 percent of the preservation requirements for Central California tiger salamander primary habitat and 33 percent of the preservation requirements for Central California tiger salamander secondary habitat (SCVHA 2024a, Figure 8). The SCVHP requires that 30 percent of the ponds in the reserve system have documented successful breeding Central California tiger salamanders (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023, 10 out of 43 (23 percent) of the ponds in the SCVHP reserve system have documented successful breeding Central California tiger salamanders (SCVHA 2024a, Table 9).

Northwestern Pond Turtle

The action area is located within the San Joaquin Valley analysis unit (AU 14) for the northwestern pond turtle (Service 2023a).

Anderson Reservoir

Anderson Reservoir provides low quality foraging, mating, and basking habitat for the northwestern pond turtle due to the lack of basking habitat, lack of emergent and submergent vegetative cover, low abundance of prey species, and high abundance of invasive predators (e.g., bullfrogs and nonnative fish) and competitors (e.g., red-eared sliders). Since October 1, 2020, the water level in Anderson Reservoir has been in a drawn-down condition well below the height of its original design elevation due to DSOD and FERC restrictions in the FOCP. The exposed shoreline rim is rocky, steeply sloped, and sparsely vegetated in many areas, although some vegetation, including grasses, bull thistle, coyote brush, and Russian thistle, has become established in areas that have not recently been inundated. No substantial amounts of emergent vegetation are present in or around Anderson Reservoir. The bed of the dewatered Anderson Reservoir provides potentially suitable nesting habitat for the northwestern pond turtle; however, the nests could be flooded when the reservoir levels rise in the winter. Suitable overwintering

and aestivation habitat for the northwestern pond turtle is absent from the bed of the reservoir but occurs in the leaf litter layer underneath trees and shrubs near the original shoreline of Anderson Reservoir before its current drawn-down condition.

Northwestern pond turtles occurred in low numbers and/or sporadically in Anderson Reservoir before its drawn-down condition, and likely occur in even lower numbers (if at all) in the remaining pools during its current drawn-down condition. A single northwestern pond turtle was observed in Anderson Reservoir during raptor surveys in 2001 (CNDDDB occurrence number 240, CDFW 2024). One northwestern pond turtle was observed in a pond below the Anderson Dam spillway waterfall in 2013 (S. Rottenborn, HTH, personal observation cited in Corps and FERC (2024)). However, no individuals have been observed in the reservoir during numerous surveys around the dam (e.g., pre-activity surveys for geotechnical investigations performed for the proposed project) since 2013, and monthly surveys of the entire drawn-down reservoir April-July 2021 and March-July in 2022 and 2023 detected no individuals. Thus, northwestern pond turtles occur in low numbers and/or sporadically in the reservoir itself during normal reservoir levels and even lower numbers (if at all) during the current drawn-down condition.

Coyote Creek

Coyote Creek and its riparian corridor below Anderson Dam provide suitable aquatic foraging, basking, sheltering, and mating habitat for the northwestern pond turtle. However, the suitability of Coyote Creek for the northwestern pond turtle is reduced by lower water temperatures maintained in the summer to support steelhead. The lower water temperatures reduce the growth rate of the northwestern pond turtle and force it to bask more frequently in order to thermoregulate. However, the quality of basking habitat for the northwestern pond turtle is reduced along Coyote Creek due to regulated flows from Anderson Dam which have reduced the natural geomorphic flows important for scouring the riparian vegetation and opening up the riparian corridor. This has allowed willows to armor the channel and excessively shade potential basking habitat for the northwestern pond turtle. Nearby grassland habitat provides suitable nesting habitat, and woody debris and leaf litter underneath nearby shrubs and trees provide suitable overwintering and aestivation habitat for the northwestern pond turtle. However, the level of recruitment of northwestern pond turtles along Coyote Creek is likely low due to the abundance of bullfrogs that prey on hatchlings and juveniles and the abundance of mammal predators that prey on nests.

Small numbers of individuals have been observed in Coyote Creek immediately downstream from Anderson Dam, though they are far outnumbered by nonnative red-eared sliders. CNDDDB occurrences of the northwestern pond turtle within the action area along Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam include (CDFW 2024):

1. One northwestern pond turtle observed basking on a log in Coyote Creek approximately 0.3 mile downstream of Anderson Dam in 2021 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,569);
2. An unknown number of northwestern pond turtles observed in Coyote Creek north of Riverside Golf Course in 1987-1988 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,448);
3. One northwestern pond turtle observed in a pond in Coyote Creek in Coyote Creek Parkway approximately 0.6 mile northwest of Highway 101 at Bailey Avenue in May 2012 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,446);

4. An unknown number of northwestern pond turtles observed in Coyote Creek approximately 0.2 mile north of Monterey Road at Blanchard Road and 1.25 miles northwest of Highway 101 at Bailey Avenue in 1987 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,447);
5. One northwestern pond turtle observed at the Coyote Creek Percolation Ponds in October 2020 (CNDDDB occurrence number 178); and
6. One northwestern pond turtle observed in the vicinity of the Coyote-Evergreen Canal approximately 0.5 mile north-northwest of Highway 101 at Bailey Avenue and Monterey Highway at Toms Trail in April 2012 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,445).

The northwestern pond turtle has been observed at scattered locations along Coyote Creek from Anderson Dam downstream to the Coyote Percolation Dam, including the Ogier Ponds, during focused surveys conducted in 2019 (Valley Water 2019) and during monthly monitoring in spring and summer 2021, 2022, and 2023 for the FOCF. The species could also be present in the North Channel and Live Oak Restoration Reach maintenance areas. The species has been observed along Coyote Creek downstream to the upper limits of tidal influence (CDFW 2024).

Ogier Ponds

Ogier Ponds, which are former gravel pits along Coyote Creek, provide low quality aquatic foraging, mating, sheltering, and overwintering habitat for the northwestern pond turtle due to the lack of shallow water habitat, basking habitat, and emergent and submergent vegetation, low abundance of prey species, and high abundance of invasive predators (e.g., bullfrogs and nonnative fish) and competitors (e.g., red-eared sliders). The northwestern pond turtle may nest in grasslands near Ogier Ponds and overwinter or aestivate in the leaf litter layer underneath trees and shrubs near Ogier Ponds. However, the level of recruitment of northwestern pond turtles at Ogier Ponds is likely low due to the abundance of bullfrogs that prey on hatchlings and juveniles and the abundance of mammal predators that prey on nests. Two adult northwestern pond turtles were observed in Pond 2 at Ogier Ponds in February 2003 (CNDDDB occurrence number 256, CDFW 2024).

North Coyote Valley

Coyote Creek flow may influence groundwater levels in North Coyote Valley, and therefore the occurrence of northwestern pond turtles in North Coyote Valley was also considered in the action area for indirect effects. Wetlands in North Coyote Valley provide potentially suitable aquatic habitat for the northwestern pond turtle if they retain water through spring and most of the summer. The grasslands in North Coyote Valley provide suitable nesting and dispersal habitat. Northwestern pond turtles have been recorded in a number of locations associated with Coyote Creek and adjacent waterbodies on the east side of Coyote Valley (CNDDDB occurrences summarized above, CDFW 2024), and in fewer locations (associated with reservoirs and a few stock ponds) west of the valley (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 1,449, 1,454, and 1,450, CDFW 2024; HTH 2020a). However, a number of surveys conducted along Fisher Creek and in ponds in North Coyote Valley have not detected the species on the valley floor in North Coyote Valley (HTH 2000e, 2000f, 2000g, 2006a, 2006b, 2007a, 2007b, 2020a, and 2021).

Upper Penitencia Creek Steelhead Relocation Sites

The proposed steelhead relocation site in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park provides suitable aquatic habitat for the northwestern pond turtle for foraging, basking, sheltering, and mating. A single northwestern pond turtle was observed at Alum Rock Park in Upper Penitencia

Creek, 0.3 to 0.7 mile southwest of its confluence with Arroyo Aguague in 2016 (CNDDDB occurrence 1,337; CDFW 2024), and thus within and just downstream of where steelhead relocation may occur. The individual was suspected of having turtle-shell disease (CDFW 2024). There are 15 adult and four juvenile research-grade observations of northwestern pond turtles reported to iNaturalist in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park in 2015-2024 (iNaturalist 2024, <https://www.inaturalist.org>); however, some may be multiple observations of the same individuals. The observation of several juvenile northwestern pond turtles indicates that Alum Rock Park provides high quality habitat for breeding northwestern pond turtles.

The proposed steelhead relocation site in Coyote Creek near the confluence with Upper Penitencia Creek provides suitable but lower quality habitat for the northwestern pond turtle for foraging, basking, sheltering, and mating due to the site being surrounded by urbanized development within the City of San Jose. CNDDDB occurrences of the northwestern pond turtle are located (1) approximately 2.4 miles northeast (upstream) along Upper Penitencia Creek where three adults were observed in 2013 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1,385, CDFW 2024), and (2) approximately 1.4 miles east-southeast where two adults were observed in the Overfelt Percolation Ponds in 1998 (CNDDDB occurrence number 176, CDFW 2024). Two adult northwestern pond turtles were observed in Coyote Creek approximately 0.7 mile downstream of the proposed steelhead relocation site in 2017 (iNaturalist (2024), research-grade observation, <https://www.inaturalist.org>).

Likelihood of Occurrence in the Action Area

Based on the known multiple occurrences of the northwestern pond turtle within the action area and the availability of suitable, but mostly low quality, habitat within the action area, the Service believes the northwestern pond turtle is likely to occur in low numbers and forage, bask, mate, shelter, and disperse in suitable aquatic habitat throughout the action area and overwinter, aestivate, nest, and disperse in suitable upland habitat within 1,640 feet of suitable aquatic habitat within the action area.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

The northwestern pond turtle is a covered species under the SCVHP. The SCVHP authorizes over the 50-year permit term the permanent loss of 1,824 acres of primary habitat (i.e., suitable aquatic habitat plus a 150-foot buffer to include suitable upland habitat for overwintering/nesting) and 7,825 acres of secondary habitat (i.e., suitable upland dispersal habitat more than 150 feet from suitable aquatic habitat) and the temporary disturbance of 440 acres of primary habitat and 986 acres of secondary habitat (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023 (Year 11 of the SCVHP), the SCVHP has authorized 17 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of primary habitat, 9 percent of the total allowable permanent loss of secondary habitat, 20 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of primary habitat, and 23 percent of the total allowable temporary loss of secondary habitat for the northwestern pond turtle (SCVHA 2024a, Table 6). The SCVHP requires by Year 45 (2057) the preservation of 38,900 acres of modeled habitat for the northwestern pond turtle in the SCVHP reserve system (ICF International 2012, p. 5-154). As of June 2023, the SCVHP has achieved approximately 32 percent of the preservation requirements for northwestern pond turtle primary habitat and 38 percent of the preservation requirements for northwestern pond turtle secondary habitat (SCVHA 2024a, Figure 8). The SCVHA reports as of October 2022, the SCVHP has preserved 6,039 acres of suitable habitat for the northwestern pond turtle of which 1,526 acres is primary habitat (G. Haas, SCVHA, in litt. 2022). The SCVHP requires that 25 percent of the ponds in the reserve system have documented successful breeding northwestern pond turtles (i.e., occupied by juveniles and adults) (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023, nine out of 45 (20 percent) of

the ponds in the SCVHP reserve system have documented successful breeding northwestern pond turtles (SCVHA 2024a, Table 9).

Tiburon Paintbrush

Potentially suitable habitat for Tiburon paintbrush is present within the Seismic Retrofit Project component area but not within other portions of the proposed project footprint. Focused surveys conducted for Tiburon paintbrush and other special-status plant species at Anderson Dam for the Dam Maintenance Program in 2006/2008 (Valley Water 2012a) and for the Seismic Retrofit component area in 2013-2014 (Valley Water 2014c) did not detect the species. Follow-up surveys conducted in 2017 and 2018 of additional project areas added later, and surveys conducted to update special-status plant information in 2021 (Valley Water 2021b) and 2023, also did not detect the species within the Seismic Retrofit Project area. Thus, Tiburon paintbrush is absent from the proposed project footprint.

However, two populations of the Tiburon paintbrush (i.e., Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill) are present along Coyote Ridge within the action area for indirect effects due to atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 7 and 9, CDFW 2024). Atmospheric nitrogen deposition, primarily from vehicle exhaust, threatens rare serpentine endemic plants like the Tiburon paintbrush by facilitating the spread of invasive plant species into serpentine soils that are naturally nitrogen-limited. The two Tiburon paintbrush populations receive high levels of atmospheric nitrogen deposition due to their location downwind of urbanized San Jose (Service 2021a). The Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill populations of the Tiburon paintbrush are located on southern Coyote Ridge, west of Anderson Reservoir (CDFW 2024). The two populations are approximately 0.95 mile apart. The Paintbrush Canyon occurrence is located approximately 1.2 miles northeast (downwind), and the Paintbrush Hill occurrence is located approximately 1.8 mile east (downwind) of the Ogier Ponds CM (CDFW 2024). The nearest known locations of Tiburon paintbrush to the proposed project footprint are nearly 0.5 mile southwest of the nearest proposed project stockpiling activity in the bed of Anderson Reservoir, 1.4 miles northwest of the nearest proposed project construction area at the dam, and 1.2 miles northeast of the Ogier Ponds CM (CDFW 2024). A third population of Tiburon paintbrush was discovered in Santa Clara County in May 2024 along Coyote Ridge at SCVHA's proposed Richmond Ranch Preserve north of Metcalf Road (M. Fogarty, SCVHA, litt. 2024); however, this population is outside of the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition as it occurs more than 4.5 miles north-northwest (upwind) of the Ogier Ponds CM and more than 7.5 miles northwest (upwind) of Anderson Dam.

Permittee-responsible mitigation for the Bay checkerspot butterfly associated with the Kirby Canyon Landfill Development Project, reinitiated in 2013, has resulted in the current protection of the two Santa Clara County Tiburon paintbrush occurrences at Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill (Service 2021a). The biological opinion includes as a conservation measure the continued leasing and management of a 250-acre Bay checkerspot butterfly preserve (Kirby Canyon Butterfly Trust) until the landfill has been closed and revegetated with appropriate native vegetation, after which a conservation easement shall be placed on the restored landfill area (Service 2014, p. 7; Kirby Canyon Conservation Plan Trustees and Technical Advisory Committee in litt. 2023). The Kirby Canyon Butterfly Trust was sold to Valley Water with the stipulation that it is still being used as mitigation for the landfill (Service in litt. 2020). The Kirby Canyon Butterfly Trust includes the Paintbrush Hill occurrence, owned and managed by Valley Water, while Paintbrush Canyon is on land adjacent to the Kirby Canyon landfill and owned as

mitigation by Waste Management, Inc. The butterfly preserve is grazed by cattle for the benefit of the Bay checkerspot butterfly. While cattle grazing may have some benefit for the Tiburon paintbrush by reducing the cover of invasive grasses, cattle grazing may also threaten the Tiburon paintbrush by herbivory or trampling by cattle (Valley Water 2024a).

The Paintbrush Canyon occurrence had approximately 1,000 Tiburon paintbrush plants in 2013 and $1,900 \pm 375$ plants in 2018 (CNDDDB occurrence number 9, CDFW 2024; Niederer et al. 2018, p. 13). The steeper slopes of Paintbrush Canyon mostly protect this occurrence from the most devastating effects of cattle grazing and wild pig rooting.

The Paintbrush Hill occurrence, located on property owned and managed by Valley Water, is mapped as three separate polygons in the CNDDDB (CNDDDB occurrence number 7, CDFW 2024), and from 1997 through 2018 the species was only observed within the largest polygon; the last observations in the two smaller polygons were in 1994 and 1997, respectively. However, in 2019, 19 plants were observed in a location 250 feet south of the northern polygon. There were approximately 100 Tiburon paintbrush plants at Paintbrush Hill in 2013, 224 in 2018 (Creekside Science 2018a, p. 1), 222 in 2019 (including 46 seedlings; Valley Water 2020a, p. 3), 139 in 2020 (including five seedlings; Valley Water 2021a, p. 3), 130 in 2021 (including four seedlings; Valley Water 2022a), 118 in 2022 (including 2 seedlings; Valley Water 2023a, p. 3), and 105 in 2023 (no seedlings; Valley Water 2024a, p. 3) (Figure 3). In 2018, because of the difficulty in discerning individual plants, plants were counted as individuals if there were at least 2 centimeters (cm) of bare soil between emerging branches. This technique minimized guessing and increased repeatability but may have led to overcounting in some cases (Creekside Science 2018a, p. 1). Counts in 2019 attempted to distinguish individuals using the best available information, including growth pattern, morphology, and distance from other plants (Valley Water 2020a, p. 2). Counts following the Creekside Science (2018a, p. 1) 2-cm rule resulted in 340 reproductive adults compared to Valley Water's (2020a, p. 3) estimate of 176, including a large individual with 46 stems that would have been counted as 12 individuals using the aforementioned rule. For this reason, Valley Water (2020a, pp. 3–4) stated that they do not consider the 2-cm rule a viable metric, and counts in 2020 only used the best available information to differentiate individuals (Valley Water 2021a, p. 2). Although the available population numbers show for the most part a relatively stable or increasing trend in this population (Figure 3), the lower counts in 2020 – 2023 highlight that this small population may need additional protection if it is to persist or increase in size (Valley Water 2024a, p. 3).

Less than 20 percent of the Tiburon paintbrush plants at Paintbrush Hill have been protected from damage from cattle grazing/trampling, deer herbivory, and wild pig rooting by being enclosed inside fencing since 2012 (Valley Water 2024a). Valley Water has been monitoring the effects of the enclosures on the Tiburon paintbrush at Paintbrush Hill since 2019 (Valley Water 2024a). Table 4 below compares the average height, number of stems per plant, number of inflorescences per plant, number of infructescences per plant, and number of capsules per infructescence for Tiburon paintbrush plants inside and outside of the enclosures. Averaging across all years, Tiburon paintbrush plants inside enclosures were significantly taller and had significantly more inflorescences per plant, more infructescences per plant, and more capsules per infructescence than outside of enclosures ($p < 0.01$) (Table 4) (Valley Water 2024a). Thus, the enclosures should increase the reproduction of Tiburon paintbrush plants inside the enclosures by protecting the reproductive stages from cattle grazing/trampling, deer herbivory, and wild pig rooting; however, the buildup of thatch and invasive plants within the enclosures could negate any benefits of the enclosures (Valley Water 2024a). The number of Tiburon paintbrush plants observed inside enclosures declined over the first three years 2019-2021, then

Figure 3. Number of Tiburon paintbrush plants at the Paintbrush Hill occurrence in 1993-2023 (CDFW 2024, Valley Water 2024a).

Table 4. Population summary statistics of Tiburon paintbrush inside and outside the enclosures at Paintbrush Hill in 2019-2023 (copied from Valley Water 2024a, Table 2).

In enclosure?	All Years			2019			2020			2021			2022			2023		
	All†	In	Out	All†	In	Out	All†	In	Out	All†	In	Out	All†	In	Out	All†	In	Out
Average height per plant (cm)	18.8	*24.5	*17.6	22.2	30.7	19.6	20.0	17.9	20.4	15.2	14.8	17.3	15.0	20.1	14.0	20.0	28.5	17.9
Average # of stems per plant	6.4	6.1	6.4	5.6	5.9	5.6	7.8	8.9	7.6	7.0	4.5	7.5	6.0	5.9	6.0	5.4	5.5	5.4
Average # of inflorescences per plant	2.5	*3.7	*2.2	2.7	4.4	2.1	2.3	0.8	2.5	1.8	2.8	1.4	2.0	2.2	1.9	3.7	7.4	2.8
Average # of infructescences per plant	1.5	*3.3	*1.1	1.3	3.7	0.6	0.6	1.5	0.5	1.8	2.6	1.6	1.4	2.2	1.2	2.8	5.9	2.1
Average # of capsules per infructescence	4.2	*5.4	*3.4	5.0	5.6	4.0	4.7	4.0	5.0	3.2	4.3	2.9	2.6	2.6	2.7	5.0	7.0	3.6

† Reproductive plants only; seedlings not included

* p-value for the difference between in/out of enclosure is significant at $p < 0.01$ (Welch’s t-test). Tests not done for individual years.

Note: Higher value for in/out of enclosure is **bold** in each set of three columns.

increased again in 2022 and 2023 (Valley Water 2024a). The proportion of the total population within enclosures has remained within a close range, between 14 percent in 2021 and 20 percent in 2023 (Valley Water 2024a).

To determine the characteristics of suitable habitat for the Tiburon paintbrush, Valley Water compared the cover of non-grass plants (forbs), rocks larger than 6 cm, grass, thatch, and bare ground at locations where Tiburon paintbrush was present versus absent (Table 5) (Valley Water 2024a). On average, the cover of forbs and large rocks (>6 cm) were higher where Tiburon

paintbrush plants were present (Table 5). Grass cover, thatch cover, and bare ground were higher where Tiburon paintbrush plants were absent (Table 5) (Valley Water 2023a). The differences were significant for all variables except grass cover ($p < 0.05$, two-sample t-test assuming unequal variance) (Valley Water 2024a).

Table 5. Average percent cover by cover type on Paintbrush Hill. Asterisks denote variables with significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between values where Tiburon paintbrush plants were or were not present in the quadrat (copied from Valley Water 2024a, Table 4).

Tiburon paintbrush present?	Average % Grass	Average % Forb *	Average % Rock (>6cm) *	Average % Thatch/litter *	Average % Bare ground *
No	15.1	15.4	21.7	19.0	29.0
Yes	14.8	23.4	33.4	13.2	15.0

With regard to enclosures, results of the 2022 assessment indicate that thatch/litter and bare ground cover were greater inside them, although the effect is significant only for bare ground ($p < 0.05$, two-sample t-tests assuming unequal variance). The cover of grass, forbs, and rock were greater outside the enclosures, but the difference was significant only for grass cover (Table 6) (Valley Water 2023a). Higher thatch cover within the enclosures may reduce some of the benefits to the Tiburon paintbrush of reduced predation and trampling within the enclosures.

Table 6. Average percent cover by cover type within and outside of protective enclosures on Paintbrush Hill. Asterisks denote variables with significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between values inside and outside enclosures (copied from Valley Water 2023a, Table 5).

In enclosure?	Average % Grass *	Average % Forb	Average % Rock (>6cm)	Average % Thatch/litter	Average % Bare ground *
Yes	11.7	14.7	20.6	19.7	33.3
No	17.0	17.1	24.2	17.7	24.2

Over the five monitoring years to date, 66 potential host plant species have been recorded within one foot of Tiburon paintbrush individuals (Valley Water 2024a). Of these, 10 species were recorded 100 times or more over all years (Valley Water 2024a). By far the most common co-occurring species was soap plant, recorded 475 times, followed by lace parsnip, recorded 246 times (Valley Water 2024a). Other frequently co-occurring species were Italian rye grass, melic grass, wild oat, foxtail chess, blue-eyed grass, and imbricate phacelia. In 2022 soft chess, recorded 168 times, overtook yarrow, recorded 164 times, as the third most commonly recorded co-occurring species (Valley Water 2023a). Other frequently co-occurring species were Italian rye grass, recorded 163 times, and melic grass, recorded 155 times (Valley Water 2023a). Although the Mediterranean annual grasses (soft chess, wild oat, foxtail chess) are increasing in cover at the site, it does not seem likely that they are prime host plants for the Tiburon paintbrush due to their short life history, small stature, and phenology that is mismatched with that of the Tiburon paintbrush (Valley Water 2024a).

Valley Water (2020a, p. 8; 2021, p. 9) noted that Tiburon paintbrush host selection on a plant that is desirable by herbivores (e.g., soap plant) may be detrimental to the species. Rooting disturbance that was consistent with gophers rather than wild pigs (based on observations inside and outside enclosures) appeared to include soap plant husks, raising the possibility that herbivores foraging for host plant bulbs could harm the Tiburon paintbrush as a byproduct.

Creekside Science has suggested that likely host plants for Tiburon paintbrush include yarrow, golden yarrow, and possibly California aster and other perennial forbs and grasses (Creekside Science 2018c). They have used three species in their host plant experiments at the Paintbrush Canyon occurrence: yarrow, purple needlegrass, and tomcat clover, which is an early senescing annual (Creekside Science 2017) but state that one of the factors associated with successful seeding efforts was high cover of golden yarrow (Creekside Science 2018b). Golden yarrow is not widespread at the Paintbrush Hill occurrence, though it is present in small numbers: it was recorded five times within one foot of a Tiburon paintbrush individual during 2019 monitoring, seven times in 2020, six times each in 2021 and 2022, and three times in 2023 (Valley Water 2024a).

Tiburon paintbrush inflorescences appear to be very brittle (Valley Water 2023a). They are easily broken and can incur damage in the period between flowering and fruiting (approximately mid-April to mid-July) that prevents plants from completing their reproductive output for the year. Over time, because the plants are perennial, this means this population may persist but not increase or may decline if reproductive success is not sufficient for replacement. In all five years of Valley Water's study, most plants, particularly those outside cage enclosures, experienced some level of damage over the course of the growing season, apparently from a combination of herbivory and animal trampling. Broken or missing inflorescence stalks are common (see the reduction from an average of 2.2 inflorescences to only 1.1 infructescences per plant outside cages, with a smaller reduction inside cages (3.7 inflorescences to 3.3 infructescences per plant) (Table 4) (Valley Water 2024a). Thus, the enclosures are likely increasing the reproduction of Tiburon paintbrush within them by protecting the brittle inflorescences from herbivory and trampling before fruiting. A change in cattle stocking in the area in 2022 and 2023 with cattle removed in May-November likely resulted in no trampling or herbivory from cattle during the most sensitive portion of the development of Tiburon paintbrush fruits (late May-July), when inflorescence stalks become brittle and easily broken (Valley Water 2024a).

In 2019, 41 of the total 222 plants at Paintbrush Hill (18 percent) were noted as having obvious signs of herbivory at the time of flowering (flowering stalks predated) (Valley Water 2024a). Five more were marked as having most stems with multiple branches shorter than 5 cm, which may be a sign of herbivory followed by later season regrowth, and two were marked as trampled (22 percent affected in total) (Valley Water 2024a). In 2020, 30 of 139 plants (22 percent) were noted as having obvious signs of herbivory at the time of flowering (flowering stalks predated), and 26 more were marked as having most stems with multiple branches shorter than 5 cm (40 percent affected in total) (Valley Water 2024a). In 2021, after having observed the style of herbivory by cattle and rabbits, Valley Water began marking what animal was the likeliest culprit. Of the 43 plants (33 percent) where obvious signs of herbivory were noted in 2021, 19 were denoted as likely cattle (ragged/near complete herbivory), 24 likely rabbits (neat, clean nibbled stalks), 15 beetle (beetles present, only one with obvious damage to fruits), and two plants could not be determined (Valley Water 2024a). Three were marked completely trampled by cattle, and an additional 28 were marked as having most stems with multiple branches shorter than 5 cm, for a total of 74 of 130 plants affected in 2022 (57 percent) (Valley Water 2024a). Of the 32 plants noted to have some signs of herbivory in 2022 (28 percent), 11 were marked as likely rabbit, one likely cattle, 12 insect, and nine unspecified (Valley Water 2024a). In 2023, only 15 occurrences of clear herbivory were noted (14 percent), of which two were categorized as likely rabbit and four as likely cattle (Valley Water 2024a). Camera trap data in 2019-2021 confirmed the presence of cattle, deer, and pigs (Valley Water 2024a).

Wildlife cameras placed in 2019-2021 captured two clear instances of cattle eating Tiburon paintbrush (Valley Water 2024a). Cattle were the most commonly observed large herbivore. Pigs and deer were less frequent visitors but were also present all year. No clear photos of pigs or deer grazing on Tiburon paintbrush were captured. A large pig rooting event occurred in mid-February 2020 very near the Tiburon paintbrush occurrence at Paintbrush Hill and overlapping it in one location at the bottom of the hill. Fortunately, the Tiburon paintbrush plants were not destroyed since the rooting was directly adjacent to but not within the population (Valley Water 2024a). A smaller pig rooting event was captured on camera in June 2020. Pig rooting has been reported to kill plants, and thus rooting events may have a greater negative effect than regular grazing events even though they are less frequent (Valley Water 2024a). Small mammals were also observed to eat and damage Tiburon paintbrush plants; the two most relevant species are Botta's pocket gopher and brush rabbit. Damage to plants from burrowing animals which appear to be eating soaproot bulbs associated with Tiburon paintbrush plants has occurred in all years of this study (Valley Water 2024a).

Invasive plant species present in the northern polygon at Paintbrush Hill include yellow star thistle and tocalote, including directly adjacent to Tiburon paintbrush plants, and also occur scattered in moderate numbers in the grassland between the main central polygon and the road (Valley Water 2024a). Scattered invasive black mustard plants occur throughout both areas. A purple star thistle patch on the road approaching the northern polygon population was discovered and removed in 2021 and resprouts removed in 2022 and 2023 (Valley Water 2024a). A limited number of yellow star thistle, tocalote, and black mustard plants in the immediate vicinity of the Tiburon paintbrush patches have been removed during population monitoring activities as time allowed, but a concerted effort over time is recommended in order to prevent the spread and increase in density of these plants (Valley Water 2024a). Invasive soft chess, foxtail chess, and wild oat increased in frequency in proximity to Tiburon paintbrush plants since 2020 (Valley Water 2024a).

The years 2020-2023 have shown discouraging results for the Paintbrush Hill population of the Tiburon paintbrush (Figure 3) (Valley Water 2024a). The region was in a severe drought in 2021-2022, and pressure on the population from trampling and herbivory appear significant. Decreased trampling and grazing pressure from cattle in 2022 did not result in an increase in population as the severe drought continued (Valley Water 2024a). Higher precipitation during the winter of 2022/2023 also did not result in a rebound in the population in 2023 despite the reduced trampling and grazing pressure from cattle (Valley Water 2024a). The habitat quality in the central CNDDDB polygon at Paintbrush Hill has declined over the last several years, likely due to a number of factors including environmental conditions (drought, atmospheric deposition of nitrogen), compaction, erosion, grazing and trampling from cattle and game, and encroachment by non-native plant species (Valley Water 2024a).

Based on the known recent observations of Tiburon paintbrush in the Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill populations, the Service believes that the Tiburon paintbrush likely occurs within the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition at Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill. The Tiburon paintbrush is unlikely to occur at any other locations within the action area.

Atmospheric Nitrogen Deposition

Serpentine soils are harsh environments for most species of plants because they have low nutrient concentrations (e.g., low nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium), low calcium:magnesium ratios, low organic matter content, thin and rocky soils, and high concentrations of

heavy metals (e.g., nickel, iron, cobalt, and chromium) that are toxic to most plants (Weiss 1999, p. 1477; Weiss 2006, p. 22; Branco 2010, p. 5566). Serpentine-endemic plant species, like the Tiburon paintbrush, have adapted to the harsh conditions of serpentine soils, which gives them a competitive advantage over non-serpentine plant species. However, atmospheric nitrogen deposition from air pollution threatens serpentine-endemic plants because nitrogen is the primary limiting nutrient for plants on serpentine soils (Weiss 1999, p. 1476). Dry deposition of nitrogen from smog is responsible for the invasion of non-native grasses observed in the serpentine grasslands in the Santa Clara Valley south of the City of San Jose (Weiss 1999, p. 1476; Fenn et al. 2010, p. 2410; Weiss 2019b, p. 28). Nitrogen deposition is especially high near urban areas, where combustion sources (i.e., cars, trucks, industrial and home heating) produce substantial concentrations of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) (Weiss 1999, p. 1477).

The Santa Clara Valley has high rates of total nitrogen deposition with 12.7 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare per year estimated in 2012-2014 near the City of San Jose, decreasing downwind along a gradient to the southeast along the Coyote Ridge, and decreasing at higher elevations (Weiss 2019b, p. 10). Total nitrogen deposition in the Santa Clara Valley has decreased by 3-4 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare per year since 2000-2002 due to the introduction of more stringent standards for emissions of NO_x by vehicles in California (Weiss 2019b, p. 10). However, the catalytic converters installed on passenger vehicles to reduce NO_x emissions have led to an increase in ammonia (NH₃) emissions since 2000-2002 (Weiss 2019b, p. 2; Fenn et al. 2018, p. 910). NH₃ deposition in urbanized San Jose and areas downwind increased by 1-3 kilograms N per hectare per year since 2000-2002 to 5.8 kilograms nitrogen per hectare per year in 2012-2014 (Weiss 2019b, p. 10). The Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations of the Tiburon paintbrush were estimated to have been exposed to 8.8 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare per year in 2000-2002 and 5.6 to 7 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare per year in 2017-2019 (S. Weiss, Creekside Center for Earth Observation, in litt. 2021). The recently reported levels of nitrogen deposition are high enough to act as fertilizer and enhance the growth of invasive annual grasses at the expense of serpentine-endemic plant species (Weiss 1999, p. 1483). The critical load¹² for nitrogen deposition in California serpentine grasslands is estimated at 6 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare per year (S. Weiss, Creekside Center for Earth Observation, in litt. 2021). Therefore, based on the levels of nitrogen deposition reported within and near the Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill populations of the Tiburon paintbrush, the species is likely to be threatened by the invasion of exotic annual grasses driven by nitrogen deposition.

Coyote Ceanothus

Anderson Population

The proposed project is located within the Anderson population of the Coyote ceanothus, which is by far the largest of the three extant populations with over 188,000 shrubs (>98.8 percent of all Coyote ceanothus shrubs rangewide) (Service 2023d, Table 1; CNDDDB occurrence number 6, CDFW 2024). Coyote ceanothus occurs in the action area, primarily on the right (western) dam abutment and the north side of Anderson Dam, but with smaller numbers of individuals present on the southeast side of the dam as well (Figure 4). Figure 4 shows the location and number of

¹² The “critical load” for atmospheric nitrogen deposition is the amount of nitrogen pollution that leads to harmful changes in an ecosystem. For instance, excess nitrogen can act as a fertilizer, encouraging exotic grass species. Critical loads are usually expressed as kilograms per hectare per year of wet or total (wet and dry) deposition.

Figure 4. Location of Coyote ceanothus and Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants within and near the project footprint for the Seismic Retrofit (copied from Figure 25 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

Coyote ceanothus shrubs within the project footprint for the proposed Seismic Retrofit. A Valley Water botanist observed that after a fire on Pigeon Point above Anderson Dam in 2003, many thousands of individuals germinated and had established themselves (Hillman 2013). No suitable habitat for this species occurs within the action area for direct effects outside of the Seismic Retrofit Project component area.

Comprehensive surveys of suitable habitat within the project area, including all portions of the Seismic Retrofit component area, were conducted for the proposed project. All suitable habitat was surveyed in 2013-2014 (Valley Water 2014c), resulting in the detection of approximately 7,542 Coyote ceanothus individuals within the surveyed area.

Since those surveys were conducted, Valley Water has modified the project area boundary to its current extent; most notably, Valley Water intentionally reduced the extent of project activities north of the spillway, which supported the highest densities of the Coyote ceanothus detected during the surveys, to minimize impacts on this species. Approximately 853 individuals have since been lost as a result of project-related geotechnical investigations, dam maintenance activities, and FOCIP implementation (SCVHA 2024a, Table 8). A supplemental survey in 2021 identified an additional 424 seedlings and saplings, consisting of 281 south of the dam and 143 north of the dam, that had become established below the reservoir rim since 2017 (the last time the reservoir filled to capacity) due to increased availability of substrate resulting from the drawn down condition of the reservoir (Valley Water 2021b). Surveys in January 2023 were conducted to cover limited areas of the Seismic Retrofit Area, as currently proposed, that were not previously surveyed; these surveys identified 61 individuals. Therefore, a total of 2,666 individuals are present in the reduced Seismic Retrofit Area (Figure 4). The proposed project was redesigned to reduce the total number of Coyote ceanothus plants that have been (or will be) removed by all SCVHP-covered activities to 3,519 individuals at Anderson Dam which is below the 3,550 individuals estimated by the SCVHP to be directly impacted by the proposed project and the Dam Maintenance Program combined (ICF International 2012). The SCVHP does not authorize the removal of any Coyote ceanothus from any other populations (ICF International 2012).

Additional Coyote ceanothus are present, primarily north of the Seismic Retrofit Area on Coyote Ridge, in areas that could be affected by dust mobilization from the proposed project, spread of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*, and deposition of nitrogen emitted by project activities. No Coyote ceanothus are present in the CMs Project Area (i.e., in or very close to the footprints of the Ogier Ponds, North Channel Extension, Phase 2 Coyote Percolation Dam Fish Passage Enhancements, Sediment Augmentation Program, or Live Oak Restoration Reach CMs). The small Kirby population of the Coyote ceanothus (CNDDDB occurrence number 11, CDFW 2024) occurs within the action area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition as it occurs within 1.1 miles southeast (downwind) of the Ogier Ponds CM; this population receives under existing conditions the highest rates of atmospheric nitrogen deposition due to its location at a lower elevation and closer to U.S. Highway 101 and urbanized San Jose.

Plant Pathogen *Phytophthora*

The plant pathogen *Phytophthora* was first discovered to be deadly to the Coyote ceanothus when nursery-grown Coyote ceanothus seedlings infected with *Phytophthora* died at a Coyote ceanothus population introduction site at Valley Water's Coyote Ridge Preserve in 2015. Valley Water and Phytosphere Research investigated the cause of death of Coyote ceanothus shrubs on the western dam abutment of Anderson Dam in 2017 and determined that several species of the lethal plant pathogen *Phytophthora*, including *P. cactorum*, were likely introduced into the area

from a native plant restoration project carried out in 1993 that planted 30–50+ nursery-grown Coyote ceanothus plants on the western dam abutment (SCVHA 2015, p. 2; Swiecki and Bernhardt 2018, Figure 3.2.1-6, p. 38). Once *Phytophthora* infects a site, it is nearly impossible to get rid of. Figure 5 below shows the locations of where the plant pathogen *Phytophthora* has been detected within the action area near Anderson Dam through July 24, 2023.

Three main sources of *Phytophthora* contamination were identified in the action area (Figure 5): the dam abutment west of Anderson Dam, a soil stockpile on the boat landing parking lot southeast of the dam, and the 2017 high-water level along the shoreline of Anderson Reservoir (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 17). The risk associated with these contaminated areas is related to the overall area of each infested location, pre-project host density within the area, root distribution of host plants within the soil, and the *Phytophthora* species detected (Phytosphere Research 2024).

The largest *Phytophthora*-contaminated area is on the dam abutment area west of the dam near where 30–50+ nursery-grown Coyote ceanothus plants were planted in 1993. Soilborne *Phytophthora* species detected on the dam abutment slope were *P. cactorum*, *P. cambivora*, *P. crassamura*, *P. kelmanii*, *P. megasperma*, and *P. syringae*, which are all known pathogens of many terrestrial plant species and common in container nurseries that do not follow specific phytosanitary practices designed to eliminate *Phytophthora* contamination. The detections of *P. cactorum* and *P. cambivora* in 2021 sampling extended the apparent infested area across the floodplain at the toe of the slope to the north bank of Coyote Creek and the east edge of the north channel backwater (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 17).

The second largest potential source of *Phytophthora* inoculum in the action area is the soil stockpile on the boat landing parking lot. Starting in 2021, as part of the low-elevation outlet tunnel project work at Anderson Dam, approximately 22,500 cubic yards (5.57 acres) of the highly contaminated surface soil from the dam abutment and adjacent floodplain were removed, transported along a road constructed at the base of the dam and along Coyote Road, and relocated to the upper paved parking lot southeast of the dam (i.e., the boat landing parking lot) (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 19). The placement of contaminated soil in contact with native soil and lack of an effective cover were inconsistent with the BMPs in the *Phytophthora* Pathogen Management Plan that had been developed for the FOCP (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 19). The contaminated soil was left in place, and BMPs were developed to minimize the mixing of this contaminated soil with additional material excavated at depth that was likely to have little or no contamination. The contaminated soils were covered with a composite layer of non-woven filter fabric covered with at least 1-foot depth of clean subsoil as specified in the *Phytophthora* Pathogen Management Plan.

Another source of *Phytophthora* inoculum in the action area is the Anderson Reservoir shoreline infestations near the 2017 high-water level where woody vegetation has established (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 21). Coyote ceanothus near the reservoir high-water line north and south of the dam are infected with *Phytophthora* (Phytosphere Research 2024, Table 1). The source of *Phytophthora* along the reservoir shoreline is likely from runoff from landscaped areas in residential developments above Anderson Reservoir.

Another source of *Phytophthora* inoculum in the action area is infested areas near and below Coyote Road south of Anderson Dam (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 22). One of the infested areas is at the edge of a pad used for parking and equipment storage.

No *Phytophthora* were detected in the stand of Coyote ceanothus on the slope on the north side of the spillway where the largest population occurs (Phytosphere Research 2024, p. 26).

Phytophthora was also not detected in upland samples east of the dam, except for one location at a trail junction where *P. crassamura* was detected.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

All occurrences of the Coyote ceanothus rangewide are within the permit area for the SCVHP (ICF International 2012). The SCVHP authorizes the removal of up to 3,650 Coyote ceanothus shrubs only from the Anderson population (ICF International 2012), which is by far the largest of the three extant populations with over 188,000 shrubs (>98.8 percent of all Coyote ceanothus shrubs rangewide) (Service 2023d, Table 1; CDFW 2024). As of June 30, 2023, a total of 853 Coyote ceanothus shrubs have been removed from the Anderson population under the SCVHP (SCVHA 2024a, Table 8).

The SCVHP requires the protection of five occurrences of the Coyote ceanothus with creation of new occurrences allowed if no new occurrences are found; the first occurrence must be protected within five years of the first removal of any Coyote ceanothus from the Anderson population (ICF International 2012). The Llagas Road population of the Coyote ceanothus (approximately 1,000-2,000 plants) is protected under a conservation easement within the SCVHP reserve system at the Baird/Davidson Reserve (Service 2023d; SCVHA 2024a). The Kirby and Anderson populations are not currently protected (Service 2023d), but the SCVHA is the process of acquiring the vast majority of the Anderson population (SCVHA 2024b). In summer 2024, SCVHA received from the Service \$2,504,420 through a nontraditional Section 6 grant for the acquisition of 300 acres of the Anderson Lake Ranch property to protect in perpetuity the vast majority of the Anderson population of the Coyote ceanothus as a wildlife reserve under the SCVHP (SCVHA 2024b). Public access will be prohibited in the wildlife reserve to protect the Coyote ceanothus from the introduction and further spread of *Phytophthora* (SCVHA 2024b). The SCVHA has committed to completing the land acquisition before the end of 2027 as a condition of the grant (SCVHA 2024b). Once acquired, two of the three extant populations of the Coyote ceanothus (more than 90 percent of the rangewide population) would be protected in perpetuity under a SCVHP reserve.

Valley Water began the creation of a new population of the Coyote ceanothus on a 10-acre site on their property on Coyote Ridge in 2015. As of summer 2023, 1,295 planting basins had surviving Coyote ceanothus plants at the population creation site (Valley Water 2024b). Results for 2023 indicate that container plants maintained high survival rates over time (80-90 percent survival seven years after planting across all habitat types), and there was little difference in survival rates in different habitat types (Valley Water 2024b). In contrast, direct seeded plants exhibited the opposite pattern, with a much lower average survival rate (42 percent seven years after planting) (Valley Water 2024b). There was a substantial difference between habitat types over time for direct seeded plants, ranging from a low of 8 percent survival rate in Year 7 in the Lower Sage test plot, to a high of 85 percent survival rate in the Pine test plot (Valley Water 2024b). The low survival rate for direct seeded plants in the Lower Sage test plot is likely due to intense herbivory and mortality of young seedlings in the plot in the first several years after planting, and its proximity to California sagebrush, which likely provides cover for small mammals; however, as those plants in the Lower Sage test plot have matured, there is little to no additional mortality (Valley Water 2024b). Flowering of planted Coyote ceanothus in the population creation site was first documented in 2019, but with very limited fruit production that year (Valley Water 2023b). By 2023, 97 percent of Coyote ceanothus container plants flowered, and 88 percent produced fruit seven years after planting, while for direct seeded plants 84

percent flowered and 76 percent produced fruit seven years after planting (Valley Water 2024b). Natural recruitment (a total of 52 seedlings) was observed for the first time at the population creation site in 2023 (Valley Water 2024b). Seedlings were typically found under the canopy of planted Coyote ceanothus shrubs and in areas where many flowers and seed were produced (Valley Water 2024b). A pollinator study at the Coyote ceanothus population creation site identified a total of 47 insects visiting Coyote ceanothus plants, including two native bees (yellow-faced bee (*Bombus vosnesenskii*) and black-tailed bumble bee (*B. melanopygus*)) and 45 flies. Non-native European honeybees were also observed visiting Coyote ceanothus flowers at the site. Flies were the most abundant floral visitor on Coyote ceanothus shrubs at both the population creation site and the extant Llagas population at the Davidson Reserve (Valley Water 2024b).

Santa Clara Valley Dudleya

Potentially suitable habitat for Santa Clara Valley dudleya is present in the Seismic Retrofit project component area, but not within other portions of the proposed project footprint; however, the species does occur within the action area for dust and the indirect effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition. Santa Clara Valley dudleya was not recorded during focused special-status plant surveys at Anderson Dam performed within the Dam Maintenance Program area in 2006/2008 (Valley Water 2012a). However, during protocol-level plant surveys conducted in 2013-2014 within suitable habitat for this species in the project area, including all portions of the Seismic Retrofit component work area as it was envisioned at that time, approximately 144 Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants were detected on rock outcrops on and around Silica Carbonate Hill (Valley Water 2014c). The plants were mainly located in mixed serpentine chaparral habitat, although some were in coast live oak woodland and forest and the foothill pine-oak woodland habitats. As additional areas were added to the proposed project boundary in 2017 and 2018, these areas were also surveyed, though no new individuals were detected. Surveys conducted to update special-status plant information in 2021 did not detect any Santa Clara Valley dudleya in areas where they had not been observed in 2013-2014 (Valley Water 2021b). Since the 2013/2014 surveys, the project area has been reduced; the construction footprint for the Seismic Retrofit Area extends to the bases of outcrops occupied by the species but does not include any individuals. Furthermore, no suitable habitat for this species is present in the limited portions of the Seismic Retrofit Area that were not previously surveyed. Therefore, no individuals are currently present in the proposed project footprint for the Seismic Retrofit Area, although they are present immediately adjacent to this area (see Silica Carbonate Hill in Figure 4 above).

Additional Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants are present, primarily north of the Seismic Retrofit Area on Coyote Ridge, in areas that could be affected by deposition of nitrogen emitted by proposed project vehicles and equipment. Occurrences that are east and southeast (downwind) of the construction area for the Seismic Retrofit and Ogier Ponds CM are most at risk of atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction vehicles and equipment. Therefore, Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants along Coyote Ridge between SCVHA's Coyote Ridge Open Space Preserve and Anderson Dam are at most risk of elevated atmospheric nitrogen deposition during proposed project construction. The vast majority of the 96 occurrences of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya at the Coyote Ridge Open Space Preserve are outside of the area for indirect effects from atmospheric nitrogen deposition as they occur north (upwind) of the Seismic Retrofit and Ogier Ponds CM construction areas (SCVHA 2024a, Table 10; CDFW 2024). No Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants are present in the CMs project areas.

Santa Clara Valley Habitat Plan

Almost all of the entire range of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya is within the permit area for the SCVHP (ICF International 2012) except for several occurrences at Henry W. Coe State Park and Midpeninsula Regional Open Space Preserve (CDFW 2024). There are 59 California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB) occurrences of Santa Clara Valley dudleya rangewide (CDFW 2024, Service 2023d). The SCVHP authorizes the removal of up to 11 occurrences of Santa Clara Valley dudleya (ICF International 2012). As of June 2023, only one occurrence of Santa Clara Valley dudleya has been removed under the SCVHP (SCVHA 2024a, Table 8). As of June 2023, 109 occurrences of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya have been protected within the SCVHP reserve system including 96 occurrences at the Coyote Ridge Open Space Preserve, eight at the Calero County Park Preserve, one at the Baird/Davidson Preserve, three at the Tilton Ranch Reserve, and one at the Tulare Hill Wedge Preserve (SCVHA 2024a, Table 10). Note the CNDDDB defines an occurrence as groups of plants separated by at least 0.25 mile which results in the lumping of the 96 SCVHP occurrences of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya at the Coyote Ridge Open Space Preserve into only two CNDDDB occurrences (CNDDDB occurrence numbers 4 and 5, CDFW 2024; T. Edell, ICF, in litt. 2021; SCVHA 2017; Service 2021b).

California Ridgway's Rail

The action area is within the Central/South San Francisco Bay recovery unit (Service 2013b). No California Ridgway's rails occur within the proposed project footprint. Within the action area for the effects of flows and sedimentation in Coyote Creek, California Ridgway's rails are expected to occur in tidal marsh habitat from the vicinity of Newby Island Landfill downstream to the mouth of Coyote Slough (at its confluence with Alviso Slough). Surveys conducted from a number of locations along the edges of the Newby Island Landfill in 2018 detected a pair of California Ridgway's rails in the dead-end South Coyote Slough south of the landfill and a single individual near the confluence of that slough and Coyote Creek just west of the landfill (HTH 2018). Surveys conducted for the Invasive *Spartina* Project in 2020 detected California Ridgway's rails in developing marshes in the Island Ponds and in marshes on both sides of Coyote Creek near the confluence with Alviso Slough (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2021). Based on the availability of suitable habitat and historical occurrences of this species, California Ridgway's rails are expected to occur within the action area from the vicinity of Newby Island Landfill downstream to the lower end of the action area at the mouth of Coyote Slough, breeding and foraging in tidal salt and brackish marsh habitat. Based on the known occurrence of the California Ridgway's rail within and near the action area and the availability of suitable habitat, the Service believes the California Ridgway's rails is likely to occur within the action area in the tidal marsh of lower Coyote Creek.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The action area is within the Central/South San Francisco Bay recovery unit and within the range of the southern subspecies of salt marsh harvest mouse (Service 2013b). No salt marsh harvest mice occur within the proposed project footprint. Within the action area for the effects of flows and sedimentation in Coyote Creek, the salt marsh harvest mouse has been detected during trapping studies in a number of locations in the vicinity of the action area, from the Coyote Creek Reach 1A area near Dixon Landing Road downstream to the creek's confluence with Alviso Slough. Examples of such areas include Alviso Slough near the northwest corner of Pond A12, Triangle Marsh, New Chicago Marsh, and the Coyote Creek Bypass area. The latest trapping data for the Lower Coyote Creek Reach 1A mitigation site indicated the presence of 28 salt marsh harvest mice (WRA, Inc. 2023). The highest-quality habitat for this species within the

action area vicinity occurs in tidal salt marsh along the lower reaches of Alviso and Coyote Sloughs, and at the mouth of Artesian Slough, as well as in diked salt marsh within New Chicago Marsh and within the mitigation wetlands on the south side of Pond A18. Brackish marshes farther upstream along Coyote and Artesian Sloughs represent lower-quality habitat, and salt marsh harvest mice have a lower probability of occurrence (and if present, likely occur in lower densities) in such brackish marshes. However, as a result of this species' detection in brackish marshes in the Warm Springs area in 2006 (HTH 2007c) and recent findings by Smith (2019) and Smith et al. (2020) in the Suisun Bay, it could occur in at least small numbers in brackish marshes.

The fresher marshes in the upper reaches of Coyote Creek and in the South Coyote Slough area north of the northeastern corner of Pond A18 are not appropriate habitat for the species. For example, a 2018 trapping study involving 1,580 trap-nights along four transects on the northern, western, and southern edges of Newby Island, and along four transects in marshes along South Coyote Slough and in the Warm Springs marshes, detected no salt marsh harvest mice despite capturing 562 individuals of other small mammal species (HTH 2018).

In sum, salt marsh harvest mice are expected to be present in the action area primarily in salt marsh from the mouth of Coyote Slough upstream to the marshes along Coyote Creek between South Coyote Slough and Artesian Slough, likely decreasing in abundance in a downstream-upstream direction. Very low numbers of individuals may be present in brackish marsh farther upstream (e.g., in the Warm Springs area).

Based on the known occurrence of the salt marsh harvest mouse within and near the action area and the availability of suitable habitat, the Service believes the salt marsh harvest mouse is likely to occur within the action area in the tidal marsh of lower Coyote Creek.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The effects of SCVHP-covered activities on federally listed species are addressed in the intra-Service biological opinion for the SCVHP (Service 2013a). Therefore, the effects analysis below focuses on the effects of project activities not covered by the SCVHP.

California Red-legged Frog, Central Coast Foothill Yellow-legged Frog, and Central California Tiger Salamander

Additional Year of Dewatering Anderson Reservoir

Maintenance of Anderson Reservoir in a dewatered condition for one additional year (from late fall/early winter of Year 5 through the fall of Year 6 of proposed project construction), beyond the 3.5 years of dewatering authorized by the SCVHP, could adversely affect California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders occurring near the reservoir if they attempted to breed in the remaining pools in the dewatered reservoir and the pools dried out or were pumped dry before the tadpoles or larvae could complete their metamorphosis. California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-

legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders could also be injured or killed by construction activities using heavy equipment within the dewatered reservoir. Valley Water will minimize the potential for injury or mortality of California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders by having Service-approved biological monitors conduct pre-activity surveys and monitoring of the dewatered reservoir during Year 6 of project construction and relocating any listed amphibians, tadpoles, larvae, and eggs out of harm's way to Service- and CDFW-approved location(s).

California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders could benefit from an additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir by removing a major source for invasive bullfrog breeding in the Coyote Creek watershed. This would reduce the effects of bullfrog predation on and competition with California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders near the reservoir. Also, California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders would be able to disperse across the dewatered reservoir more easily, since the water-free reservoir would temporarily remove a barrier to their dispersal. This dispersal may allow exchange of individuals and genes between subpopulations on either side of the reservoir, which could benefit the population given that the reservoir impedes such dispersal under normal conditions.

Dryback of Groundwater-dependent Wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley

The additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir may also indirectly affect breeding habitat for California red-legged frogs and Central California tiger salamanders and non-breeding aquatic habitat for California red-legged frogs along Coyote Creek and in the approximately 1,000-acre North Coyote Valley (e.g., Laguna Seca) by lowering groundwater levels resulting in the early drying of these aquatic habitats (see yellow-dashed lines in Figure 2 above for locations that may be subject to indirect effects). If California red-legged frogs and Central California tiger salamanders attempted to breed in these aquatic habitats in North Coyote Valley and along Coyote Creek, their larvae would desiccate if the ponds dried up before they could complete metamorphosis. However, none of the wetlands in North Coyote Valley remain wet long enough under existing conditions to support breeding California red-legged frogs. Central California tiger salamanders have not been observed breeding in North Coyote Valley. Therefore, the potential to adversely affect breeding California red-legged frogs and Central California tiger salamanders and their larvae is low. Adult and juvenile California red-legged frogs and Central California tiger salamanders may desiccate or be preyed upon if they have to travel further to reach suitable aquatic habitat in North Coyote Valley.

Valley Water will implement a Service-approved riparian and wetland habitat dryback monitoring and groundwater management plan in North Coyote Valley and along Coyote Creek (HTH 2023) and will pay SCVHP mitigation fees if the proposed project results in the degradation of riparian or wetland habitats in North Coyote Valley or Coyote Creek. These SCVHP mitigation fees will go toward restoring, preserving, and managing habitat in perpetuity for the California red-legged frog and Central California tiger salamander within the SCVHP reserve system. However, monitoring of wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley in 2022 under FOCP determined that the observed dryback conditions were likely due to the extended drought in 2021-2022 instead of the effects of the drawdown of Anderson Reservoir under FOCP (HTH 2023). Therefore, the likelihood of one extra year of drawdown of Anderson Reservoir under ADSRP resulting in dryback conditions on wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley is relatively low. Valley Water will further reduce the potential for lowered groundwater levels causing the early drying of riparian and wetland habitats in North Coyote

Valley and along Coyote Creek by importing water for release into Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam. Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs are unlikely to occur in North Coyote Valley or along Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam and thus would not be affected by the early drying of riparian and wetland habitats there.

Higher Magnitude and Frequency of Flood Flows in Coyote Creek

The SCVHP covers Anderson Dam releases during dewatering for Seismic Retrofit construction up to 550 cfs, the capacity of the current dam outlet, for dewatering during the period November 1 to April 30 and up to 50 cfs for dewatering during the period May 1 to October 31. The SCVHP describes these maximum releases as being associated with draining the reservoir to dewater it for construction. However, during Seismic Retrofit construction, flood flows potentially as high as 6,000 cfs will be allowed to pass downstream instead of being retained in Anderson Reservoir. Any Anderson Dam releases above 550 cfs during dewatering would not be covered by the SCVHP. Thus, the proposed project may result in the higher magnitude and frequency of flood flows in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction than is covered by the SCVHP. Any California red-legged frogs occurring in Coyote Creek during the higher flood flows could be injured or killed or washed downstream. Although California red-legged frogs are unlikely to successfully breed in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam due to the abundance of invasive aquatic predators (e.g., bullfrogs and non-native fish), it is possible that a California red-legged frog could attempt to breed in the creek and its egg mass and tadpoles be scoured and washed downstream by flood flows resulting in the injury or death of the eggs or tadpoles.

Central California tiger salamanders are unlikely to breed in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam due to the abundance of invasive aquatic predators (e.g., bullfrogs and non-native fish). Adult and juvenile Central California tiger salamanders are also unlikely to occur near Coyote Creek during flood flows; however, if they were sheltering in any burrows along the creek when they were flooded, they could be washed downstream and injured or killed. Central California tiger salamanders could also be preyed upon if they were displaced from burrows by higher construction-period flows through the dam.

The Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog is unlikely to occur in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam and therefore would not be affected by the higher magnitude and frequency of flood flows in Coyote Creek.

Relocation of Steelhead to Upper Penitencia Creek

California red-legged frogs and Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs and their egg masses and tadpoles could be preyed upon or could be subjected to increased competition for food if steelhead are relocated from Coyote Creek to Alum Rock Park in Upper Penitencia Creek. A waterfall at Alum Rock Canyon creates a fish passage barrier which would prevent any relocated steelhead from swimming any further upstream. The relocation of steelhead could also result in the introduction of amphibian diseases (e.g., Bd, ranavirus, *Batrachochytrium salamandrivorans* (Bsal)) and invasive New Zealand mudsnails into Upper Penitencia Creek. Any new amphibian diseases or more virulent strains of existing diseases introduced to Upper Penitencia Creek could be further spread through the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed by infected bullfrogs, Sierran treefrogs, and other amphibians into breeding habitat for the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander resulting in the injury or mortality of the listed amphibians. The introduction of invasive New Zealand mudsnails into Upper Penitencia Creek would degrade aquatic habitat for the California red-legged frog and Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog.

Valley Water will reduce the potential for the introduction of amphibian diseases and invasive New Zealand mudsnails into Upper Penitencia Creek during steelhead relocation by implementing decontamination protocols including cleaning and sterilizing all equipment, bathing all relocated steelhead in tubs of water from Upper Penitencia Creek before releasing them into the creek and avoiding dumping any water from Coyote Creek into Upper Penitencia Creek. Valley Water will implement a Service-approved monitoring plan for amphibian diseases and invasive New Zealand mudsnails in Upper Penitencia Creek at the steelhead relocation site and at two control sites above the fish passage barrier: one in Upper Penitencia Creek and the other in the adjacent tributary Arroyo Aguague. Monitoring results associated with the relocation of 74 steelhead in August 2020 from Coyote Creek to Upper Penitencia Creek under the FOCF found that of 18 steelhead tested by skin swabs, none tested positive for amphibian diseases while one result was inconclusive (Valley Water 2021c, 2022c). No invasive New Zealand mudsnails were observed in Upper Penitencia Creek or Arroyo Aguague during visual surveys, kick-net sampling, and eDNA analysis after steelhead relocation under the FOCF (Valley Water 2022c).

The year after steelhead were relocated to Upper Penitencia Creek, Valley Water tested creek water in May and September 2021 for amphibian diseases at the steelhead relocation site in Upper Penitencia Creek, the two control sites above the fish passage barrier in Upper Penitencia Creek and Arroyo Aguague and compared them to creek water from several sites in Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam (Valley Water 2022c). Creek water from one of the steelhead relocation sites in Upper Penitencia Creek tested positive for Bd in September 2021 but not in May 2021 while creek water from each control site above the fish passage barrier tested positive for Bd in May 2021 but not in September 2021 (Valley Water 2022c). Creek water from the two most downstream sites in Coyote Creek tested positive for Bd in September 2021 but not in May 2021 (Valley Water 2022c). Creek water from the same two most downstream sites in Coyote Creek also tested positive for ranavirus, while none of the Upper Penitencia or Arroyo Aguague sites tested positive for ranavirus (Valley Water 2022c). A bullfrog found in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed in Arroyo Aguague upstream of the fish passage barrier tested positive for Bd but not ranavirus while amphibians from the Anderson Reservoir storm drain tested negative for Bd and ranavirus (Valley Water 2022c). Based on the finding of Bd in Upper Penitencia Creek both above and below a fish passage barrier, Bd was likely already present in Upper Penitencia Creek before the steelhead relocation. However, there is the possibility for steelhead relocation from Coyote Creek to result in the introduction of ranavirus to Upper Penitencia Creek since creek water samples from Coyote Creek, but not Upper Penitencia Creek tested positive for ranavirus. Although Bd has already been detected in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed, the relocation of steelhead could result in an increase in Bd loading or the introduction of more virulent strains of Bd or other amphibian diseases to Upper Penitencia Creek that could injure or kill California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed.

A large number of Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs in the nearby Alameda Creek watershed were found dead from Bd following the extended drought years of 2012-2016 (Peek and Kupferberg 2018). Peek and Kupferberg (2018) believe that the drought resulted in bullfrogs, California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and other amphibians congregating at higher densities in the few remaining pools resulting in higher levels of Bd loading (Peek and Kupferberg 2018). Although Bd was likely already present, the higher loading of Bd resulted in the death of Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs (Peek and Kupferberg 2018). Although some mortality of Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs was observed due to Bd infection, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs persisted within the

infected areas after the outbreak (Peek and Kupferberg 2018). Field sampling two years after the outbreak found all frog species including Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were Bd positive (Peek and Kupferberg 2018). Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs were also found dead from Bd in the upper Coyote Creek watershed at Henry W. Coe State Park (U.S. Geological Survey 2019). Therefore, it is possible that if steelhead relocation resulted in an increase in Bd loading that listed amphibians could be killed even though the disease is already present in the watershed; however, it is unlikely that the local listed amphibian populations would be extirpated by Bd.

Valley Water will minimize the effects of steelhead relocation on listed amphibians in Upper Penitencia Creek by implementing a Service-approved plan for the removal of aquatic invasive predators (e.g., bullfrogs, non-native crayfish, non-native turtles, and non-native fish) from aquatic habitat for the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander on Valley Water-owned properties in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed. The aquatic invasive predators control plan will reduce predation on and competition with the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander. Bullfrog removal will also reduce a major vector for amphibian diseases that could injure or kill the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander.

Northwestern Pond Turtle

Additional Year of Dewatering Anderson Reservoir

From the end of the Year 5 construction season through the Year 6 construction season, proposed project effects on northwestern pond turtles resulting from the dewatered condition of Anderson reservoir are not covered by the SCVHP. The northwestern pond turtle uses Anderson Reservoir for foraging, mating, and overwintering but in low numbers due to the lower quality of the habitat it provides (e.g., limited basking habitat, lack of submergent and emergent vegetation cover, and the large number of invasive predators including bullfrogs and nonnative fish). Since the northwestern pond turtle is only able to physically eat in water, the northwestern pond turtle may starve if it goes too long without access to water. In response to drying conditions, northwestern pond turtles may disperse to look for other water sources or aestivate in the litter layer in uplands within 1,640 feet of aquatic habitat. Therefore, dewatering Anderson Reservoir for an additional year will result in a loss of foraging habitat and could cause the northwestern pond turtle to either starve, disperse to other water bodies, or aestivate. Dispersing northwestern pond turtles are at greater risk of predation or being struck by vehicles. Suitable aestivation habitat (e.g., leaf litter under shrubs and trees along the original shoreline of the reservoir) would be even further away from aquatic habitat in the dewatered reservoir thereby increasing the risk of northwestern pond turtles starving, being preyed upon, or being struck by vehicles as they must disperse further to find suitable aestivation habitat. The potential for injury or mortality of northwestern pond turtles during one extra year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir and construction activities occurring within the dewatered reservoir during Year 6 will be minimized by having Service-approved biological monitors conduct pre-activity surveys and relocating northwestern pond turtles out of harm's way to Service- and CDFW-approved location(s). Additionally, the dewatering of Anderson Reservoir for an additional year may also benefit the northwestern pond turtle by removing a large amount of habitat for invasive predators (e.g., bullfrogs and nonnative fish) and invasive competitors (e.g., red-eared sliders) which could result in a decrease in the abundance of invasive predators and competitors in the watershed.

Northwestern pond turtles may also nest in the exposed reservoir bed of Anderson Reservoir when it is dewatered. Therefore, dewatering for an additional year may increase opportunities for nesting within the exposed reservoir bed; however, the eggs and hatchlings in the nest would be injured or killed when the reservoir refills and floods the nest.

Dryback of Groundwater-dependent Wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley

The additional year of Anderson Reservoir dewatering could result in adverse dryback effects on groundwater-dependent aquatic, wetland, and riparian habitat along Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam and seasonal wetlands in the approximately 1,000-acre North Coyote Valley (e.g., Laguna Seca) (see dashed yellow-lines in Figure 2). In response to drying conditions, northwestern pond turtles may disperse to look for other water sources or aestivate in the litter layer in uplands within 1,640 feet of aquatic habitat. Therefore, the early drying of groundwater-dependent wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley could result in a loss of foraging habitat and could cause the northwestern pond turtle to either starve, disperse to other water bodies, or aestivate. Dispersing northwestern pond turtles are at greater risk of predation or being struck by vehicles, especially along Monterey Highway and other major roads in North Coyote Valley.

Valley Water will continue to implement the Wetland and Riparian Habitat Dryback Monitoring Plan (HTH 2023) in North Coyote Valley and along Coyote Creek and will pay SCVHP mitigation fees if the proposed project results in the degradation of riparian or wetland habitats in North Coyote Valley or Coyote Creek. These SCVHP mitigation fees will go toward restoring, preserving, and managing habitat in perpetuity for the northwestern pond turtle within the SCVHP reserve system. However, monitoring of wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley in 2022 under FOCF determined that the observed dryback conditions were likely due to the extended drought in 2021-2022 instead of the effects of the drawdown of Anderson Reservoir under FOCF (HTH 2023). Therefore, the likelihood of one extra year of drawdown of Anderson Reservoir under ADSRP resulting in dryback conditions on wetlands along Coyote Creek and in North Coyote Valley is relatively low. Valley Water will further reduce the potential for lowered groundwater levels causing the early drying of riparian and wetland habitats in North Coyote Valley and along Coyote Creek by importing water from the Coyote Discharge Line and Cross Valley Pipeline Extension for release into Coyote Creek below Anderson Dam.

Higher Magnitude and Frequency of Flood Flows in Coyote Creek

Whereas the SCVHP covers Anderson Dam releases during dewatering for Seismic Retrofit construction up to 550 cfs, the effects of higher flows on the northwestern pond turtle are not covered by the SCVHP. Construction Phase Baseline conditions for Seismic Retrofit construction allow for discharges from the dam of up to 2,500 cfs. During Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit construction, the reservoir's outlets will be left open during the wet season to minimize the amount of water that accumulates in the reservoir bed. The magnitude of flow, and frequency of flows of a certain magnitude, will depend on rainfall amounts during individual runoff events and Coyote Reservoir releases. Valley Water (2022d) predicts higher flows during construction because outlets will be left wide open, so that Anderson Reservoir is not detaining water. At their maximum, such flows could be as high as approximately 6,000 cfs, which represents the maximum capacity of all dam outlets that will be present. However, a 6,000-cfs flow during Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit construction has a very low probability of occurring, as it would represent a 200-year event (with a 0.5 percent likelihood of occurring in any given year). The higher the flow, the lower the probability and frequency of that flow

occurring in any given year, so that very high flows, greater than the 10-year or 20-year events, are unlikely during the project construction period, though possible.

Northwestern pond turtles along Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam could be displaced by winter flows that are higher during construction than the Construction Phase Baseline. Because higher wet-season flows will ramp up naturally, individuals close enough to the creek that may be affected by the rising water elevation will be able to emerge and move to higher ground in response to rising water levels. Such displaced individuals may be subject to increased predation risk and vehicular mortality if they disperse away from the creek. However, most northwestern pond turtles are likely to be overwintering (i.e., hibernating) in the leaf litter layer underneath trees and shrubs during the cooler winter weather when flood flows are likely to occur. If any northwestern pond turtles are overwintering near the creek, they could be washed downstream and injured or killed by higher flood flows. However, construction-period reservoir operations will more closely follow the natural hydrograph, with higher flows associated with rain events and lower flows during dry conditions, than normal dam operations. These flows during construction (including both drier conditions in summer and some higher-flow events in winter) are similar to the hydrological conditions under which northwestern pond turtles using creeks evolved; therefore, northwestern pond turtles should be well adapted to such conditions.

Flows that occur through Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction will result in erosion of wetland and riparian habitat along Coyote Creek downstream if flow velocity is high enough to erode sediment and scour vegetation. Such habitats provide potential cover for northwestern pond turtles, and the duff layer associated with riparian vegetation may support overwintering northwestern pond turtles. However, the long-term effects on the ecology of Coyote Creek will be beneficial. Sediment supplies to the creek have been modified and reduced due to the historical presence of the dam and the accumulation of sediment behind the dam. The constraints on sediment input to the creek, and limitations on natural erosion and sediment deposition processes downstream from the dam, have contributed to limited regeneration of species such as cottonwoods and willows that rely on bare sediment along stream channels for germination. As a result, following the potential initial loss of wetland and riparian habitat due to increased construction period wet-season flows, erosion, and sedimentation, the bed dynamism and rejuvenated sediment load from potential flows during the construction period could improve the regeneration of riparian vegetation over the long term and help sustain high-quality habitat conditions. Furthermore, high flows will increase the number of downed trees and will scour riparian vegetation that may be excessively shading the creek, thus increasing the availability of sun-lit areas for northwestern pond turtles to thermoregulate and improving the availability of high-quality basking sites.

Relocation of Steelhead to Upper Penitencia Creek

If steelhead require relocation from the CWMZ to Upper Penitencia Creek during proposed project construction, they could be relocated to areas supporting northwestern pond turtles along an approximately 0.7-mile-long reach of Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park. The physical presence and activity of biologists during fish release and subsequent monitoring may disturb individual northwestern pond turtles causing them to flee their basking sites and disrupt their ability to thermoregulate. According to research-grade observations in iNaturalist, 15 adult and four juvenile northwestern pond turtles were observed in Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park in 2015-2024 (iNaturalist 2024; <https://www.inaturalist.org>); however, some may be multiple observations of the same individuals. Therefore, it is possible that up to 19 northwestern pond turtles could flee from their basking structures during steelhead relocation activities. However, the level of disturbance would be relatively small and temporary as northwestern pond

turtles would likely return to their basking structures soon after the completion of fish relocation and monitoring activities that day.

Relocated steelhead could compete with northwestern pond turtles for food. However, as described in the Fish Rescue and Relocation Plan (Valley Water and Stillwater Sciences 2020), the number of steelhead relocated to a given area within Upper Penitencia Creek would be low enough that steelhead densities would be within the natural range of variation that has allowed populations of the northwestern pond turtle to persist so that no long-term, population-level impacts of steelhead relocation on northwestern pond turtles would occur. Relocation of fish from Coyote Creek to Upper Penitencia Creek, and any follow-up monitoring (e.g., for amphibian diseases or New Zealand mudsnails) involves some risk of introducing turtle diseases or invasive species. However, the Fish Rescue and Relocation Plan includes measures to minimize the spread of pathogens or invasive aquatic species. If any fish relocations to Upper Penitencia Creek are necessary, then Valley Water would continue to implement the Amphibian Disease and New Zealand Mud Snail Monitoring Plan (Valley Water 2020d) throughout the proposed project.

Implementation of water quality BMPs will minimize the potential for degradation of aquatic habitat for the northwestern pond turtle during fish relocation and monitoring. Additionally, Valley Water will remove invasive predators and competitors of the northwestern pond turtle from Valley Water-owned properties in the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed which will reduce the risk of predation on hatchling and juvenile northwestern pond turtles and decrease competition for basking sites and prey items.

Tiburon Paintbrush

Tiburon paintbrush is absent from the proposed project footprint. The nearest known locations are on Coyote Ridge nearly 0.5 mile southwest of the nearest proposed project stockpiling activity in the bed of Anderson Reservoir and 1.4 miles northwest of the nearest proposed project construction area at Anderson Dam. Project construction activities will have no direct effects on this species. Even dust mobilized by proposed project activities will not travel so far as to adversely affect Tiburon paintbrush occurrences. The spread or mobilization of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora* as a result of proposed project activities would not affect Tiburon paintbrush due to the distance between the project area and the species' occurrences, and the higher-elevation locations of Tiburon paintbrush occurrences (so that *Phytophthora*-contaminated materials cannot be carried by runoff or gravity to those occurrences).

Nitrogen emitted by exhaust pipes from proposed project construction vehicles and equipment may affect the Tiburon paintbrush by fertilizing the soils and allowing nonnative grasses and forbs that would not otherwise be able to colonize (at least robustly) those serpentine soils to become established. The invasive plants could displace the Tiburon paintbrush and limit its recruitment. Nitrogen emitted from the Seismic Retrofit component area may therefore affect any Tiburon paintbrush plants growing in areas where nitrogen emitted by construction activities is deposited. However, known occurrences of this species are located to the north and northwest of the Seismic Retrofit area, and prevailing winds during the construction season are primarily from the west and northwest (WeatherSpark 2023). Therefore, the amount of construction-related nitrogen deposition from the Seismic Retrofit project on occurrences and habitat of the Tiburon paintbrush will be low.

Tiburon paintbrush is absent from areas directly affected by the proposed CMs, and therefore no direct impacts of CMs on Tiburon paintbrush will occur. However, implementation of CMs (e.g., Ogier Ponds restoration) could affect the Tiburon paintbrush by contributing to the cumulative effects of nitrogen deposition on serpentine habitats supporting this species. In particular, activities associated with the Ogier Ponds CM will involve considerable earth moving. The Ogier Ponds are located immediately west of Coyote Ridge, which supports populations of Tiburon paintbrush at Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill within the action area. Nitrogen emitted from earth-moving equipment and vehicles associated with work at the Ogier Ponds could be deposited on occurrences of, and suitable habitat for, the Tiburon paintbrush by the westerly winds that prevail during the majority of the construction season. Thus, invasive plant species facilitated by the nitrogen deposition could displace the Tiburon paintbrush and limit its recruitment in the Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill populations. Lesser amounts of nitrogen emitted during activities associated with the Coyote Percolation Dam CM and North Channel Extension will also be carried to Coyote Ridge.

Tiburon paintbrush is a SCVHP-covered species. However, because the SCVHP provides coverage for adverse effects to Tiburon paintbrush only for effects resulting from management of SCVHP preserves, and neither of the two populations on Coyote Ridge that could be affected by proposed project-related nitrogen emissions are located in SCVHP preserves, any effects of the proposed project on this species will not be covered by the SCVHP. Also, SCVHP mitigation fees paid by Valley Water for proposed project effects will not necessarily benefit the Paintbrush Canyon and Paintbrush Hill populations unless either population is eventually incorporated into the SCVHP reserve system. However, some SCVHP mitigation fees will go toward the preservation, restoration, and management of the newly discovered population of the Tiburon paintbrush at SCVHA's proposed Richmond Ranch Preserve on Coyote Ridge north of Metcalf Road.

Valley Water will reduce the effects from proposed project-related atmospheric nitrogen deposition on the Tiburon paintbrush by performing invasive plant management in and around the Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations of the species. During each year of construction for the Ogier Ponds CM, as well as the year following completion of that CM, Valley Water will perform manual weeding of plants considered to be of moderate or high invasiveness by the California Invasive Plant Council (2024) on the Paintbrush Hill population and perform manual weeding or fund weeding at the Paintbrush Canyon population. Such weeding will be performed at least twice during each growing season in which invasive plant management occurs. Weeding may be performed by hand or using hand-held motorized tools (e.g., line trimmers) as long as no impacts to individual Tiburon paintbrush plants would occur. Special care will be taken to avoid trampling individual Tiburon paintbrush plants, which are quite fragile.

Coyote Ceanothus

The effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction activities on the Coyote ceanothus is covered under the SCVHP. Maintenance of Anderson Reservoir in a dewatered condition for one additional year, beyond the 3.5 years of dewatering authorized by the SCVHP, during proposed project construction is the only non-SCVHP-covered activity with any potential to affect the Coyote ceanothus. This additional year of dewatering will occur from late fall/early winter of Year 5 through the fall of Year 6 of proposed project construction. Activities that will occur within the dewatered reservoir bed during this construction period are hauling of core material from the Packwood Gravel Borrow Pit and from Stockpile Area K,

hauling of transition material from Stockpile Area K, possible hauling of minor amounts of material to the Reservoir Disposal Area, and restoration of all reservoir access roads/haul roads by the end of Year 6.

These activities will mobilize dust that could adversely affect the health of Coyote ceanothus plants. The haul road along the edge of the southern arm of the reservoir will pass near some mature Coyote ceanothus growing on the edge of the reservoir northeast of the existing boat ramp. However, the haul road that will traverse the edge of the northern arm of the dewatered reservoir, adjacent to the high-density Coyote ceanothus occurrence on Pigeon Point, in Years 1-5 will not be used after Year 5. Therefore, few Coyote ceanothus will be located close to Year 6 haul routes. It is possible that some additional Coyote ceanothus seedlings could be established along the reservoir rim during the additional year of dewatering, and such seedlings would then be lost when the reservoir is refilled after completion of construction.

Implementation of Valley Water BMP AQ-1 (Table 2) will reduce the potential for construction activities to mobilize dust onto Coyote ceanothus outside the proposed project area, thus reducing the effects of dust and the potential for the plant pathogen *Phytophthora* to be mobilized to Coyote ceanothus plants within that dust. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs BI-8 and WQ-9 (Table 2) will minimize competition between invasive plants and Coyote ceanothus by requiring local plant species in revegetation. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs HM-7, HM-8, HM-9, HM-10, WQ-15, and WQ-16 (Table 2) will minimize the potential for hazardous materials and other pollutants to affect the Coyote ceanothus, and HM-12 will reduce the potential for fire to affect this species. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs BI-3, WQ-4, WQ-5, and WQ-11 will involve removing temporary fill, establishing appropriate staging and stockpiling areas and construction access areas, and keeping the work site clean, minimizing effects to the Coyote ceanothus and avoiding the spread of *Phytophthora* and weeds. Implementation of Valley Water BMP BI-4 will minimize effects of pesticides on non-target species such as Coyote ceanothus.

Implementation of SCVHP Conditions 4 and 5 will reduce the potential for and magnitude of effects on the Coyote ceanothus through numerous AMMs, including limiting the footprint of activities, reducing the potential for pollutants to impact plants, avoiding the encouragement of invasive plants, and avoiding erosion and sediment effects on the Coyote ceanothus. SCVHP Condition 7 will entail minimizing ground disturbance and vegetation removal, stabilizing soil to avoid erosion and sedimentation, and revegetating with native plants or other appropriate plants. SCVHP Conditions 13, 19, and 20 specifically address serpentine-associated plants (including Coyote ceanothus) by requiring surveys to determine where such plants occur, avoidance and minimization of covered species where feasible, and plant salvage when impacts are unavoidable (at the discretion of the SCVHA).

Maintenance of Anderson Dam facilities will occur as part of the Dam Maintenance Program and will employ the BMPs and mitigation measures implemented by the Dam Maintenance Program (Table 2) to avoid and minimize impacts on sensitive biological resources such as the Coyote ceanothus. Dam Maintenance Program Mitigation Measure Vegetation-1 requires periodic botanical surveys, which will identify the locations of Coyote ceanothus, thus facilitating their avoidance when maintenance activities are performed (although it is unlikely that new plant occurrences will occur within the Seismic Retrofit's impact areas). Dam Maintenance Program BMPs BI-10 and BI-11 include measures to minimize effects to vegetation whenever clearing or trimming is necessary and minimize effects to roots. BMP BI-12 entails avoidance of Coyote ceanothus and sensitive natural communities such as serpentine communities that support this

species in and adjacent to the Seismic Retrofit area. BMP BI-13 requires use of local ecotypes of native plants and appropriate erosion control seed mixes to avoid impacts from invasive plant species.

The potential for *Phytophthora* to be spread by Seismic Retrofit construction activities will be reduced via implementation of a project-specific *Phytophthora* Pathogen Management and Monitoring Plan prepared for the proposed project prior to the start of work and approved by Valley Water and the Service. This Plan will be based on those developed for the FOCIP (Valley Water 2020e, 2021d) and the results of FOCIP implementation and *Phytophthora* monitoring, including lessons learned from the FOCIP project implementation.

Coyote ceanothus is a SCVHP-covered species. Thus, general and serpentine impact mitigation fees paid by Valley Water for proposed project effects will be used by the SCVHA to offset adverse effects to this species (with one caveat discussed below), through the preservation, restoration, and management of populations of, and suitable habitat for, the Coyote ceanothus.

In addition to payment of SCVHP mitigation fees for preservation, restoration, and management of the Coyote ceanothus, Valley Water is complying with SCVHP conditions related to proposed project effects on this species through two additional measures. In compliance with a SCVHP requirement for Valley Water to protect or create a new population of this species within five years of proposed project effects, an occurrence of the Coyote ceanothus on the Baird and Davidson properties (i.e., Llagas Road population), on the west side of Coyote Valley, was recently acquired and protected by SCVHA. The SCVHP also states that within the 50-year permit term, five populations of Coyote ceanothus must be created or protected. To meet the SCVHP's long-term requirements, Valley Water has begun establishing a new population of the Coyote ceanothus on property it owns on Coyote Ridge, north of Anderson Dam. Planting of seedlings and direct seeding in the test plots on Coyote Ridge has been occurring annually since 2015, and these plants are being monitored to determine the success of the site to support a new, functional population of the Coyote ceanothus (Valley Water 2023b). Based on the results of this initial planting, Valley Water has prepared an occurrence creation plan that summarizes all the research and field efforts (Valley Water 2018), and this plan is being used to guide a subsequent full-scale planting effort currently underway, with the goal of establishing a viable Coyote ceanothus population on Valley Water's Coyote Ridge property. Plants are being grown via seed collected from the Anderson Dam population in a nursery and planted in accordance with the occurrence creation plan, as modified based on lessons learned from the initial planting effort. Success criteria include whether the population is reproducing and self-sustaining (based on reproduction and survival rates) over time, with minimal active site management. Specific management activities for the long-term health of the population will be described in a subsequent long-term management plan.

Implementation of BMPs and compliance with SCVHP conditions and AMMs (including payment of SCVHP mitigation fees and establishment of a new Coyote ceanothus population) will reduce adverse effects on the SCVHP-covered Coyote ceanothus. The number of individual Coyote ceanothus shrubs that could be affected by the one non-SCVHP-covered proposed project activity – maintaining the reservoir in a dewatered condition for one additional year – would be very low, if any.

Santa Clara Valley Dudleya

The effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction activities on the Santa Clara Valley dudleya is covered under the SCVHP. As described above for the Coyote ceanothus, the only non-SCVHP-covered proposed project activity with any potential to affect Santa Clara Valley dudleya is maintenance of Anderson Reservoir in a dewatered condition for one additional year, beyond the 3.5 years of dewatering authorized by the SCVHP. During activities in the dewatered bed of the reservoir from late fall/early winter of Year 5 through the fall of Year 6, dust mobilization could adversely affect the health of Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants. However, the potential for, and magnitude of, any such adverse effects is low. Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants are not known or expected to occur along the southern arm of the reservoir, which lacks the high-quality rock outcrops present at Silica Carbonate Hill. The haul road along the edge of the northern arm of the dewatered reservoir, close to the Santa Clara Valley dudleya occurrences on Silica Carbonate Hill, will not be used after Year 5. Therefore, no Santa Clara Valley dudleya will occur close to Year 6 haul routes.

Implementation of Valley Water BMP AQ-1 (Table 2) will reduce the potential for construction activities to mobilize dust onto Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants outside the project area, thus reducing the effects of dust and the potential for the plant pathogen *Phytophthora* to be mobilized to Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants within that dust. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs BI-8 and WQ-9 (Table 2) will avoid competition between invasive plants and Santa Clara Valley dudleya by requiring local plant species in revegetation. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs HM-7, HM-8, HM-9, HM-10, WQ-15, and WQ-16 (Table 2) will minimize the potential for hazardous materials and other pollutants to affect the Santa Clara Valley dudleya, and HM-12 will reduce the potential for fire to affect such plants. Implementation of Valley Water BMPs BI-3, WQ-4, WQ-5, and WQ-11 (Table 2) will involve removing temporary fill, establishing appropriate staging and stockpiling areas and construction access areas, and keeping the work site clean, minimizing effects on the Santa Clara Valley dudleya and avoiding the spread of *Phytophthora* and weeds. Implementation of Valley Water BMP BI-4 (Table 2) will minimize effects of pesticides on non-target species such as the Santa Clara Valley dudleya.

Implementation of SCVHP Conditions 4 and 5 will reduce the potential for and magnitude of effects on the Santa Clara Valley dudleya through numerous AMMs, including limiting the footprint of activities, reducing the potential for pollutants to affect plants, avoiding the encouragement of invasive plants, and avoiding erosion and sediment effects on the Santa Clara Valley dudleya. SCVHP Condition 7 will entail minimizing ground disturbance and vegetation removal, stabilizing soil to avoid erosion and sedimentation, and revegetating with native plants or other appropriate plants. SCVHP Conditions 13, 19, and 20 specifically address serpentine-associated plants (including the Santa Clara Valley dudleya) by requiring surveys to determine where such plants occur, avoidance and minimization of covered species where feasible, and plant salvage when effects are unavoidable (at the discretion of the SCVHA).

Maintenance of Anderson Dam facilities will occur as part of the Dam Maintenance Program and will employ the BMPs (Table 2) and mitigation measures implemented by the Dam Maintenance Program to avoid and minimize effects on sensitive biological resources such as the Santa Clara Valley dudleya. Dam Maintenance Program Mitigation Measure Vegetation-1 requires periodic botanical surveys, which will identify the locations of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya, thus facilitating their avoidance when maintenance activities are performed (although it is unlikely that new plant occurrences will occur within the Seismic Retrofit's impact areas). Dam Maintenance Program BMPs BI-10 and BI-11 (Table 2) include measures to minimize effects to

vegetation whenever clearing or trimming is necessary and minimize effects to roots. BMP BI-12 (Table 2) entails avoidance of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya and sensitive natural communities such as serpentine communities that support this species in and adjacent to the Seismic Retrofit area. BMP BI-13 (Table 2) requires use of local ecotypes of native plants and appropriate erosion control seed mixes to avoid effects from invasive plant species.

The potential for *Phytophthora* to be spread by Seismic Retrofit construction activities will be reduced via implementation of a project-specific *Phytophthora* Pathogen Management and Monitoring Plan prepared for the proposed project prior to the start of work and approved by Valley Water. This Plan will be based on those developed for the FOCIP (Valley Water 2020e, 2021d) and the results of FOCIP implementation and *Phytophthora* monitoring, including lessons learned from the FOCIP project implementation.

Santa Clara Valley dudleya is a SCVHP-covered species. General and serpentine impact fees paid by Valley Water for proposed project effects will be used by the SCVHA to offset adverse effects to this species through the preservation, restoration, and management of populations of, and suitable habitat for, this species.

Implementation of BMPs and compliance with SCVHP conditions and AMMs (including payment of mitigation fees) will reduce adverse effects on the SCVHP-covered Santa Clara Valley dudleya. It is unlikely that any additional Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants (beyond those affected by SCVHP-covered activities) could be affected by the one non-SCVHP-covered proposed project activity (maintaining the reservoir in a dewatered condition for one additional year).

California Ridgway's Rail and Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Effects of Potentially Increasing Flows during Construction

None of the proposed project's effects on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse are covered by the SCVHP. The proposed project will have no direct effects on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, as these species occur in the action area only in tidal marshes along Coyote Slough more than 30 miles from proposed project construction activities, but indirect effects to these listed species may occur. California Ridgway's rails are expected to occur within the action area from the vicinity of Newby Island Landfill downstream to the lower end of the action area at the mouth of Coyote Slough, breeding and foraging in tidal salt marsh and brackish marsh habitat. Salt marsh harvest mice occur in tidal and nontidal brackish and salt marshes from the Coyote Creek Reach 1A area near Dixon Landing Road downstream to the creek's confluence with Alviso Slough. Even activities that could reduce water quality in Coyote Creek, such as spills of fuel or chemicals during construction, are unlikely to have a substantive effect on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse given the dilution that would occur between construction areas and tidal marshes. However, during Seismic Retrofit construction, the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse could be adversely affected by increased frequency and magnitude of flows, effects of such increased flows on the salinity of tidal marshes and tidal marsh vegetation, and deposition of sediment mobilized from the reservoir. Construction phase baseline conditions for Seismic Retrofit construction allow for discharges from Anderson Dam of up to 2,500 cfs. During Seismic Retrofit construction, the reservoir's outlets will be left open during the wet season to minimize the amount of water that accumulates in the reservoir bed. The magnitude of flow, and frequency of flows of a certain magnitude, will depend on rainfall amounts during individual runoff events and Coyote Reservoir releases. At their maximum, such flows could be

as high as 6,000 cfs, which represents the maximum capacity of all dam outlets that will be present. However, a 6,000-cfs flow during Seismic Retrofit construction has a very low probability of occurring, as it would represent a 200-year event (with a 0.5 percent likelihood of occurring in any given year). The higher the flow, the lower the probability and frequency of that flow occurring in any given year, so that very high flows, greater than the 10-year or 20-year events, are unlikely during the project construction period, though possible.

Flows in tidal portions of Coyote Slough during proposed project construction may be higher than baseline levels, in which flows associated with storm events are currently managed by Anderson Dam. The California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse may have to move to higher ground or seek refuge in dense vegetation during flood events, particularly if they coincide with lunar high tides (e.g., king tides). California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice are particularly susceptible to predation during such events as they are forced to move into more exposed areas and to upland edges. Therefore, there is some potential for predation on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice to increase as a result of very high flows released from Anderson Reservoir during proposed project construction. However, flows high enough to cause California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice to be exposed to increased predation risk occur infrequently (with the magnitude of the flows inversely proportional to frequency of occurrence), so the likelihood and magnitude of any adverse effect of high flows on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice during the 7-year proposed project construction period are low.

Valley Water (2022e) modeled potential effects of construction-period flows on tidal habitats along lower Coyote Creek and Coyote Slough. This modeling assumed that higher flows through Anderson Dam, taken from the memo used to compare construction-period flows through the dam with Pre-FERC Order Baseline flows (Valley Water 2022d), would be coupled with tide height equaling mean higher-high water (MHHW) to represent the conditions that would occur if higher flows down Coyote Creek coincided with high tides.

In addition to input of water flowing through Anderson Dam, there are 125 square miles of watershed downstream from Anderson Dam that would contribute water to Coyote Creek that eventually reaches tidal habitats (Valley Water 2022e). Storms that result in higher flows through Anderson Dam are likely to cause additional runoff entering Coyote Creek from the rest of the watershed. For example, during a late December 2022 storm, Anderson Dam was releasing water at a rate of 500 cfs, but Coyote Creek flows at Highway 237 (just upstream from the uppermost tidal areas) were above 2,000 cfs (Valley Water, unpublished data). Thus, Anderson Dam contributes only a portion of the water that reaches tidal areas of Coyote Creek; the exact proportion provided by flows through Anderson Dam varies according to variability in rainfall and runoff among locations within the Coyote Creek watershed. For the purposes of the modeling performed for this impact analysis, Valley Water (2022e) did not consider flows from other parts of the Coyote Creek watershed, as those additional flows are not the result of the proposed project, and thus Valley Water's analysis only considered the effects of flow through Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction on tidal habitats (Valley Water 2022e).

Analyzing flows at 5, 10, 20 to 25, and 50-100-year return intervals, Valley Water's modeling predicted that the extent of inundated floodplain (i.e., tidal marsh), beyond post-FOCP baseline conditions, would increase by approximately 68 acres (during the 5-year event) to 155 acres (during the 50 to 100-year event). Predicted acreage of additional inundation was 86 acres during the 10-year event and 121 acres during the 20 to 25-year event. These scenarios represented an increase in inundation ranging from 4.3 to 9.7 percent of the entire tidal floodplain in the action

area. Water surface elevation (i.e., depth) was predicted to increase more in the uppermost limits of tidal action, from Highway 237 downstream to the confluence of Lower Penitencia Creek with Coyote Creek. Downstream from Lower Penitencia Creek (i.e., in the areas where California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice could potentially occur), water surface elevation was predicted to increase by approximately 0.15 to 0.75 feet (during the 5-year flow) to 0.4 to 2.0 feet (during the 50 to 100-year flow), with intermediate increases during the 10 and 20 to 25-year flows. Figure 6 below depicts areas predicted to be inundated from a 5-year flow passed through Anderson Dam, added to MHHW, and Figure 7 below depicts areas predicted to be inundated from a 50 to 100-year flow passed through Anderson Dam, added to MHHW.

Figure 6. Modeled inundation change in tidal areas from the construction baseline conditions (maximum Anderson Dam outflow of 2,500 cfs) to 3,500 cfs, representing a 5-year event passed through Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction (copied from Figure 29 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

As indicated in Figures 6 and 7, most of the areas affected by higher flows through Anderson Dam outlets are subtidal and intertidal habitats that are not currently vegetated. Most of the tidal marsh that would be inundated by such flows is located in the upper tidal reaches, such as in the Warm Springs Marshes, South Coyote Slough, and the Reach 1A Bypass area (all around the Newby Island Landfill). Less inundation of tidal marsh would occur farther downstream. Similarly, compared to areas inundated during a recent (January 2022) king tide, the additional areas that would be inundated by a 50 to 100-year event are concentrated in the upper tidal reaches (see blue areas in Figure 8 below). These marshes that would be inundated by flows from Anderson Dam during storm events support California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice. In addition, 50 to 100-year flows would inundate some high-marsh and ecotone habitat farther downstream, around the edges of the Island Ponds and along the railroad tracks, that would not be inundated during the king tide analyzed in Figure 8. Thus, 50 to 100-year flows would inundate some habitat used by California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest

mice to escape rising water levels. Twenty to 25-year flows would not inundate most of the high marsh and ecotone habitat in these tidal areas.

Figure 7. Modeled inundation change in tidal areas from the construction baseline conditions (maximum Anderson Dam outflow of 2,500 cfs) to 5,000 cfs, representing a 50 to 100-year event passed through Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction (copied from Figure 30 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

Thus, although Seismic Retrofit-related increases in magnitude of flows, and frequency of higher flows, could affect California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice present along Coyote Slough, such effects would be greater with larger flows, as more of the tidal marsh would be inundated, yet the probability of such flows decreases with increasing rate of flow. Flows high enough to cause California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice to be exposed to increased predation risk occur infrequently (with the magnitude of the flows inversely proportional to frequency of occurrence), so the likelihood and magnitude of any adverse effect of high flows on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice during the 7-year Seismic Retrofit construction period is not high. Nevertheless, the probability that a 20-year flow event will occur within the 7-year construction period is 30 percent.

California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice have evolved with exposure to high water levels from high fluvial flows and tidal flooding. As water levels ramp up, California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice would move to higher ground and refugia in vegetation to avoid predation. Some predation could still occur, though (e.g., Figure 7 shows inundation of some ecotonal, high-tide refugial habitat), and the short-term (construction-period) effects of higher flows could lead to increased predation and loss of individual California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice. California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse numbers are lower in the upper tidal reaches that would be affected most by higher flows during Seismic Retrofit construction than in lower reaches that would be affected least. Due to the possibility that higher

Figure 8. Modeled inundation of tidal areas from a January 2022 king tide (red) versus the additional inundation from a 50 to 100-year flow event (5,000 cfs) passed through Anderson Dam during Seismic Retrofit construction (blue) (copied from Figure 31 in Corps and FERC (2024)).

flows during proposed project construction (i.e., flows exceeding the environmental baseline, post-FOCP maximum rate of 2,500 cfs) could result in increased extent, duration, or depth of inundation of tidal marsh habitat, increasing the potential for predation on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice, Valley Water will contribute to avian and mammalian predator management activities, and high tide refugial habitat enhancement activities, in the South Bay. This measure will reduce the risk of predation on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice within and near the action area.

The breeding period of the California Ridgway's rail is prolonged. Pair bonding and nest building are generally initiated by mid-February (Service 2013b). Nesting may begin as early as late February or early March (Evens and Page 1983) and extend through July in the South Bay (DeGroot 1927, Service unpubl. data). Two peaks in nesting activity occur, a greater peak between mid-April and early-May and a lesser peak between late-June and early-July (DeGroot 1927, Applegarth 1938, Gill 1972, Harvey 1988). The second nesting peak has been interpreted as attempts by late nesters (DeGroot 1927), second attempts after initial nesting failures (Gill 1972), or second broods (Wilbur and Tomlinson 1976). Because California Ridgway's rails evolved in and near tidal marsh habitats subject to inundation from storm events and king tides, they are less likely to have active nests in tidal marsh during the winter and early spring period when Seismic Retrofit-related increases in flows are most likely to occur. However, if a mid/late spring storm event were to occur and flows through Anderson Dam were substantially higher than construction phase baseline conditions, active nests of the California Ridgway's rail could be lost to inundation. However, such an event has an extremely low probability of occurring. Studies of the fate of 71 California Ridgway's rail nests in the South Bay in 1992 found 1.4

percent of nests were lost due to flooding, while a study of 18 rail nests in northern San Francisco Bay in 1998-1999 found 5.5 percent of nests were lost due to flooding (Service 2013b, Table II-3). Therefore, it is possible for California Ridgway's rail nests to be flooded even under existing conditions.

The southern subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse is generally sexually active from March through November (Fisler 1965). However, salt marsh harvest mouse nests have also been observed in December in South Bay tidal marshes at Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge at Pond A19 in December 2021 and outboard of Pond R4 in December 2023 (Alluvion Biological Consulting in litt. 2022; WRA, Inc. in litt. 2023; R. Tertes, Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge, pers. comm.). Therefore, salt marsh harvest mice nests could be flooded and lost to inundation if a storm event were to occur and flows through Anderson Dam were substantially higher than construction phase baseline conditions in March-December. The likelihood of salt marsh harvest mouse nests being flooded increases if a mid/late spring storm event were to occur and flows through Anderson Dam were substantially higher than construction phase baseline conditions.

In summary, the dam's outlets will be managed during Seismic Retrofit construction in such a way as to potentially result in increased frequency, depth, and/or duration of inundation of tidal marsh habitats far downstream from the dam. Such increased inundation would reduce the vegetative cover available to California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice, increasing predation of individuals that have to seek out more limited patches of vegetation that is not inundated. Such impacts would be infrequent and would occur only during the construction period.

Effects of Potential Changes in Salinity during Construction

The potential for increased flows during Seismic Retrofit construction to modify the salinity of water and sediment in tidal marshes, and thus the species composition of tidal marshes, was also assessed. Monitoring San Francisco Bay salinity, the U.S. Geological Survey (Schemel 1998) concluded that large storm events can result in reductions in salinity in San Francisco Bay as a result of increased input from local South Bay streams and from the Sacramento/San Joaquin River Delta. Monitoring plant communities in South Bay marshes from 1989 to 2012, HTH (2012) documented the dynamic nature of tidal marsh plant associations, with vegetation in certain areas becoming dominated by plant species associated with higher salinity in some years and changing to more brackish species associated with moderate or lower salinity in other years. They concluded that changes in dominant tidal marsh plant species among years is primarily a result of the effects of variability in freshwater runoff on plant species having differing tolerances to salinity. Following years of higher runoff, the extent of brackish-marsh plant species such as alkali bulrush expands at the expense of species associated with higher-salinity marshes such as pickleweed. Following drier years, the reverse occurs. Because the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse are typically associated with more saline marshes, changes in dominant tidal marsh plant species composition as a result of increased freshwater inputs during Seismic Retrofit construction could potentially degrade habitat quality in marshes along lower Coyote Creek by reducing the extent of salt marsh and increasing the extent of brackish marsh.

However, the proposed project will not result in a substantial effect on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse as a result of the potential for increased freshwater input during construction, for a number of reasons. The most important contribution to salinity in the South Bay, including lower Coyote Creek, comes from input from the Sacramento/San Joaquin Delta

(HTH 2012). During wet years and large storm events when flows through Anderson Dam are higher, runoff through the Sacramento/San Joaquin River Delta is also expected to be higher, so that the influence of freshwater inputs from Coyote Creek on South Bay salinity will always be lower than the influence from the Sacramento/San Joaquin River Delta. The amount of fresh water reaching tidal habitats along lower Coyote Creek will not differ between baseline conditions and conditions during Seismic Retrofit construction; rather, it is the magnitude of flows during storm events that could increase during construction. The total volume of fresh water passing through Anderson Dam and reaching tidal habitats along lower Coyote Creek will depend on the weather, not on dam management during construction.

The California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse is able to use a variety of tidal marsh plant associations, and while these species are most closely associated with marsh dominated by plants associated with higher-salinity marshes, they also use brackish marsh vegetation (HTH 1990a, 1990b, 2007c, Shellhammer et al. 2010, Smith 2019). As a result, changes in the distributions of dominant plants as a result of changes in runoff are unlikely to result in a substantial reduction in populations of the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Finally, any effects of increased freshwater inputs resulting from management of the dam's outlets during construction would be short-term impacts, occurring only during, and possibly immediately following, Seismic Retrofit construction. Monitoring of marsh vegetation has documented that plant associations change relatively quickly (e.g., over a year or two) in response to variability in freshwater runoff and salinity, so any minor effects of increased freshwater inputs resulting from Seismic Retrofit construction would not last for more than a year or two following completion of construction. Because the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse have evolved under conditions in which tidal marsh salinity varies among years based on climatic variability and freshwater inputs from San Francisco Bay tributaries, the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse would not be affected substantially by potential short-term changes in freshwater inputs from Coyote Creek during Seismic Retrofit construction.

Effects of Sediment Mobilization during Construction

During Seismic Retrofit construction, considerable amounts of sediment that has accumulated in the bed of Anderson Reservoir may be mobilized downstream. When this sediment is covered by reservoir water, as under normal conditions when the reservoir is filled, it is not easily eroded. However, when the reservoir has been dewatered, sediment would be more subject to erosion from rainfall runoff and from the reservoir's tributaries. Modeling of sediment mobilization under various scenarios of storm events and reservoir water levels by AECOM (2021) concluded that maximum sediment mobilization would occur if back-to-back 2-year rainfall events (i.e., events that have a 50 percent likelihood of occurring in any given year), or a single 5-year event (with a 20 percent likelihood of occurring in any given year), were to occur when little water was present in the reservoir and sediments are exposed. During those events, flows would be high enough to erode large amounts of sediment from the reservoir (approximately 167,000 tons per event) but not so high as to fully cover the sediments with water, which would reduce their erosivity. Less sediment would be mobilized during lower-magnitude, more frequent flows, that occur when the reservoir has temporarily filled to contain more water and cover more sediment, or during higher flows that quickly cover sediment in the reservoir with water.

To predict the effects of such sediment mobilization on species using tidal marsh along lower Coyote Creek and Coyote Slough, the modeling efforts also estimated sediment deposition in tidal habitats along lower Coyote Slough. Under normal conditions, average sediment loads carried by the tides in the vicinity of the Island Ponds (approximately midway between the upper

limits of tidal action along Coyote Creek and the mouth of Coyote Slough that serves as the lower end of the action area) are approximately 500 tons per tide cycle (or 1,000 tons per day) with peak daily loads of over 2,000 tons per day (over two tide cycles) (AECOM 2021). Thus, the tidal marshes, aquatic habitats, and mudflats in the action area are dynamic features, exposed to considerable sediment flux even in the absence of sediment mobilization from Anderson Reservoir. Nevertheless, sediment mobilized from the reservoir and carried to tidal habitats along lower Coyote Creek/Coyote Slough would result in some deposition in these habitats.

Within tidal habitats at the lowermost end of Coyote Creek and in Coyote Slough, maximum deposition of up to 6.46 inches of sediment in lower intertidal areas near the Warm Springs wetlands, could occur during a 2-year, double peak storm event that occurs over 4.8 days when the reservoir has been dewatered during Seismic Retrofit construction. The depth of deposition would decrease along an upstream-downstream gradient within the tidal marsh, being very low under all scenarios near the mouth of Coyote Slough. In addition, the depth of deposition would decrease with increasing elevation, so that the upper intertidal zone would experience less deposition, and deposition would be even less in the high marsh; in other words, sediment deposition in tidal areas is greatest in sloughs and channels providing aquatic, subtidal habitats, and intertidal mudflats, and least in vegetated tidal marsh. Whereas the modeling results assume deposition rates under very low-flow, inactive conditions, the flow velocities associated with events that transport large amounts of sediment downstream would be higher, and actual depths of deposition would therefore be lower because some sediment would continue to be carried downstream. Also, subsequent flows with lower sediment loads would wash some of the deposited sediment away, so that these sediment depths would not represent the magnitude of long-term increases in depth/elevation. Therefore, the depth of sediment actually deposited in vegetated marshes during a given flow event would be lower than modeled.

Sediment mobilization during Seismic Retrofit construction provides a means of moving much-needed sediment to tidal marshes. The historical urbanization and the presence of Coyote Dam and Anderson Dam have reduced the volume of sediment that would otherwise have been carried downstream in unmodified conditions. Due to sea level rise, sediment accumulation in tidal marshes is important to help vegetated marshes remain at elevations, relative to a rising sea. Delivering increased sediment to the San Francisco Bay's marshlands has been identified as a priority for long term marsh resilience in light of rising sea levels.

In addition, the South Bay Salt Ponds Restoration Project is restoring former salt ponds to tidal habitats, yet most ponds are, upon breaching, below elevations that would allow colonization and persistence of marsh vegetation. Sediment deposition is necessary to elevate these marshes to the point that they can be colonized by marsh vegetation. The effects of rising sea levels on tidal marshes are dependent upon the relative rate of sea level rise versus rates of sedimentation and accretion of the marsh surface. Unless a balance between sedimentation/accretion and erosion/subsidence is met that equals or exceeds the rate of sea level rise, there will be a net loss of tidal marsh habitat (Service 2013b). Thus, by helping to elevate tidal habitats in the lower Coyote Creek/Coyote Slough area, sediment mobilization from Anderson Reservoir would contribute to the establishment of vegetated marshes in breached salt ponds such as the Island Ponds and Pond A6 and help existing marsh to be maintained in the face of sea level rise, thus helping to maintain suitable habitat for the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. However, the extent of sediment mobilization from Anderson Reservoir that reaches tidal marshes is unknown.

Aside from inundation, sediment deposition associated with Seismic Retrofit construction may have short-term, minor adverse effects and long-term beneficial effects on the California Ridgway's rail. California Ridgway's rails forage primarily on invertebrates, though California Ridgway's rails may also take small vertebrates (Albertson and Evens 2000). California Ridgway's rails feed in higher intertidal areas (e.g., mudflats), usually close to the cover of vegetated marshes, though they forage within marsh vegetation as well. Sudden deposition of several inches of sediment could reduce foraging efficiency by covering prey, which may adversely affect the prey and reduce their availability by making it harder for California Ridgway's rails to reach them. However, because many of the California Ridgway's rail's prey species are benthic burrowers living in a dynamic environment, these invertebrates are able to adapt to sediment deposition, and no large-scale or long-term reduction in the invertebrates' populations (and therefore food availability for California Ridgway's rails) would result from sediment deposition associated with Seismic Retrofit construction. Also, the depth of sediment deposition would decrease with increasing elevation; the upper edges of mudflats (where California Ridgway's rails typically forage) and tidal sloughs higher in the marsh would experience much less sediment deposition than the maximum 6.46 inches of sediment deposition modeled. Insects, spiders, and other prey available to California Ridgway's rails in vegetated marsh, may not be affected at all by sedimentation (e.g., if those prey are on vegetation above the high waters that carry the sediment).

Although considerable deposition of sediment could occur in low intertidal habitats under certain storm event/reservoir level scenarios, salt marsh harvest mice do not use those intertidal habitats. Rather, salt marsh harvest mice occur in vegetated marshes, primarily in higher-elevation portions of marshes where sediment deposition would be much lower than the maximum 6.46 inches of sediment deposition modeled. During flood events that deposit sediment, the mice climb higher into vegetation or move into higher patches, so no salt marsh harvest mice will be covered or stuck in deposited sediment. Newly deposited sediment may cover seeds or other plant materials on the substrate surface, reducing food availability somewhat, although ample marsh vegetation will remain available to salt marsh harvest mice. However, there is no expectation that this sediment deposition will kill vegetation used by salt marsh harvest mice. Tidal marsh plants are adapted to growing in dynamic depositional environments, so the density and structure of vegetative cover and nesting habitat will not be adversely affected.

As discussed above, sediment deposition would have a long-term beneficial effect on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse by contributing to the establishment of vegetated marshes in breached ponds such as the Island Ponds and Pond A6 and helping existing marsh to be maintained in the face of sea level rise, thus helping to maintain suitable habitat for these tidal marsh species in the long term.

During Seismic Retrofit construction, Valley Water will monitor sedimentation of, and water quality within, Coyote Creek downstream from Anderson Dam following the Sediment Monitoring Plan (Horizon Water and Environment 2021). This monitoring will determine whether construction activities are resulting in substantial turbidity impacts. Otherwise, proposed project construction monitoring would not affect the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, as no construction monitoring would take place in areas where these species occur.

Effects of Potential Contaminant Mobilization during Construction

In addition to inundation and sediment deposition impacts, contaminants in Anderson Reservoir sediments could adversely affect the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Under the Clean Water Act Section 303(d), Anderson Reservoir is listed as impaired for mercury and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) (SWRCB 2018). In particular, mercury and PCBs have been found in fish caught in Anderson Reservoir.

Diazinon is an organophosphate insecticide that was developed in 1952 to replace dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT). Neither Anderson Reservoir nor any of its tributaries are identified on the Clean Water Act Section 303(d) list as impaired for diazinon (SWRCB 2017a). Diazinon was banned for residential use in 2004, and there is no agricultural source of diazinon near Anderson Reservoir. None of the five samples cited by the SWRCB exceeded regulatory thresholds for listing (SWRCB 2017a), and the Final 303(d) Listing Report includes five samples with no exceedances. In consultation with SFRWQCB staff, it was determined that no further testing is necessary, nor any diazinon-specific control measures are necessary during the implementation of the FOCP (Valley Water 2021f).

Mercury is a naturally occurring trace metal that can enter water bodies through geologic or atmospheric sources. In reservoir sediments, anaerobic bacteria can convert mercury to methylmercury and release it into the water column. Anderson Reservoir is identified on the Clean Water Act Section 303(d) list as impaired for mercury in fish (SWRCB 2017a). The source of mercury in Anderson Reservoir is unknown, but it is assumed to be naturally occurring in local geology and deposited to the watershed atmospherically. Composite samples of lake sediments collected in 2019 revealed that the reservoir has low sediment mercury concentrations consistent with natural background and industrial-era atmospheric deposition (SWRCB 2017b). Mercury concentrations in reservoir fish are elevated, likely due to biogeochemical and food web conditions that are conducive to methylmercury production and bioaccumulation (Valley Water 2021f). Valley Water's existing mercury data do not indicate that there is a reasonable potential for mercury in Anderson Reservoir sediments to exceed mercury thresholds (Valley Water 2021f).

PCBs are synthetic organic chemicals that were used for numerous industrial applications until manufacturing was banned in 1979. PCBs are carcinogenic and toxic to humans and wildlife with repeated exposure. They are relatively insoluble in water and tend to adsorb to sediments and suspended particulate matter. PCBs bioaccumulate in benthic-feeding organisms and their predators and concentrate in the skin and fat of fish. Humans and wildlife are exposed to PCBs mainly through consumption of contaminated fish. Anderson Reservoir is included on the Clean Water Act Section 303(d) list as impaired for PCBs in fish (SWRCB 2017a), with four of seven samples from Anderson Reservoir fish exceeding evaluation guidelines. However, sediment PCB concentrations in Anderson Reservoir are apparently low, as PCBs have never been detected in outflow from Anderson Reservoir. Valley Water (2021f) prepared a Mercury, Diazinon, and PCBs Plan describing the potential occurrence of these contaminants in Anderson Reservoir and the means by which their concentrations would be tested during dredging for the FOCP. Monitoring and analysis of these issues were conducted pursuant to that plan in conjunction with implementation of the FOCP. In consultation with SFRWQCB staff, it was determined that no further testing is necessary, nor are any diazinon-specific control measures necessary during the implementation of the FOCP (Valley Water 2021f).

Literature indicates that California Ridgway's rail reproductive success can be adversely affected by a variety of contaminants and metals, including mercury and PCBs. When introduced to bird species through the bioweb, these contaminants may occur in the species' eggs in the South Bay (Schwarzbach et al. 2006, Ackerman et al. 2012, Casazza et al. 2014). Mercury is toxic to rail embryos and has a long biological half-life. Schwarzbach et al. (2006) found high mercury levels

and low hatching success (due both to predation and, presumably, mercury) in California Ridgway's rail eggs throughout the San Francisco Bay Estuary. Mercury contamination has also been linked to reduced body condition in California Ridgway's rails (Ackerman et al. 2012), suggesting there are detrimental effects on survivorship of adult birds as well.

Literature also shows that salt marsh harvest mice may be affected by mercury and PCBs in the intertidal zone (Clark et al. 1992). There is some potential for contaminants in Anderson Reservoir sediments to adversely affect salt marsh harvest mice. Mercury and PCBs in sediment from Anderson Reservoir could be deposited in salt marsh harvest mouse habitat, and mice may take up these contaminants through their food. Clark et al. (1992) found that salt marsh harvest mice were captured only at sites where concentrations of mercury or PCBs were below specific levels in house mice. They found mercury concentrations to be an order of magnitude higher in livers of house mice at Calaveras Point than at any other point measured in the San Francisco Bay, likely owing to mercury mobilized down the Guadalupe River/Alviso Slough system.

Although some mercury and PCBs may be mobilized in sediments from Anderson Reservoir, Valley Water (2021f) determined that concentrations of mercury in Anderson Reservoir sediments are relatively low, particularly in comparison to levels already present in the South Bay due to inputs from the Guadalupe River waters. Similarly, available monitoring data indicate low levels of diazinon and PCBs in sediments and water mobilized from Anderson Reservoir (Valley Water 2021f), and removal of fish (which bioaccumulate mercury and PCBs) from Anderson Reservoir when it is drained prior to Seismic Retrofit construction would remove much of these contaminants from the system. Therefore, no substantial adverse effects on the health or reproductive success of California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice would result from mobilization of sediment and potentially adhered contaminants from Anderson Reservoir.

Post-Construction Operations, Maintenance, and Monitoring

Post-construction operation of Anderson Dam will follow rule curves under the FAHCE Program to benefit salmonids downstream. Analysis of the effects of post-construction FAHCE operations on tidal marsh species was performed relative to the Pre-FERC Order Baseline (2017 conditions) and Water Evaluation and Planning-modeled Future Baseline (2035 conditions). FAHCE flows are not expected to result in substantial effects, either adverse or beneficial, on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mice. Flows under the FAHCE rule curves will be generally similar to those under 2017 conditions but possibly slightly lower, while FAHCE flows are likely to be slightly higher than under the Water Evaluation and Planning-modeled Future Baseline. In general, FAHCE flows may entail slightly lower flow in winter and summer, due to retention of water in the reservoir for spring pulse flows, than either the Pre-FERC Order Baseline or Future Baseline, punctuated by the spring pulse flows described above. Spring pulse releases would be of such low magnitude that they would not result in any substantial inundation, even temporarily, of habitat for the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mice; these brief flows would result in very small water surface elevation increases that are well within the normal range of tidal elevations along lower Coyote Creek and Coyote Slough. Similarly, Coyote Creek flow augmentation through the Cross Valley Pipeline Extension would not have substantive impacts on water surface elevations, relative to tidal marsh, in tidal areas because of the limited amount of such flow augmentation.

Valley Water (2022b) analyzed the potential effects of proposed FAHCE-related freshwater inputs on salinity in the South Bay. Because of the limited magnitude of FAHCE-related flows, Valley Water concluded that the natural range and frequency of freshwater flows experienced by

streams such as Coyote Creek would not change, and therefore, the ecological habitats in tidal areas downstream would not be affected substantially by these freshwater inputs. Therefore, operational flows from Anderson Dam following construction would not result in any substantial effects on tidal habitats as a result of changes in salinity.

Avoidance and Minimization Measures

Implementation of water quality AMMs will minimize the potential for hazardous materials and other pollutants to enter Coyote Creek waters and eventually be transported downstream to tidal habitats. Due to the possibility that higher flows during proposed project construction (i.e., flows exceeding the environmental baseline, post-FOCP maximum rate of 2,500 cfs) could result in increased extent, duration, or depth of inundation of tidal marsh habitat, increasing the potential for predation on California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice, Valley Water will contribute to avian and mammalian predator management activities, and high tide refugial habitat enhancement activities, in the South Bay. This measure, coupled with the benefits (potentially substantial) of increased sediment input from the proposed project on development and maintenance of the California Ridgway's rail's and salt marsh harvest mouse's tidal marsh habitat, will minimize the proposed project's adverse effects on these species.

During the construction period, winter flows downstream from Anderson Dam may be higher during storm events than under baseline conditions, potentially increasing predation risk as vegetative cover in tidal marshes is reduced by high water and California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice are less concealed from predators. Salt marsh harvest mouse nests may also be flooded during storm events since the listed mice may breed March-December and major winter storms commonly occur in December. California Ridgway's rail nests are less likely to be flooded because the rails lay their nests primarily in the spring after most major winter storm events although some nests may be initiated as early as late February or early March. Mobilization of sediment from the bed of the reservoir during construction-period storm events could lead to sediment deposition in intertidal and tidal marsh habitats used by the rail and mouse. This sediment deposition may have short-term, minor adverse effects on California Ridgway's rails by reducing prey availability and foraging efficiency and on salt marsh harvest mice by covering seeds or other plant materials on the substrate surface, reducing food availability somewhat. Contaminants mobilized with the sediment are unlikely to have a substantive effect on the health or reproductive success of California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice, especially in the context of the much larger mercury loads mobilized from the Guadalupe River watershed (not associated with the proposed project). Sediment deposition in tidal areas along Coyote Slough will have long-term beneficial effects on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse by facilitating the development of tidal marsh habitat in marsh restoration areas and helping to raise the elevation of existing marshes to keep pace with marsh loss from sea level rise. The effects of the proposed project on increasing predation risk in California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice during major storm events will be reduced by Valley Water contributing funding for control of predators and enhancement of high-tide refugia in tidal marsh habitat in the South Bay within and near the action area.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the

Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area of the proposed project. The effects of almost all private development and local public projects within the action area would be covered by and minimized and mitigated through the SCVHP. Although the SCVHP does not cover effects to the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the vast majority of actions within the tidal marsh in the South Bay would require a permit from the Corps per the Clean Water Act and/or Rivers and Harbors Act and are therefore federal actions.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander and the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to these species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual California red-legged frogs, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs, and Central California tiger salamanders; (2) BMPs will be implemented to reduce the potential for spread of amphibian diseases during steelhead relocation to Upper Penitencia Creek; (3) breeding habitat will be enhanced within the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed by removing aquatic invasive predators; and (4) the effects of SCVHP-covered activities will be mitigated by the payment of SCVHP mitigation fees that will go toward the preservation, restoration, and management of occupied California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, and Central California tiger salamander habitat in the SCVHP reserve system.

After reviewing the current status of the northwestern pond turtle, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's conference opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the northwestern pond turtle. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual northwestern pond turtles; (2) few northwestern pond turtles are likely to be adversely affected by the additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir since the species occurs there infrequently and in low numbers due to the poor quality of the aquatic habitat within the reservoir; (3) flows will be maintained in Coyote Creek downstream of Anderson Dam during construction due to bypassing flows through Anderson Dam and the release of imported water; (4) aquatic habitat will be enhanced within the Upper Penitencia Creek watershed and Coyote Creek by removing aquatic invasive predators; and (5) the effects of SCVHP-covered activities will be mitigated by the payment of SCVHP mitigation fees that will go toward the preservation, restoration, and management of occupied northwestern pond turtles habitat in the SCVHP reserve system.

After reviewing the current status of the Tiburon paintbrush, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the Tiburon paintbrush. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) no Tiburon paintbrush plants will be directly disturbed by the proposed project; (2) Valley Water will minimize the indirect effects of atmospheric nitrogen deposition on the Paintbrush Hill and Paintbrush Canyon populations of the Tiburon paintbrush by implementing a Service-approved invasive species monitoring and control plan; (3) SCVHA will preserve and manage in perpetuity a newly discovered third population of the Tiburon paintbrush at the Richmond Ranch Preserve under the SCVHP; and (4) the effects of SCVHP-covered activities will be mitigated by the payment of SCVHP mitigation fees that will go toward the preservation, restoration, and management of the Tiburon paintbrush in the SCVHP reserve system.

After reviewing the current status of the Coyote ceanothus, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the Coyote ceanothus. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on the Coyote ceanothus; (2) few Coyote ceanothus shrubs will be affected by dust from non-SCVHP covered activities during the additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir; (3) BMPs will be implemented to reduce the potential for the spread of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*; (4) the proposed project was redesigned to reduce the total number of Coyote ceanothus plants that have been (or will be) removed by all SCVHP-covered activities to 3,519 individuals at Anderson Dam which is below the 3,550 individuals estimated by the SCVHP to be directly impacted by the proposed project and the Dam Maintenance Program combined (ICF International 2012); (5) less than 2 percent of the Anderson population will be removed by all SCVHP-covered activities; (6) Valley Water is implementing a Service-approved plan for the creation of a new population of the Coyote ceanothus on Valley Water land on Coyote Ridge; and (7) the effects of SCVHP-covered activities will be mitigated by the payment of SCVHP mitigation fees that will go toward the preservation and management of five populations of the Coyote ceanothus within the SCVHP reserve system.

After reviewing the current status of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the Santa Clara Valley dudleya. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on the Santa Clara Valley dudleya; (2) few Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants will be affected by dust from

non-SCVHP covered activities during the additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir; (3) BMPs will be implemented to reduce the potential for spread of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora*; (4) no Santa Clara Valley dudleya plants will be removed by the proposed project; and (5) the effects of SCVHP-covered activities will be mitigated by the payment of SCVHP mitigation fees that will go toward the preservation and management of occupied Santa Clara Valley dudleya habitat within the SCVHP reserve system.

After reviewing the current status of the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of these species based on the following: (1) the effects of the increased risk of predation on the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse during higher flows released from Anderson Dam during proposed project construction will be minimized by Valley Water funding predator management and high-tide refugia enhancement in suitable tidal marsh habitat within and near the action area if flows from Anderson Dam exceed 2,500 cfs; (2) no suitable habitat will be directly disturbed by the proposed project; and (3) the increased rate of deposition of sediment in former salt ponds and tidal marsh habitat in the action area due to the proposed project will benefit the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse in the long-term by facilitating the development of tidal marsh habitat in marsh restoration areas and helping to raise the elevation of existing marshes to keep pace with marsh loss from sea level rise.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by FERC and the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. FERC and the Corps have a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If FERC or the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the

applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, FERC and the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Sections 7(b)(4) and 7(o)(2) of the Act generally do not apply to listed plant species. However, limited protection of listed plants from take is provided to the extent that the Act prohibits the removal and reduction to possession of federally listed endangered plants or the malicious damage of such plants on areas under federal jurisdiction, or the destruction of endangered plants on non-federal areas in violation of State law or regulation or in the course of any violation of a State criminal trespass law.

Amount or Extent of Take

California Red-legged Frog

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual California red-legged frogs will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of California red-legged frogs that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to portions of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP as the following:

1. The capture of all life stages of the California red-legged frog within the 1,492-acre proposed project footprint.
2. The harassment and harm of all life stages of the California red-legged frog within all groundwater-dependent wetlands in 1,000 acres of North Coyote Valley that are subject to dryback during one additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir.
3. The injury or mortality of two (2) adult, sub-adult, or juvenile California red-legged frogs, four (4) tadpoles, and one egg mass.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the California red-legged frog associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Central Coast Foothill Yellow-legged Frog

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the portions of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP as the following:

1. The capture of all life stages of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog within the 1,492-acre proposed project footprint.
2. The injury or mortality of two (2) adult, sub-adult, or juvenile Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frogs and four (4) tadpoles.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Central California Tiger Salamander

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual Central California tiger salamanders will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of Central California tiger salamanders that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the portions of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP as the following:

1. The capture of all life stages of the Central California tiger salamander within the 1,492-acre proposed project footprint.
2. The harassment and harm of all life stages of the Central California tiger salamander within all groundwater-dependent wetlands in 1,000 acres of North Coyote Valley that are subject to dryback during one additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir.
3. The injury or mortality of two (2) adult, sub-adult, or juvenile Central California tiger salamanders and four (4) larvae.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the Central California tiger salamander associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Northwestern Pond Turtle

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual northwestern pond turtles will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of northwestern pond turtles that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the portions of the proposed project that are not covered by the SCVHP as the following:

1. The capture of all adult and juvenile northwestern pond turtles within the 1,492-acre proposed project footprint.
2. The harassment of all adult and juvenile northwestern pond turtles during steelhead relocation activities along 0.7 mile of Upper Penitencia Creek at Alum Rock Park.

3. The harassment and harm of four (4) adult or juvenile northwestern pond turtles within Anderson Reservoir during the extra year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir.
4. The harassment and harm of all adult and juvenile northwestern pond turtles within all groundwater-dependent wetlands in 1,000 acres of North Coyote Valley that are subject to dryback during one additional year of dewatering of Anderson Reservoir.
5. The injury or mortality of four (4) adult or juvenile northwestern pond turtles.
6. The loss of one (1) northwestern pond turtle nest during refilling of Anderson Reservoir.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the northwestern pond turtle associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

California Ridgway's Rail

1. The harassment and harm of all California Ridgway's rails within 155 acres of tidal marsh habitat in the South Bay near the Coyote Creek estuary that would be subject to additional inundation if a 50-100-year flood event (5,000 cfs) were passed through Anderson Dam during one of the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction.
2. The harassment and harm of all California Ridgway's rails within 68 acres of tidal marsh habitat in the South Bay near the Coyote Creek estuary that would be subject to additional inundation if a 5-year flood event (3,000 cfs) were passed through Anderson Dam during two of the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction.
3. The injury or mortality of two (2) California Ridgway's rails due to the increased risk of predation during higher flows from Anderson Dam during proposed project construction.
4. The loss of one California Ridgway's rail nest due to flooding during higher flows from Anderson Dam during proposed project construction.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the California Ridgway's rail associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

1. The harassment and harm of all salt marsh harvest mice within 155 acres of tidal marsh habitat in the South Bay near the Coyote Creek estuary that would be subject to additional inundation if a 50-100-year flood event (5,000 cfs) were passed through Anderson Dam during one of the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction.
2. The harassment and harm of all salt marsh harvest mice within 68 acres of tidal marsh habitat in the South Bay near the Coyote Creek estuary that would be subject to additional inundation if a 5-year flood event (3,000 cfs) were passed through Anderson Dam during two of the seven years of Seismic Retrofit construction.

3. The injury or mortality of two (2) salt marsh harvest mice due to the increased risk of predation during higher flows from Anderson Dam during proposed project construction.
4. The injury or mortality of eight (8) young salt marsh harvest mice due to flooding of two (2) nests during higher flows from Anderson Dam during proposed project construction.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse associated with the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, northwestern pond turtle, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, northwestern pond turtle, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed conservation measures. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize incidental take of the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, northwestern pond turtle, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse:

- 1) All conservation measures, as described in the biological evaluation and restated here in the Description of the Proposed Action section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, FERC, or the Corps, as applicable, must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. FERC, or the Corps, as applicable, shall include full implementation and adherence to the conservation measures, as described in the biological evaluation and restated here in the Description of the Proposed Action section of this biological opinion, as a condition of any permit or contract issued for the proposed project.
2. FERC or Valley Water shall inform the Service within 30 days each time that flows from Anderson Dam exceed 2,500 cfs during Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit construction that would trigger the required funding of predator management and high-tide refugia enhancement for the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse in the South Bay. The recipient(s) of the funding and the project(s) being funded shall be reviewed

and approved by the Service. Annual reports documenting implementation and compliance shall be submitted to the Service.

Monitoring:

- a. For those components of the action that are not covered by the SCVHP that will result in habitat degradation or modification whereby incidental take in the form of harm is anticipated, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall provide a precise accounting of the total acreage of habitat impacted to the Service after completion of construction.
- b. For activities/species that are not covered by the SCVHP, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall immediately contact the Service's Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office (SFWO) at (916) 414-6623 to report direct encounters between listed species and project workers and their equipment whereby incidental take in the form of harassment, harm, injury, or death occurs. If the encounter occurs after normal working hours, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day. When injured or killed individuals of the listed species are found, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals section below.
- c. For those components of the action that are not covered by the SCVHP that will require the capture and relocation of any listed species, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall immediately contact the SFWO at (916) 414-6623 to report the action. If capture and relocation need to occur after normal working hours, FERC, the Corps, or Valley Water shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day.
- d. For activities that are not covered by the SCVHP, a post-project completion report shall be provided to the Service documenting with photographs the successful restoration of all habitats temporarily disturbed within the action area and any observations of listed species within the action area.
- e. All sightings of listed species shall be submitted to CDFW's CNDDDB.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals:

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Coast Bay Division Supervisor of the SFWO at (916) 414-6623.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) FERC and the Corps should include in their projects the control of non-native bullfrogs, non-native fish, non-native crayfish, non-native turtles and other invasive species and predators within suitable aquatic habitat for the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, and northwestern pond turtle.
- 2) FERC and the Corps should include in their projects the restoration, preservation, and management in perpetuity under a Service-approved long-term management plan suitable aquatic breeding habitat and surrounding upland habitat for the California red-legged frog, Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog, Central California tiger salamander, and aquatic habitat and basking, overwintering, and nesting habitat for the northwestern pond turtle.
- 3) FERC should maintain a natural flow regime and avoid cold water releases and spring/summer pulse flows in Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog breeding habitat downstream of dams regulated by FERC and include in dam operations the passage of winter storm flood flows that are important for creating and maintaining aquatic habitat complexity downstream.
- 4) FERC and the Corps should include in their projects the selective thinning of the riparian canopy where it is excessively shading habitat for the Central Coast foothill yellow-legged frog and northwestern pond turtle.
- 5) FERC and the Corps should include wildlife crossings for California red-legged frogs, Central California tiger salamanders, and northwestern pond turtles in their projects.
- 6) FERC and the Corps should install basking habitat and enhance nesting habitat for the northwestern pond turtle in their projects.
- 7) FERC and the Corps should report any suspected observations of turtle-shell disease in the northwestern pond turtle.
- 8) FERC and the Corps should reduce the risk of predation on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California Ridgway's rail by planting native high tide refugia cover (e.g., marsh gumplant) in suitable tidal marsh habitat.
- 9) FERC and the Corps should report sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species to the CNDDDB of the CDFW. A copy of the reporting form and a topographic map clearly marked with the location the animals were observed also should be provided to the Service.
- 10) FERC and the Corps should require the implementation of a Service-approved invasive plant species monitoring and control plan in Bay checkerspot butterfly, Coyote ceanothus, Tiburon paintbrush, and Santa Clara Valley dudleya habitat outside of the SCVHP reserve system that is indirectly affected by atmospheric nitrogen deposition from proposed project construction activities.
- 11) FERC and the Corps should include in their projects the Service's conservation recommendations for the western population of the federally proposed threatened monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*) (Service 2023c,

<https://xerces.org/publications/planning-management/western-monarch-butterfly-conservation-recommendations>).

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation and the conference on the Anderson Dam Seismic Retrofit Project. You may ask the Service to confirm the conference opinion as a biological opinion issued through formal consultation if the northwestern pond turtle is listed. The request must be in writing. If the Service reviews the proposed action and finds that there have been no significant changes in the action as planned or in the information used during the conference, the Service will confirm the conference opinion as the biological opinion on the project and no further section 7 consultation will be necessary. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16(a), reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the federal agency, where discretionary federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law, and:

- 1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- 2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- 3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or conference opinion; or
- 4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

The incidental take statement provided in this conference opinion does not become effective until the species is listed and the conference opinion is adopted as the biological opinion issued through formal consultation. At that time, the project will be reviewed to determine whether any take of the northwestern pond turtle has occurred. Modifications of the opinion and incidental take statement may be appropriate to reflect that take. No take of the northwestern pond turtle that is not covered by the SCVHP may occur between the listing of the species and the adoption of the conference opinion through formal consultation, or the completion of a subsequent formal consultation.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion or conference opinion, please contact Joseph Terry, Senior Biologist (joseph_terry@fws.gov) or at (916) 943-6721 or Ryan Olah, Coast Bay Division Supervisor (ryan_olah@fws.gov), at (916) 414-6623.

Sincerely,

Michael Fris
Field Supervisor

cc:

U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, California

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Tiffany Chao, Valley Water, San Jose, California

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